

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Factorial and Square Root

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Abstract

*This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10.000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using **factorial** and **square-root** along with basic operations. Previously, the author worked with same numbers using only basic operations. The previous work is up to number 300.000. Extending more than 10000, in some cases, we need **factorial** and/or **square-root**. For more details refer author's work [7]-[27]. Similar kind of work using **Triangular numbers**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **square function** and **cubic function** is done in another works [39, 40, 41, 43].*

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1 Introduction

First we shall give some different ways of representing natural numbers using the digits 0 to 9 or 1 to 9. See the subsections below

1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are* represented in three different types.

1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [7] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 100 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 101 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 102 &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 786 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\
 2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 10483 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\
 10549 &:= 1^2 \times 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 10550 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
 10553 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\
 10554 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer [7]-[27]. These works brings the representations of natural numbers from 1 to 300.000. Soon, we shall extend it to **half-million**, i.e., 500.000.

2 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Triangular Numbers

This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10.000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using **factorial** and **square-root** along with basic operations. Previously, the

author worked with same numbers using only basic operations. Similar kind of work using **Triangular numbers**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **square function** and **cubic function** is done in another works [39, 40, 41, 43]. Except the numbers 0 and 1, the all other numbers either have **factorial** or **square-root** or both. Without use of these two extra properties, the work is already done by author in 2014 [7]

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3) \times 456789 & 0 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6) \times 54321 \\
 1 &:= (-1 + 2)^{3456789} & 1 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 - 65 + 43 + 21 \\
 2 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2 &:= \sqrt{9} - (8 - 7)^{654321} \\
 3 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3 &:= 9 - \sqrt{8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1} \\
 4 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)!/4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 65 - 43 - 21 \\
 5 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5 &:= -9 - (8 - 7)^6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 6 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6 &:= (9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
 7 &:= -1 + 2 + \sqrt{3 - \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9} & 7 &:= \sqrt{98 \times 7 - 654 + 32} - 1 \\
 8 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/(6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 9 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9 &:= -9 \times 8/(7!/6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 10 &:= -1 + (2 - 3) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 10 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 - (6 - 5)^{43} - 2 + 1 \\
 11 &:= -(-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 11 &:= 9 + \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 12 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 12 &:= -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) - 6! + (5 + 4)^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
 13 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 13 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 54 + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 14 &:= 1 - 23 + 45 - 6 + (7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9} & 14 &:= -(-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 15 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 15 &:= 9 + \sqrt{8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1} \\
 16 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 16 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 17 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 17 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + (32 \times 1 - 6 - 54) \\
 18 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 18 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/(6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 19 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 19 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 + 4 - 3^2 - 1 \\
 20 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4 - 5 + (6 - 7)^{89} & 20 &:= \sqrt{7 \times 6 - 9 - 8} + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 21 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 21 &:= 9 + 8 + 76 + 54 - 3! \times 21 \\
 22 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 22 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 23 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 23 &:= 98 + 7 - 6!/5 + 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 24 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 24 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 25 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 25 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21} \\
 26 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 26 &:= (-9 + 87)/6 + 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21} \\
 27 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 27 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21} \\
 28 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 28 &:= 98 + 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 29 &:= 1 - 2^3 + 4! \times 5 - 67 - 8 - 9 & 29 &:= \sqrt{-9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)} \\
 30 &:= (1^{23} + 4) \times \sqrt{5! - 67 - 8 - 9} & 30 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 87)/6 + 54/3 - 2 - 1 \\
 31 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 31 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 87)/6 + (5 + 43)/(2 + 1) \\
 32 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4 + 5 - (6 - 7)^{89} & 32 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
33 &:= (1 - 2)^3 \times (45 - 67) + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
34 &:= 1^{23} - (45 - 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
35 &:= (-1 + 2)^{(3+4)!} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
36 &:= (-1 + 2)^{(3+4)!} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
37 &:= -\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
38 &:= (1 - 2)^3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
39 &:= 1^{23} \times 4 + (5! + 6!)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
40 &:= 1^{23} \times 4 \times 5 - 6 + 78/\sqrt{9} \\
41 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
42 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + 45 + 6/(7 + 8 - 9) \\
43 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
44 &:= 1 + (2 + 3! - 4 - 56) \times (7 - 8) - 9 \\
45 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
46 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
47 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/\sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
48 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times 4!/(5 + 6 - 7 + 8 - 9) \\
49 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
50 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
51 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
52 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
53 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
54 &:= 1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
55 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
56 &:= 1 - 23 + 45 + 6 - 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\
57 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
58 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
59 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
60 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
61 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
62 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
63 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
64 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)!/4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
65 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
66 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
67 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
68 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
69 &:= 1 - 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
33 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
34 &:= 9 - (8 - 7)^{65} + 4! + 3 - 2 + 1 \\
35 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
36 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (-6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
37 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 65 - 4 + 3! + 21 \\
38 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
39 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
40 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
41 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
42 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
43 &:= \sqrt{9 \times (87 - 6)} - 5 + (4 - 3) \times 21 \\
44 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 5/6! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
45 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 54 - 32 \times 1 \\
46 &:= 98 \times 6/7 + (5 - 4 \times 3!) \times 2 \times 1 \\
47 &:= \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6 - 5 + 4 + 3! \times 21 \\
48 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
49 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 + 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
50 &:= 98 - 7 - 65 + 4! + 3 - 2 - 1 \\
51 &:= 98 + 76 - 5! - 4 \times 3! + 21 \\
52 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
53 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
54 &:= 9 \times \sqrt{8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1} \\
55 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
56 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times (65 - 4! - 32 - 1) \\
57 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
58 &:= ((9 + 8 + 7)/6)! + 5 + 4!/3 + 21 \\
59 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
60 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 - 21 \\
61 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
62 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 - \sqrt{4}) + 3! + 2 \times 1 \\
63 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} - 6 + 54 - 3 - 21 \\
64 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} - 6 + 32 \times (5 - 4) - 1 \\
65 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 - 54 + 32 \times 1 \\
66 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 - 54 + 32 + 1 \\
67 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
68 &:= 98 - 7 \times 6 + 5 - 4! + 32 - 1 \\
69 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
70 &:= \sqrt{-1-2+3+4} \times (5+6+7+8+9) & 70 &:= 98-7-(65-\sqrt{43^2}-1) \\
71 &:= 12 \times (4+5)/3 + \sqrt{6!-7+8^{\sqrt{9}}} & 71 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
72 &:= 1 + 2 + 3! + 45 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 72 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 + 5 - \sqrt{4} - 3! - 2 \times 1 \\
73 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 73 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
74 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 74 &:= \sqrt{98/7 + 65 \times 43} + 21 \\
75 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 75 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!^2 \times 1 \\
76 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 76 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 + 54) - 3^2 + 1) \\
77 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 77 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
78 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 78 &:= 9 + 87 - 6 - 5 + 4! - 32 + 1 \\
79 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 79 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 54/3 + 21 \\
80 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 80 &:= 98 - 76 + 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 32 + 1 \\
81 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 81 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 32 \times 1 \\
82 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 82 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 54 \times 2/3 - 1 \\
83 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 + \sqrt{56-7} + 89 & 83 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - (6 - 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 - 1 \\
84 &:= 12 + 3! + 4! - 5 - 6 \times 7 + 89 & 84 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
85 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 85 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
86 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 86 &:= 98 + 7 - 6 \times 5/\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 + 1 \\
87 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 87 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
88 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 88 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
89 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 89 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
90 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 90 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
91 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 91 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
92 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! - 5 - 6 - 7 + 89 & 92 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
93 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - \sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 93 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
94 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 94 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
95 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 95 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
96 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 96 &:= (98 + 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 - 1) \\
97 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 97 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
98 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 98 &:= \sqrt{98/7 \times (654 + 32 \times 1)} \\
99 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 99 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3 + 21 \\
100 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 100 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 + 65 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
101 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 101 &:= 98 + 7 - 65 - \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 21 \\
102 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 102 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 43 + 2 + 1 \\
103 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 103 &:= 98 - 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3! + 21 \\
104 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 - \sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 104 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
105 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 105 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
106 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 106 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
107 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 107 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
108 &:= 1^{234} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 89 \\
109 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
110 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
111 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
112 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
113 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 89 \\
114 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! + 45) + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 \\
115 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3 - 4)! + 5 \times (6 - 7 - 8)/9 \\
116 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5 + 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
117 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5! - 6/(7 + 8 - 9) \\
118 &:= 12 + 34/\sqrt{5 + 6 - 7} + 89 \\
119 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
120 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)! \\
121 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
122 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
123 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
124 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
125 &:= 123 - (45 - 67)/(8 + \sqrt{9}) \\
126 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4!) + 56 - 7 \times (8 - 9) \\
127 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
128 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
129 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
130 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
131 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
132 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
133 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
134 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
135 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
136 &:= (12 + 3!) \times 4 - 5 + 67 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\
137 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
138 &:= 123 - 4 - 56 + 78 - \sqrt{9} \\
139 &:= 12 - 3^4 + 5! + 6 - 7 + 89 \\
140 &:= 123 + 4! - 56/7 - 8 + 9 \\
141 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
142 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
143 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + \sqrt{4})!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
144 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
145 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
146 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
108 &:= 9 \times (\sqrt{8 + 7 - 6 - 5} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
109 &:= -9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
110 &:= 98 - (7 - 6 \times 5/\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 + 1) \\
111 &:= (\sqrt{9} - 87)/6 - 5 + 4 + 3! \times 21 \\
112 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
113 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
114 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
115 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
116 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5) + (4! + 3!) \times 2 - 1 \\
117 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
118 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
119 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 65 + (4! + 3!) \times 2 \times 1 \\
120 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)^6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
121 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
122 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
123 &:= 98 - ((7 + 65)/4!)! + 32 - 1 \\
124 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
125 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
126 &:= 9 \times 87 - 654 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
127 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
128 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
129 &:= -9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
130 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7!/6! + 54 + 3! \times 2 - 1 \\
131 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
132 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
133 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
134 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
135 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
136 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
137 &:= 9 \times 876/54 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
138 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
139 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
140 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
141 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
142 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
143 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6! \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
144 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 - 5 + 4 \times 3! \times (2 + 1) \\
145 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 - (6 - 5! - 4^3 + 21) \\
146 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3! + 2) + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
147 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
148 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
149 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
150 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
151 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
152 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
153 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
154 &:= 123 + 4! + 56/7 + 8 - 9 \\
155 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
156 &:= (12 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6) \times 78/9 \\
157 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
158 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
159 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
160 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
161 &:= -1 - 2 + ((3 + 4)! - 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
162 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 - 4 + 5)! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
163 &:= (12 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + 56 + 78/\sqrt{9} \\
164 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
165 &:= -1 + 2 + ((3 + 4)! - 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
166 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
167 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
168 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
169 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
170 &:= -1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4)! + 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
171 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
172 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
173 &:= -1 + 2 + ((3 + 4)! + 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
174 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + \sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
175 &:= 1 \times (2 - 3!!) + (45 + 67) \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
176 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
177 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
178 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
179 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
180 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
181 &:= (12 - 3! \times 4! - 56 + 7) \times (8 - 9) \\
182 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
183 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
147 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
148 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
149 &:= 9 \times 876/54 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
150 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
151 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
152 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
153 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
154 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
155 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
156 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
157 &:= \sqrt{9} + (32 \times 1 - 8 + 76 + 54) \\
158 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
159 &:= -9 + 8 \times (\sqrt{7 - 6 + 5!} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
160 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7 + 6 + 54 \times 3/2 - 1} \\
161 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times \sqrt{6!/5} - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
162 &:= (98 + 76 - 5!) \times (4 \times 3! - 21) \\
163 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7 - 6 + 54 + 3^{2+1}} \\
164 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
165 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) - 54 - 32 - 1 \\
166 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
167 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
168 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
169 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
170 &:= 98 \times 6!/(7 \times 5!) + 43 \times 2 \times 1 \\
171 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 - 21) \\
172 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
173 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + \sqrt{6!/5}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
174 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4!)) - 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
175 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
176 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
177 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
178 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
179 &:= (\sqrt{9})!!/8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 43 \times 2 - 1 \\
180 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 54 - 3 + 21 \\
181 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times \sqrt{6!/5} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
182 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
183 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$184 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$185 := 1^2 - 3 \times 4 + 5! - 6 - 7 + 89$$

$$186 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$187 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$188 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$189 := -1 + (2 + 3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$190 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$191 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$192 := (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$193 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$194 := 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$195 := 12 - 34 + 5! + 6! - 7 \times 89$$

$$196 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$197 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$198 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$199 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$200 := 1 \times 2 - 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) + 9$$

$$201 := -1 - 2 + 3!! / 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$202 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$203 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$204 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! / 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$205 := -1 - 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$206 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$207 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! / (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$208 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! / (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$209 := -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$210 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / 4$$

$$211 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! / (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$212 := -1 - 2 + 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$213 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$214 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$215 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$216 := -1 + 2 + 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$217 := (1 + 2)! + 34 \times 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$218 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$219 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! / (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$220 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$221 := 12/3 + 4^5 - 6! - 78 - 9$$

$$184 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$185 := 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3)^2 \times 1$$

$$186 := (\sqrt{9})!! - (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! - 4) \times \sqrt{3^2} \times 1$$

$$187 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$188 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!} / 6!$$

$$189 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$190 := 98 + 76 + 5 - 4 - 3! + 21$$

$$191 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$192 := (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$193 := ((9 - 8)^7! - 6) \times (5 - 43) + 2 + 1$$

$$194 := 98 - (7 - 6)^5 + 4 \times (3! - 2)! + 1$$

$$195 := \sqrt{9} \times (87 - 65) + 43 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$196 := -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$197 := 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$198 := 98 + (7 - 6)^5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - 21$$

$$199 := 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! / 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$200 := 98 \times 6/7 + 5! - 4 - 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$201 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$202 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$203 := 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$204 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$205 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$206 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$207 := (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3 - 21$$

$$208 := \sqrt{9} \times 87 - (65 - 4 - 3^2 + 1)$$

$$209 := 9 + 87 - 6 + 5! - 4 + 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$210 := (-9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$211 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$212 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$213 := 987 - 654 - (3 \times 2 - 1)!$$

$$214 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!})$$

$$215 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) \times 65 + \sqrt{4} - 3 + 21$$

$$216 := 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3! + 21)$$

$$217 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$218 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$219 := 98 - 7! \times 5/6 + 4321$$

$$220 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (-5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$221 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
222 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
223 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
224 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
225 &:= (1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
226 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
227 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
228 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
229 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
230 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
231 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
232 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
233 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
234 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
235 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
236 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
237 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
238 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
239 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
240 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
241 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
242 &:= (1 - 2)^3 \times (45 - 67) \times (8 + \sqrt{9}) \\
243 &:= 1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
244 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
245 &:= (1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
246 &:= -(-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
247 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
248 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
249 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
250 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 56 + 78 - 9 \\
251 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
252 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
253 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!)/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
254 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
255 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
256 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
257 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
258 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
259 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
260 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
222 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 - 4! \times (3! + 21) \\
223 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
224 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
225 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
226 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
227 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
228 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
229 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 - 5 \times 4 - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
230 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4 - 3!)^2 - 1 \\
231 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
232 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4 - 3!)^2 + 1 \\
233 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5/6!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
234 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
235 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 + 65) - \sqrt{4} - 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
236 &:= 98 - 7 - 65 + (4 + 3!) \times 21 \\
237 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2)! - 1 \\
238 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/(6! \times 5) \\
239 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
240 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
241 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) - 65 - 4! + 321 \\
242 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6!)/5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
243 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
244 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3/(2 + 1))! \\
245 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
246 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
247 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
248 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4^3 - 21 \\
249 &:= 987 - 6! + 5 - 4! + 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
250 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
251 &:= 9 + 87 - 6 + 5! + 43 - 2 \times 1 \\
252 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6! + 5!))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
253 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5/6!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
254 &:= (9 - 8)^7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times 32 - 1 \\
255 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - \sqrt{6!/5} - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
256 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
257 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + \sqrt{6! + 5 + 4}) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
258 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
259 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6!/5 + 4 + 32 \times 1 \\
260 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
261 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
262 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
263 &:= -1 - 2^3 \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
264 &:= -1 \times 2^3 \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
265 &:= 1 - ((2 - 34) \times 5 - 6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9} \\
266 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
267 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
268 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
269 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
270 &:= (12 + 3)^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 + 67 - 8 - 9 \\
271 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
272 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
273 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
274 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
275 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
276 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
277 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
278 &:= (-1 + 2^3) \times \sqrt{4} + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
279 &:= 1 + 234 + 56 - 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
280 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 + \sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
281 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
282 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/(4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
283 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
284 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
285 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 - 4 + 56) \times (7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
286 &:= (1^2 \times 3! - 4) \times (56 + 78 + 9) \\
287 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
288 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
289 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
290 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
291 &:= ((1 + 2)! - 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 - 7) - 8 + 9) \\
292 &:= (1 \times 2 \times 3 - 4) \times 5! + 6 \times 78/9 \\
293 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
294 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
295 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
296 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
297 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
298 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
261 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6 - 54 + 321 \\
262 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6!)/5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
263 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/(-5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
264 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
265 &:= 98 + 7 + (6!/5 - 4^3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
266 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
267 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 65 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
268 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
269 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
270 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5! - 4! + 32 + 1 \\
271 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
272 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
273 &:= 9 + 8 + 76 + 54 + 3! \times 21 \\
274 &:= 9 + 87 - 6 + 5! + 43 + 21 \\
275 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times \sqrt{4} - 3! + 21 \\
276 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (54 - 3! + 21)/6 \\
277 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
278 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 43 \times 2 + 1 \\
279 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 + (7 + 65) \times 4 - 32 - 1 \\
280 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
281 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times (65 + 4) + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
282 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
283 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!/4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
284 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!)/((6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
285 &:= 98 - 76 + 5! + (4 \times 3)^2 - 1 \\
286 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
287 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
288 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
289 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
290 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5! + 4! + 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
291 &:= 987 - 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
292 &:= (987 - 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2) \times 1 \\
293 &:= 987 - 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
294 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
295 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3^2 \times 1 \\
296 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
297 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
298 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5) + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
299 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
300 &:= (1 + 2)! + 3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
301 &:= 12 + 3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
302 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
303 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
304 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
305 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3! - 4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
306 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
308 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
309 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
310 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
311 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
312 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
313 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
314 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
315 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times \sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
316 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
317 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
318 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
319 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
320 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
321 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
322 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
323 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!/\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
324 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!/4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
325 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
326 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
327 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
328 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
329 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
330 &:= (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
331 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!/4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
332 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
333 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
334 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!/4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
335 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
336 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
299 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
300 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
301 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
302 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
303 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
304 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
305 &:= (9 - 8 - 7) \times 65 - (4 - 3!! + 21) \\
306 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
307 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 - \sqrt{6!/5} - 4 + 321 \\
308 &:= (98 - 76) \times (5 \times 4 - (3! - 2 - 1)!) \\
309 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + 6) - 5 + 4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
310 &:= 9 \times (876 + 54)/(3! + 21) \\
311 &:= 98 + (7 \times 6 + 5!/4) \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
312 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 43 \times (2 + 1)! \\
313 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
314 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
315 &:= 9 \times 8 + (76 + 5) \times \sqrt{4 + 3 \times 2 - 1} \\
316 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
317 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
318 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
319 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
320 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 65 + 4! \times (3 \times 2 - 1) \\
321 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (5 \times 4 + 87 - 6 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
322 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
323 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
324 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!} \\
325 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
326 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 43) + 21 \\
327 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
328 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5!) \\
329 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
330 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6)!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
331 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times 6!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
332 &:= 9 - 87 + 65 + 4! + 321 \\
333 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
334 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!} \\
335 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
336 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + (54 \times 3! - 2) \times 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
337 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
338 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
339 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
340 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
341 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
342 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
343 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5!)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
344 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
345 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
346 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
347 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
348 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
349 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
350 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
351 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
352 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
353 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
354 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
355 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
356 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
357 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
358 &:= 123 + 4^5 - 6! - 78 + 9 \\
359 &:= 1 - 2 \times (34 - 5! - 6 - 78 - 9) \\
360 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
361 &:= ((1 + 2)! + 3 + 4 - 5 + 6 + 7!)/(8 + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
362 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
363 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
364 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
365 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
366 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
367 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
368 &:= (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3})^{4+5} - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
369 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 - 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
370 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
371 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
372 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
373 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4!)/\sqrt{5!}/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
374 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
375 &:= (1 + 2 - 3!) \times 45 + 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
337 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
338 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/\sqrt{6!}/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
339 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
340 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! \times 5/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
341 &:= 9 + 8 + 6 \times 54 + 7 - 3! - 2 + 1 \\
342 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 - 21) \\
343 &:= -9 - 8 - 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
344 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
345 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
346 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
347 &:= 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3!^{2+1} \\
348 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
349 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
350 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
351 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 54 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
352 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 \times 5 - \sqrt{4} - 3! - 21 \\
353 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
354 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
355 &:= 98 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3/(2 + 1) \\
356 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
357 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
358 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
359 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
360 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!/6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
361 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
362 &:= -9 \times 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
363 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
364 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
365 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 65 + 4! \times 3! + 21 \\
366 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
367 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
368 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
369 &:= (9 - (8 - 7)^6) \times (54 - 3! - 2) + 1 \\
370 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! + 6!)/5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
371 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) - \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2 \times 1) \\
372 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
373 &:= 9 - 87 + 6 + 5! + 4 + 321 \\
374 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7!/6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
375 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 - 6 - 5!/4 + 321
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
376 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
377 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
378 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
379 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
380 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
381 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
382 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
383 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
384 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
385 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
386 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
387 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
388 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
389 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
390 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
391 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
392 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
393 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
394 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
395 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
396 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
397 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
398 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
399 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
400 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
401 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
402 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
403 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
404 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
405 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
406 &:= 12 \times (34 + 5) - 67 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
407 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! / 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) \\
408 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + 4!) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
409 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! / 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
410 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
411 &:= 12 \times 3^4 + 5! - 678 - \sqrt{9} \\
412 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
413 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
376 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
377 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + (65 - 4) \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
378 &:= 987 - 6! + 5! - 4! / 3 - 2 + 1 \\
379 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
380 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
381 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 - 6 + 5! - 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
382 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
383 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
384 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! / 6) \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
385 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!) / 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
386 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
387 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6 + 5) + 43 \times (2 + 1) \\
388 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)! / 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
389 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 65 + 4! \times (3! + 2) + 1 \\
390 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
391 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) + \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2 \times 1) \\
392 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
393 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / \sqrt{6! / 5} - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
394 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4 / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
395 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 76 - 5! - \sqrt{4} + 321 \\
396 &:= (98 / 7 - 6 - 5! / 4) \times (3 - 21) \\
397 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
398 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
399 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / (6 + 5!) \\
400 &:= (9 - 8 + 7! / 6!) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
401 &:= 9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
402 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6!) / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
403 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
404 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5^{4! / (3+2+1)} \\
405 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5 + 432 - 1 \\
406 &:= 9 \times (8 + (7! - 6!) / 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
407 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
408 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
409 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
410 &:= 98 / 7 + 6! - (54 / 3)^2 \times 1 \\
411 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
412 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
413 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / \sqrt{6! / 5} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
414 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 414 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
415 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 415 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 5 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + 43 \times 2 + 1 \\
416 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 416 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
417 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3! \times 4! + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 417 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (-4 \times 3 + 87 + 65) - 2 - 1 \\
418 &:= 12 \times 4/3 - 5! + 6 \times (78 + 9) & 418 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
419 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 419 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
420 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/\sqrt{4} & 420 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
421 &:= 1 - (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 421 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! \times 5/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
422 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 422 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
423 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 423 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
424 &:= 1^2 - 3! - 45 + 6 \times (8 \times 9 + 7) & 424 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
425 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 425 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
426 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 426 &:= 98 \times 6 \times 5/7 + 4 + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
427 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 427 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
428 &:= -1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4)! + 5!)/\sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} & 428 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
429 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 429 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
430 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 430 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 65 - 4! - 3! + 21 \\
431 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times (4 + 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 431 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
432 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 432 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
433 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 433 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
434 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!)/(5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 434 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
435 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!!/4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 435 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
436 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times \sqrt{4+5}} + 6 + 7 - 89 & 436 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
437 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 437 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
438 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 438 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
439 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 439 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
440 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 440 &:= ((9 - 8)^{76} + 54) \times (3! + 2 \times 1) \\
441 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 441 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
442 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 442 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 + \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!}) \\
443 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 443 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
444 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 444 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
445 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 445 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
446 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 446 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
447 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 447 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 + 432 - 1 \\
448 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 448 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
449 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 449 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
450 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 450 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
451 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 451 &:= 9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
452 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 452 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
453 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
454 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
455 &:= 1 \times (234 + 5 + 6! - 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\
456 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
457 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
458 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
459 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
460 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
461 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4^{5! / (6+7+8+9)} \\
462 &:= 1 + 23 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 - (7 + 8) / \sqrt{9} \\
463 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
464 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4^{5! / (6+7+8+9)} \\
465 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4^{5! / (6+7+8+9)} \\
466 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
467 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
468 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - \sqrt{4}) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
469 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
470 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
471 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
472 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
473 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
474 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
475 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
476 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
477 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
478 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
479 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
480 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
481 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
482 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! / (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
483 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
484 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times 4 + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
485 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
486 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
487 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + \sqrt{4}) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
488 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6 \\
489 &:= (12 - 3!) \times 4! - 5 \times (6! - 789) \\
490 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
491 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
453 &:= 987 - 654 + (3 \times 2 - 1)! \\
454 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
455 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
456 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
457 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
458 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
459 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) + (4! + 3!) \times 2 - 1 \\
460 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6 - 5) + (-4! + 3!) / (2 + 1) \\
461 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
462 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
463 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
464 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
465 &:= \sqrt{9} - (8 \times (7 - 65) - (4 - 3 - 2) + 1) \\
466 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!) / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
467 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
468 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} \times 6 + 5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
469 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) + 4! \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
470 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) / 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
471 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) + 4! \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\
472 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
473 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
474 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
475 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
476 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6! / 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
477 &:= \sqrt{9} + (87 - 6) \times 5 + 4! \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
478 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!) / (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
479 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
480 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6! / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
481 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
482 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
483 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7 + 6)! - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
484 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
485 &:= 9 - (8 - 76) \times (54 / 3! - 2) \times 1 \\
486 &:= ((98 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
487 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
488 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
489 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
490 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
491 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$492 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$493 := -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$494 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$495 := -1 + ((2 + 3)!) + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$496 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)!) + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$497 := -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$498 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$499 := 1 - 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$500 := (-1 + 2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$501 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$502 := -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$503 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$504 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$505 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$506 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4^{5! / (6+7+8+9)})$$

$$507 := -1 - 2 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$508 := (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$509 := -1 + (2 + 3! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$510 := (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$511 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$512 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!)$$

$$513 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$514 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$515 := (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$516 := (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$517 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$518 := -1 - 2 - 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$519 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$520 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$521 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$522 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$523 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$524 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$525 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$526 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$527 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$528 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$529 := -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$492 := (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$493 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!)!$$

$$494 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$495 := 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) - 5! + 4! + 32 + 1$$

$$496 := (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$497 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$498 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5!$$

$$499 := -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$500 := \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (7 - 6 + 54) + 3 + 2 \times 1}$$

$$501 := 9 - 8 - (7 - 65 - (4! - 3)^2 - 1)$$

$$502 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$503 := 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5^{\sqrt{4}} - 321$$

$$504 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$505 := (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$506 := -9 + 8 + (7! + 6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$507 := (9 + 8 + 76 - 54) \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$$

$$508 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$509 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) - \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$510 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$511 := 98 \times 7 - 6 - (5 + 4! / 3)^2 \times 1$$

$$512 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$513 := (\sqrt{9})! \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 \times 43 - 2 \times 1$$

$$514 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$515 := -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$516 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$517 := 9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$518 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$519 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$520 := (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$521 := 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4 + 3! + 21$$

$$522 := 9 + 87 \times 6 - \sqrt{54 + 3^{2+1}}$$

$$523 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$524 := (-9 + 8 - (7! + 6!) / 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$525 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$526 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5! / 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$527 := 9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$528 := (9 - 8 + 7 + 6! / (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$529 := -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$530 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! / (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$531 := -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$532 := -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$533 := (1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$534 := ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / 5!$$

$$535 := -1 - 2^{3!} - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$536 := -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$537 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$538 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$539 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$540 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$541 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$542 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! / (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$543 := -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$544 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$545 := 1^2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$546 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$547 := -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$548 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$549 := -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$550 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$551 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$552 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$553 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$554 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!} \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$555 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$556 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$557 := -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$558 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$559 := -1 - (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$560 := (1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$561 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$562 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$563 := -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$564 := -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$565 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$566 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$567 := -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$568 := -1 + 2 - 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$530 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! / 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$531 := (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5! - 4 - \sqrt{3^2} \times 1$$

$$532 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$533 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5) / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$534 := (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! - 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$535 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$536 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! / 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$537 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$538 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$539 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$540 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 54 \times (3 + 2 \times 1)$$

$$541 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$542 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$543 := -9 - 8 - 7! / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$544 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5^{4! / (3 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$545 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$546 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!) / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$547 := -9 - 8 + (7! + 6! - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$548 := -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! / 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$549 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$550 := (98 - 7) \times 6 - (5 - \sqrt{4^3} - 2) - 1$$

$$551 := 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$552 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!) / (6 + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$553 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$554 := -9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 / 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$555 := 98 + 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 21$$

$$556 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$557 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! / (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$558 := 9 \times (8 \times 7 + (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))!$$

$$559 := -9 + 8 - 7! / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$560 := (-9 + 8) \times 7! / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$561 := 9 - 8 + 7! / (-6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$562 := -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$563 := -9 + 8 + (7! + 6! - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$564 := (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$565 := 98 \times 7 - 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 / (2 + 1)$$

$$566 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6! / 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$567 := -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$568 := (-9 \times 8 - 7!) / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
569 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 569 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
570 &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 570 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
571 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 571 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
572 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 572 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
573 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 573 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
574 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 574 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
575 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4!) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 575 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
576 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 576 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
577 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 577 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
578 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 578 &:= \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6 + 5^4 + 32 - 1 \\
579 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 579 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
580 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 580 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6! + 5 \times (4 - 32) \times 1 \\
581 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 581 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
582 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 582 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
583 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 583 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
584 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 584 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
585 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 585 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 54 + 3! \times 21 \\
586 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 586 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
587 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 587 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
588 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 588 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
589 &:= (1 + 2)!! - 3! - 4 - 56 + 7 - 8 \times 9 & 589 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
590 &:= 123 - 4! + 5 + 6 \times (78 + \sqrt{9}) & 590 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 5/6 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
591 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 591 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5!) + 4! \times (3! + 2) - 1 \\
592 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 592 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7!/6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
593 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 593 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
594 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 594 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
595 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 595 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
596 &:= 1 - 2 - 3! - (4 - 56 - 7 - 8) \times 9 & 596 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
597 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 597 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
598 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 598 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
599 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 599 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
600 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 600 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
601 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 601 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
602 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 602 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
603 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 603 &:= 9 - 8 \times (7 - 65) + 4 + 3! \times 21 \\
604 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 604 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
605 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 605 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
606 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 606 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
607 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 607 &:= 9 \times (8 + 76) - 5! + 4 - 32 - 1 \\
608 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - (4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 608 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
609 &:= (1 + 23) \times 45 - 6 \times 78 - \sqrt{9} \\
610 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
611 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
612 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (\sqrt{4} \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
613 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! / (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
614 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
615 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
616 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5 - 678 - 9 \\
617 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
618 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
619 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
620 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
621 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
622 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
623 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
624 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
625 &:= (-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))^{5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
626 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
627 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
628 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
629 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
630 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
631 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
632 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
633 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
634 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
635 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
636 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
637 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! - 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
638 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
639 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
640 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
641 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
642 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
643 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
644 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3^4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
645 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
646 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
647 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / 5! \\
609 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
610 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
611 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + (54 + 3) \times 2 - 1 \\
612 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
613 &:= (9 + 8) \times (6 \times 5 + 7) - \sqrt{4^3} \times 2 \times 1 \\
614 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
615 &:= 98 \times (7 - 6 + 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 21 \\
616 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
617 &:= (9 \times (8 - 76) - 5) \times (4 - 3!) / 2 \times 1 \\
618 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 + 4! \times (3 - 2 + 1) \\
619 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
620 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
621 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! + 5!)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
622 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
623 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
624 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
625 &:= 98 + 7 + 65 \times 4! / (3 \times (2 - 1)) \\
626 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
627 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
628 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
629 &:= 98 - 76 - (5! - 4 - 3!! - 2 - 1) \\
630 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
631 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 87 \times 6 + 5! - \sqrt{43 + 21} \\
632 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! / (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
633 &:= 9 - 87 + 6! - 5 + 4 - 3^2 + 1 \\
634 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
635 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
636 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
637 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
638 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
639 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
640 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
641 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
642 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
643 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
644 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
645 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 87 \times 6 + (5 + 4 - 3) \times 21 \\
646 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
647 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
648 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
649 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
650 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
651 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
652 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
653 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
654 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
655 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
656 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5!))! \\
657 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
658 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
659 &:= (1 + 23) \times 4! - 5 + 6 - 7 + 89 \\
660 &:= 1 - 23 + \sqrt{(4 + 5)^6} - 7 \times 8 + 9 \\
661 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
662 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
663 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
664 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
665 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
666 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
667 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
668 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
669 &:= 1 + 2 - 3 - 45 + 6! - 7 - 8 + 9 \\
670 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
671 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
672 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
673 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
674 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
675 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
676 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
677 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
678 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
679 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
680 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
681 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
682 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
683 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
684 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
685 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
686 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
648 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
649 &:= 9 \times (8 + 76 + 54 + 3!)/2 + 1 \\
650 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
651 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 - 65 + 43 + (2 + 1)!! \\
652 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
653 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
654 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
655 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 - 5 + 4! + 3! \times 21 \\
656 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
657 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
658 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
659 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
660 &:= (98 - 76) \times 5!/(4 + 3 - 2 - 1) \\
661 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (4 \times 3 \times 2 + 87 - 6 + 5) + 1 \\
662 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
663 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
664 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
665 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
666 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
667 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
668 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
669 &:= 987 + (6 + 5 - 4^3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
670 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
671 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
672 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
673 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
674 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
675 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 + (5 - 4)^3 - (2 + 1)! \\
676 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
677 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
678 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
679 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
680 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4 + 32 - 1 \\
681 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
682 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
683 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
684 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
685 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4^3} + 2 \times 1 \\
686 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
687 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
688 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
689 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
690 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
691 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
692 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
693 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
694 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
695 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
696 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
697 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
698 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
699 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) + \sqrt{4} + 5 + 678 + 9 \\
700 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
701 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
702 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4!/5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
703 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
704 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
705 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
706 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
707 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
708 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
709 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
710 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
711 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
712 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
713 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
714 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5)! \\
715 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
716 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
717 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!! \\
718 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!! \\
719 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
720 &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3) - 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)! \\
721 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!! \\
722 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
723 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5)! \\
724 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5)! \\
725 &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3) - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
726 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
687 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 + (5 - 4)^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
688 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
689 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
690 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
691 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
692 &:= -9 \times 8/(7 + 6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
693 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
694 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
695 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
696 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
697 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
698 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
699 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
700 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
701 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
702 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
703 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
704 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
705 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!)/6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
706 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
707 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
708 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
709 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
710 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
711 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
712 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
713 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
714 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
715 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
716 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
717 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
718 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
719 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
720 &:= (9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
721 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
722 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
723 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
724 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
725 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
726 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
727 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! \times (4 - 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
728 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
729 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
730 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
731 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
732 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
733 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
734 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
735 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
736 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
737 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
738 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
739 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
740 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
741 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
742 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
743 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
744 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! / 4)! + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
745 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! / 4)! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
746 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
747 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
748 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
749 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
750 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
751 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
752 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
753 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4 - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
754 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
755 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! / 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
756 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
757 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
758 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
759 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
760 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
761 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
762 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
763 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
764 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
765 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
766 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
727 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
728 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
729 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
730 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
731 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
732 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6!)! + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
733 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
734 &:= -9 \times 8 / (7 - 6 - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
735 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6!)! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
736 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
737 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) / 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
738 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
739 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
740 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
741 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
742 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
743 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
744 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 / (5 + 4))! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
745 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
746 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
747 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! + 5!)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
748 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
749 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
750 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
751 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
752 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
753 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! / 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
754 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
755 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
756 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
757 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
758 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! \times 5! / 6! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
759 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
760 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 76 + 5 \times 4 + 3!! / 2 \times 1 \\
761 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
762 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
763 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
764 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
765 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
766 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$767 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$768 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$769 := -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$770 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$771 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$772 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$773 := -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$774 := (1^{23} + \sqrt{4}) \times 5! + 6 \times (78 - 9)$$

$$775 := -1 - 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$776 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$777 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$778 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$779 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$780 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$781 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$782 := (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$783 := -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$784 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$785 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$786 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$787 := -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$788 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$789 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$790 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$791 := -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$792 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$793 := (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$794 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$795 := 1 + 23 - \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6 + 789$$

$$796 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$797 := -1 - ((2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$798 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$799 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$800 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$801 := 1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$802 := 12 \times 3 \times 4! - 56 - 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$803 := -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$804 := -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$805 := (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$806 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$767 := 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 \times \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1$$

$$768 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$769 := 9 + 8 + 7 + 6! + (5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$770 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$771 := -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$772 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$773 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$774 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$775 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$776 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$777 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$778 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$779 := -9 + 8 - (7 \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$780 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5!$$

$$781 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$782 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$783 := -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$784 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$785 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$786 := -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$787 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$788 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$789 := -9 + 8 + 7!/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$790 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$791 := -9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$792 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$793 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$794 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$795 := 9 \times (87 + 6 - 5) - (\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2) \times 1$$

$$796 := -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$797 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$798 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$799 := (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!)/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$800 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$801 := 98/7 + 6! + 5 + 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$802 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$803 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$804 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$805 := 98/7 + 6! + 5 + 4^3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$806 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
807 &:= 1 + 234 + 567 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
808 &:= (1 \times 23 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 78)/9 \\
809 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
810 &:= 12^3/\sqrt{4} - (5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\
811 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! \times (45 - 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
812 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
813 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
814 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
815 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
816 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
817 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
818 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
819 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
820 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
821 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
822 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
823 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
824 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
825 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
826 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
827 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
828 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
829 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
830 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
831 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
832 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
833 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
834 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
835 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
836 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5!)/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
837 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
838 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
839 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
840 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
841 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
842 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
843 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
844 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
845 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
846 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
807 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
808 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
809 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
810 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
811 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
812 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/(6 \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
813 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
814 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
815 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 54/3 - 2 \times 1 \\
816 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
817 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
818 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
819 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 - 4! - 3! - 21 \\
820 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
821 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
822 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
823 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
824 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
825 &:= 987 - 6 - 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (3 - 21) \\
826 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
827 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
828 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
829 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
830 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
831 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
832 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
833 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
834 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
835 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
836 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
837 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
838 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
839 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
840 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7!/(6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
841 &:= 9 - 8 + 7!/6 - (5 - 4)^{32} + 1 \\
842 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
843 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
844 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
845 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
846 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
847 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
848 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5!)/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
849 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
850 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
851 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
852 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
853 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
854 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
855 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
856 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
857 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
858 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
859 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
860 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
861 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
862 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
863 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
864 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
865 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
866 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
867 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
868 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
869 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
870 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
871 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
872 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
873 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
874 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
875 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
876 &:= (1 + 2)^3 \times \sqrt{4^5} - 6 + 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
877 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
878 &:= 12 \times 4 \times 56/3 - 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
879 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
880 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
881 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
882 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
883 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
884 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
885 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
847 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
848 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6 \times (5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
849 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
850 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
851 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
852 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!)/(6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
853 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
854 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
855 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 54 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
856 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
857 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
858 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
859 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
860 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6! - 5 \times (4 - 32) \times 1 \\
861 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) + \sqrt{4} + 3 - 21 \\
862 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
863 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
864 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
865 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
866 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
867 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
868 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
869 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
870 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7!/6! + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
871 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
872 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
873 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6!) \\
874 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
875 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
876 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
877 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
878 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
879 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
880 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
881 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
882 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
883 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + (6 + 5) \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
884 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
885 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
886 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
887 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
888 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
889 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
890 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
891 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
892 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
893 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
894 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
895 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
896 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
897 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
898 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
899 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
900 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4 \\
901 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
902 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
903 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
904 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
905 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
906 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
907 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
908 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
909 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
910 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
911 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
912 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
913 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
914 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
915 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
916 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
917 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
918 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
919 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!/4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
920 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
921 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
922 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
923 &:= (1^2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (56 - 78 + 9) \\
924 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
925 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
886 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
887 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
888 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
889 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
890 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4! \\
891 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
892 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
893 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
894 &:= 9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
895 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1!) \\
896 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
897 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
898 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
899 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 - 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
900 &:= 9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 \times (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
901 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
902 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
903 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
904 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
905 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
906 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
907 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
908 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
909 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
910 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
911 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
912 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! - 4! + 32 - 1 \\
913 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
914 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
915 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
916 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
917 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
918 &:= -9 \times (8 - ((7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
919 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
920 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
921 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 + 4! + 3! + 21 \\
922 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
923 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
924 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
925 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
926 &:= 12 \times 3 \times 4! + 56 + 7 + 8 - 9 \\
927 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
928 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
929 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
930 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
931 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
932 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
933 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
934 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
935 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
936 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
937 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
938 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
939 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
940 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
941 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
942 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
943 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
944 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
945 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
946 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
947 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
948 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)!/(4 \times 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
949 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
950 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
951 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
952 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
953 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
954 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
955 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4)/5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
956 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
957 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
958 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
959 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
960 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
961 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
962 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
963 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
964 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
926 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
927 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7!/6 + 5! - 4^3/2 - 1 \\
928 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
929 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/((6 - 5) \times 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
930 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
931 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
932 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
933 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
934 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!)/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
935 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
936 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
937 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
938 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
939 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
940 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 54 \times 3 - 21 \\
941 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 21) \\
942 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
943 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
944 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
945 &:= \sqrt{9} + 876 + 54 + 3! \times 2 \times 1 \\
946 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
947 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
948 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
949 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
950 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!/5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
951 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
952 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7!/6! - 5)^{4+3+2+1} \\
953 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
954 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7!/6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
955 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
956 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
957 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
958 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
959 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
960 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4 - 3 + 21 \\
961 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
962 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
963 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
964 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
965 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
966 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
967 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
968 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times (4! + 5!)/(6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
969 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
970 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
971 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + \sqrt{4^5} \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
972 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (\sqrt{4} - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
973 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
974 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
975 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
976 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
977 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
978 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)!/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
979 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
980 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
981 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
982 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
983 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
984 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
985 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
986 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
987 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
988 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
989 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
990 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
991 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
992 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
993 &:= 1 + 23 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
994 &:= (1 + 2)!! - 3! + \sqrt{4} \times 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})! \\
995 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
996 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
997 &:= ((1 \times 2)^3 + 4 + 5) \times (67 - 8) - (\sqrt{9})! \\
998 &:= 1 \times (2 + 345 + 6! - 78 + 9) \\
999 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1000 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1001 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
965 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
966 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
967 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
968 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
969 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
970 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5) \times \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
971 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
972 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
973 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
974 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
975 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
976 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
977 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
978 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
979 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
980 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
981 &:= 987 + 6 - 5 - 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
982 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
983 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
984 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
985 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
986 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! - 43 + 21 \\
987 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
988 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
989 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
990 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
991 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
992 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
993 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
994 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
995 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
996 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
997 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
998 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
999 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1000 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5^4 + \sqrt{3^2 \times 1} \\
1001 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$1002 := (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1003 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4)/5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1004 := 1 \times 23 + 4^5 - 67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1005 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1006 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1007 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1008 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1009 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1010 := -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1011 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1012 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1013 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1014 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1015 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1016 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!/6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1017 := -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1018 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1019 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1020 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1021 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1022 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1023 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4}/5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1024 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)}$$

$$1025 := (-1 - 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1026 := (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1027 := -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1028 := (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1029 := -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1030 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1031 := -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1032 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1033 := -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1034 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1035 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1036 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1037 := -1 + (2 + 3 + \sqrt{4})!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1038 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1039 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1040 := 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1002 := (98/7 - 6) \times 5! + 43 - 2 + 1$$

$$1003 := -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1004 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1005 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1006 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1007 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1008 := (98/7 - 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)^2 - 1$$

$$1009 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1010 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) + \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1011 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1012 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1013 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1014 := (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1015 := -9 + \sqrt{(8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^{4+3+2+1}}$$

$$1016 := -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1017 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1018 := -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1019 := (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1020 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1021 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1022 := -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1023 := -9 + 8 + (7!/6! - 5)^{4+3+2+1}$$

$$1024 := \sqrt{((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))^{4+3+2+1}}$$

$$1025 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1026 := -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!$$

$$1027 := -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1028 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1029 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1030 := (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1031 := -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1032 := (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1033 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1034 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1035 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1036 := -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1037 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1038 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1039 := -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1040 := (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1041 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1042 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1043 := -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1044 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1045 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1046 := -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1047 := -1 - 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1048 := -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1049 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$1050 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1051 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1052 := 1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1053 := 12 + 345 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1054 := -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5!) + 67 \times 8 - 9$$

$$1055 := (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1056 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1057 := (12 - 3!)! + 456 - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1058 := -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1059 := 1 \times 2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1060 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1061 := -1 + 2 + 3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1062 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1063 := -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1064 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!/6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1065 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1066 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1067 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1068 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 5/4! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1069 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1070 := (-1 + 2 + 3)!/(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$1071 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1072 := (1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1073 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1074 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1075 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1076 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1077 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 \times 5)$$

$$1078 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1079 := -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1041 := 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 65) - 4! - (3 + 2 - 1)!$$

$$1042 := -9 + 8 + 7!/6! \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1043 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5)/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1044 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1045 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1046 := (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1047 := 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3 + 21$$

$$1048 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1049 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1050 := (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1051 := -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1052 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1053 := -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1054 := (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1055 := -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1056 := (9 + 87) \times (6 + 54 + 3!)/(2 + 1)!$$

$$1057 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1058 := -9 \times 8 - (7!/6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1059 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1060 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1061 := -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1062 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1063 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$1064 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1065 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1066 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5)/\sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1067 := -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1068 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1069 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1070 := ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1071 := 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 - 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1072 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1073 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1074 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (5 + 4)/6 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1075 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1076 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1077 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1078 := (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1079 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1080 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! + 678 - (\sqrt{9})! \\
1081 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 \times 5) \\
1082 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1083 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1084 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1085 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1086 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1087 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1088 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1089 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1090 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1091 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1092 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1093 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1094 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1095 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1096 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1097 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1098 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1099 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1100 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5)/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1101 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1102 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5)/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1103 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/(4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1104 &:= (1 + 2)! + 3!^4 + (56 - 78) \times 9 \\
1105 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5)/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1106 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5)/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1107 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1108 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!!/4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1109 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1110 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1111 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1112 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - \sqrt{4}) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1113 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1114 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1115 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1116 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1117 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1118 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1119 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1080 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1081 &:= 987 + 65 + 4!/3 + 21 \\
1082 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1083 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1084 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1085 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1086 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1087 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1088 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!) \\
1089 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1090 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1091 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1092 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1093 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1094 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1095 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1096 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1097 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1098 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1099 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 - 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1100 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)^6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1101 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1102 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 8) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1103 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1104 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1105 &:= 9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1106 &:= (9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! + 5) - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1107 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1108 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1109 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7!)/(6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1110 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7)^6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1111 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1112 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6!) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1113 &:= -9 - 8 - (7!/6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1114 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1115 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1116 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1117 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1118 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1119 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1120 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1121 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1122 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1123 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1124 &:= (1 + 2)! \times 3!!/4 + 5! - 6 - 7!/(8 \times 9) \\
1125 &:= 1^{23} \times 45 + (6 + 7 - 8)! \times 9 \\
1126 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 + 89 \\
1127 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1128 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1129 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1130 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1131 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1132 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1133 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1134 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1135 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1136 &:= 1234 - 5! - 67 + 89 \\
1137 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1138 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1139 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/(4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1140 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1141 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1142 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1143 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1144 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1145 &:= 12 \times 34 + 5! - 6 + 7 \times 89 \\
1146 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1147 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1148 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1149 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5 + 6) \\
1150 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5 + 6) \\
1151 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1152 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1153 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5 + 6) \\
1154 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1155 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1156 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1157 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1158 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1120 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1121 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1122 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 - 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1123 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1124 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1125 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1126 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6) - 5! - 4 - 3 - 21 \\
1127 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1128 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1129 &:= -9 + 8 - (7!/6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1130 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1131 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1132 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1133 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1134 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1135 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1136 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1137 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1138 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1139 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1140 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1141 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1142 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1143 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6! \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1144 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1145 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1146 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1147 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1148 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1149 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!))/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1150 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1151 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1152 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1153 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1154 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1155 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1156 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1157 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1158 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1159 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1159 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1160 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1160 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1161 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1161 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1162 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1162 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
1163 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1163 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1164 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1164 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1165 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1165 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6!))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1166 &:= 1 \times (2 - 3) + \sqrt{4} \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times 89 & 1166 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1167 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1167 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!) \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5 + 4 \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
1168 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1168 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1169 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1169 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1170 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1170 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1171 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1171 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1172 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1172 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1173 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1173 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1174 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1174 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1175 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1175 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1176 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1176 &:= -9 - 8 - 7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1177 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1177 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1178 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1178 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
1179 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1179 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1180 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1180 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1181 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1181 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7)^6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1182 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1182 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1183 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} & 1183 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1184 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) & 1184 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1185 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1185 &:= -9 - (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1186 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1186 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1187 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1187 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1188 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1188 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1189 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1189 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1190 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (5 \times 6 + 4 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1190 &:= (-9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1191 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1191 &:= -9 + (8 - 7)^6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1192 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) & 1192 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1193 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1193 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1194 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1194 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1195 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1195 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1196 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1196 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1197 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1197 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$1198 := -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1199 := -1 - (2 - (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1200 := 1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7)^{89}$$

$$1201 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1202 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6$$

$$1203 := -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1204 := -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1205 := -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1206 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1207 := -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1208 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!!/4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1209 := -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1210 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1211 := -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1212 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1213 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$1214 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1215 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1216 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1217 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1218 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1219 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1220 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1221 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1222 := 12/3! + \sqrt{4^5} + 6 \times 78 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$1223 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1224 := (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1225 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1226 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1227 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1228 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1229 := -1 - ((-3 \times 4 + 2) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1230 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1231 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1232 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1233 := -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1234 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1235 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1236 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1198 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1199 := -9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1200 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1201 := (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1202 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3)/(2 + 1)!$$

$$1203 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1204 := ((-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1205 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$1206 := -9 + 8 + 7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1207 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1208 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1209 := -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1210 := ((-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1211 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1212 := -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1213 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1214 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1215 := \sqrt{9^{8-7+6}} + 54 \times (3 - 21)$$

$$1216 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6! \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$1217 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1218 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 + 5 + 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1219 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1220 := ((-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1221 := -9 - (8 + 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1222 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5)/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1223 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (\sqrt{6!}/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1224 := -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6! \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1225 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1226 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)}$$

$$1227 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1228 := ((9 - 8) \times 7!/6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1229 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1230 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 + 5 + 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1231 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1232 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1233 := -9 - (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1234 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$1235 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1236 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1237 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1238 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1239 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1240 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1241 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1242 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1243 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1244 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1245 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1246 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1247 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1248 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1249 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1250 &:= (1 - 2 + 3! + 4 \times 5) \times (67 - 8 - 9) \\
1251 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1252 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1253 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1254 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
1255 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1256 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)!/4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1257 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
1258 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1259 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1260 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1261 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1262 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1263 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1264 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)!/4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1265 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1266 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
1267 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1268 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1269 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1270 &:= (1 + 2)!!/3 - 4! - (5 - 67) \times (8 + 9) \\
1271 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1272 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1273 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1274 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1275 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1237 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1238 &:= (9 - 8 - 7 + 65) \times (4! - 3) - 2 + 1 \\
1239 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1240 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1241 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1242 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1243 &:= -9 - 8 - 7!/(6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1244 &:= (-9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1245 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1246 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1247 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1248 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
1249 &:= -9 + (8 - 7!)/(6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1250 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1251 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1252 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1253 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1254 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)!/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1255 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1256 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4! \\
1257 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4! \\
1258 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1259 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1260 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7!/(6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1261 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1262 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1263 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1264 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1265 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1266 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1267 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1268 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1269 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1270 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
1271 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1272 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!)/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1273 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1274 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1275 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1276 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1277 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1278 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1279 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1280 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1281 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1282 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1283 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1284 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1285 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1286 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1287 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1288 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1289 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1290 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1291 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1292 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1293 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1294 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1295 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1296 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)/4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1297 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1298 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1299 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1300 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1301 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1302 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1303 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1304 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)/(4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1305 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1306 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1308 &:= 1234 + 5 - 6! + 789 \\
1309 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1310 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1311 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1312 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1313 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1276 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1277 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1278 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!)/(6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1279 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1280 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1281 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1282 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1283 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times \sqrt{4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)} \\
1284 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1285 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1286 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1287 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1288 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1289 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1290 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1291 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1292 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1293 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1294 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6!/5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1295 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1296 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1297 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1298 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1299 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1300 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1301 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1302 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1303 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1304 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
1305 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1306 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1307 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1308 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6!/5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1309 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! + 5!))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1310 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1311 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1312 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1313 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1314 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1315 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1316 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1317 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1318 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1319 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1320 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1321 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1322 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1323 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1324 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1325 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1326 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1327 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1328 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1329 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1330 &:= (1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 - 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 \\
1331 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (-4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1332 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1333 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1334 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1335 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1336 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1337 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1338 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1339 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1340 &:= (1 + 2)! + 3!! - (4 - 5! + 6) + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
1341 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1342 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1343 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1344 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1345 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1346 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1347 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1348 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1349 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1350 &:= (12 + 3!) \times (45 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1351 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1352 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1314 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1315 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1316 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1317 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1318 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1319 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1320 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1321 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1322 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1323 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1324 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1325 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1326 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5)) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1327 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1328 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1329 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1330 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1331 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1332 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1333 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1334 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1335 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7!/(6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1336 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1337 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1338 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1339 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
1340 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!)/5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1341 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (8 - 7)^6)^5 - 4 + 321 \\
1342 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1343 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1344 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1345 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1346 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1347 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1348 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1349 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1350 &:= 987 + 6! - (4 \times 3 + 5) \times 21 \\
1351 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1352 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1353 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1354 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1355 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^{4+5-6} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1356 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1357 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1358 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1359 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1360 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1361 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1362 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1363 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1364 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1365 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1366 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1367 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1368 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1369 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1370 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1371 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1372 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1373 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1374 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1375 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1376 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1377 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1378 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1379 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1380 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1381 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1382 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1383 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1384 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1385 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1386 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1387 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1388 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1389 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1390 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1391 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1353 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1354 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1355 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! - 6^5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1356 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1357 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1358 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1359 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1360 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1361 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1362 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1363 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1364 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1365 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1366 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1367 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1368 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1369 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1370 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1371 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1372 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1373 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 \times 5) + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1374 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7! - 6 - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1375 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1376 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1377 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1378 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1379 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1380 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1381 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1382 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1383 &:= -9 + 8 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/(7 - 6 - 5) \\
1384 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1385 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1386 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1387 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1388 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1389 &:= -9 - ((8 \times 7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1390 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1391 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1392 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1393 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1394 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1395 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1396 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1397 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1398 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1399 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1400 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1401 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1402 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1403 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1404 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1405 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1406 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1407 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1408 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1409 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1410 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1411 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1412 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1413 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1414 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1415 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1416 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1417 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1418 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1419 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1420 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1421 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1422 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1423 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1424 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1425 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1426 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1427 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1428 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1429 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1430 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1431 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1392 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6) \times 5 + (\sqrt{4} - 3) \times 2 - 1 \\
1393 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1394 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1395 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1396 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1397 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1398 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1399 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1400 &:= 9 - 6 \times 5 - 8 - 7 - 4 + 3!! \times 2 \times 1 \\
1401 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1402 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! / 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1403 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1404 &:= -9 \times (8 / (7 - 6 - 5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1405 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1406 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1407 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1408 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1409 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1410 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1411 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 - 4! + 3!! - 2 + 1 \\
1412 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1413 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1414 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1415 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / (6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1416 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5 \\
1417 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1418 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1419 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1420 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5 \\
1421 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! / 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1422 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1423 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1424 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1425 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! / 5) - 4! - 3 + 21 \\
1426 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1427 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1428 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1429 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1430 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1431 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1432 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times \sqrt{5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
1433 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5!))! \\
1434 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5!))! \\
1435 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1436 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1437 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1438 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1439 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1440 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1441 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1442 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1443 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1444 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1445 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
1446 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1447 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1448 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1449 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1450 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1451 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1452 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1453 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1454 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1455 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1456 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1457 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1458 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4! + 5!} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1459 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1460 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1461 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1462 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1463 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1464 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1465 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1466 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1467 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1468 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1469 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1470 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1471 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1432 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1433 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1434 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
1435 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1436 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1437 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1438 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1439 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1440 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1441 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1442 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1443 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1444 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1445 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1446 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1447 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1448 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1449 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1450 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1451 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1452 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1453 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1454 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1455 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1456 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1457 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1458 &:= 9 + 8 + (7! - 654)/3 - 21 \\
1459 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1460 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1461 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1462 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1463 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
1464 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1465 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1466 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1467 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1468 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1469 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1470 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1471 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1472 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1473 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1474 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1475 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1476 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1477 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1478 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1479 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1480 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1481 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1482 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1483 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1484 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1485 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1486 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1487 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1488 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1489 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1490 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1491 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1492 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1493 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1494 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1495 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1496 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times (5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1497 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1498 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1499 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1500 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1501 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1502 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
1503 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1504 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
1505 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1506 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1507 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1508 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1509 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1510 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1511 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1472 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1473 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1474 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1475 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1476 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1477 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1478 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1479 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1480 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1481 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1482 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1483 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1484 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1485 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1486 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1487 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
1488 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
1489 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1490 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1491 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1492 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1493 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1494 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1495 &:= 987 + 6! - 5 \times 43 + 2 + 1 \\
1496 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1497 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1498 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1499 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1500 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1501 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1502 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6! + 5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1503 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!}/6! \\
1504 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
1505 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1506 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1507 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1508 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1509 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1510 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1511 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + \sqrt{6!/5}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1512 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1513 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1514 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1515 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1516 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1517 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1518 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1519 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1520 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1521 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1522 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1523 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1524 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1525 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1526 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1527 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1528 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1529 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1530 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1531 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1532 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1533 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1534 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1535 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1536 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1537 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
1538 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1539 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1540 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1541 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1542 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1543 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1544 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4^5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1545 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1546 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1547 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1548 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1549 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1550 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - \sqrt{4}) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1512 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1513 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1514 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1515 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1516 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1517 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1518 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 + 4! \times (3! + 21) \\
1519 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1520 &:= (9 + 87 - 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3! - 2) \times 1 \\
1521 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1522 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1523 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1524 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1525 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1526 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1527 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1528 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1529 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1530 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1531 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1532 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1533 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1534 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1535 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1536 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
1537 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1538 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / 6 - 5! / 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1539 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1540 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 4^3 / 5) / (2 + 1)! \\
1541 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1542 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1543 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
1544 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! / 6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1545 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1546 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1547 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + (6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1548 &:= (7 \times 6 + 9 - 8) \times (5 + 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
1549 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1550 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1551 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1552 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1553 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1554 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1555 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1556 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1557 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1558 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1559 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1560 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1561 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1562 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1563 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1564 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1565 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1566 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1567 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1568 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1569 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1570 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1571 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1572 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1573 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1574 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1575 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1576 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1577 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1578 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1579 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1580 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1581 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1582 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1583 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1584 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)/4 \\
1585 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1586 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1587 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1588 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1589 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1590 &:= 12 \times 3 + 45 + 6! + 789
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1551 &:= (98 - 76 + 5^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (32 + 1) \\
1552 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1553 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1554 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6! + 5! - 4 + 32 \times 1 \\
1555 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1556 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1557 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1558 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1559 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
1560 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 - 5! \times (4!/3 - 21) \\
1561 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1562 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1563 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1564 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1565 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1566 &:= (9876 - 5! \times 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1567 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
1568 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1569 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1570 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1571 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1572 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1573 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1574 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1575 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1576 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1577 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1578 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1579 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1580 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1581 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1582 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
1583 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1584 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1585 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1586 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1587 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1588 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1589 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1590 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$1591 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1592 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1593 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1594 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 5/4 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1595 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1596 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 5/4 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1597 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1598 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1599 := -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1600 := -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1601 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1602 := (-1 + 2^3!) \times 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1603 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1604 := (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1605 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1606 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1607 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1608 := (-1 + 2^3! + 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1609 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1610 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$1611 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1612 := -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1613 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1614 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1615 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!)/6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1616 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1617 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1618 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1619 := 1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1620 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1621 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1622 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1623 := -1 + 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1624 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$1625 := -1 + 2^3! \times 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1626 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1627 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1628 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$1629 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1591 := 98 + 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$1592 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1593 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1594 := -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1595 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1596 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1597 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1598 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1599 := ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! + 4) \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$$

$$1600 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1601 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1602 := -9 \times 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1603 := -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1604 := 9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! + 3! + 21$$

$$1605 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1606 := -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1607 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1608 := -9 \times 8 + 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/(6 \times 5)$$

$$1609 := -9 - 8 + (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1610 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1611 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1612 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1613 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1614 := -9 \times 8 - (7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1615 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1616 := ((-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1617 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1618 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1619 := -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1620 := ((\sqrt{9})! \times (87 + 6) - 54/3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$1621 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1622 := -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1623 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 - 5) \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1624 := ((-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1625 := 9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1626 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1627 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1628 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1629 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1630 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1631 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1632 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1633 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1634 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1635 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
1636 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1637 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1638 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1639 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1640 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (-5 \times 6 + 4) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1641 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1642 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1643 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1644 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 5/4 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1645 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1646 &:= -1 + 2^{3!-4+5} \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
1647 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1648 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1649 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1650 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1651 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1652 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1653 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1654 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1655 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1656 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1657 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1658 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1659 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1660 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
1661 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1662 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1663 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (\sqrt{4} + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
1664 &:= ((1 - 23) \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 78)/9 \\
1665 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1666 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (\sqrt{4^5} + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1667 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1668 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1630 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 \times 5! + 4^3 \times 2 - 1 \\
1631 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1632 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7!/6 + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1633 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + (2 \times 1 - 4 + 3) \\
1634 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)!! \\
1635 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1636 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1637 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1638 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + \sqrt{6!/5}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1639 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1640 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1641 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1642 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
1643 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1644 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1645 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
1646 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 87 \times 6 - 5 + 4^3 + 21 \\
1647 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1648 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1649 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1650 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1651 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1652 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1653 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1654 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1655 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1656 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1657 &:= -9 - 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1658 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1659 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1660 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1661 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1662 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1663 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/(6 \times 5) \\
1664 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1665 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1666 &:= (98 + 7 + 6) \times 5! \times 3/4! + 2 - 1 \\
1667 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1668 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$1669 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1670 := -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1671 := -1 + 2 \times (((3 + 4)! + 5!)/6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1672 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1673 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1674 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1675 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1676 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1677 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + \sqrt{4^5} \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1678 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + \sqrt{4^5} \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1679 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1680 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1681 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + \sqrt{4^5} \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1682 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1683 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1684 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1685 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1686 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1687 := -1 + 2 \times (((3 + 4)! - 5!)/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1688 := -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (-5 \times 6 + 4) - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1689 := -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1690 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1691 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1692 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1693 := -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1694 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1695 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)}$$

$$1696 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1697 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1698 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1699 := -1 - (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1700 := -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1701 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1702 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1703 := -1 + (2^{3!} - 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1704 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1705 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1706 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1707 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1669 := -9 - 8 - (7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1670 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1671 := (9 \times (8 + 7) - 65) \times 4! - 3^2 \times 1$$

$$1672 := -9 + 8 - 7 - (6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1673 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1674 := (-9 + 8) \times 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1675 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1676 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1677 := -9 + 8 + (7! - 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1678 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1679 := -9 + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1680 := (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1681 := \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 - (3!/2 \times 1)!$$

$$1682 := (-9 + 8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1683 := (9 + 8) \times (76 + 5!/4 - 3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$1684 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1685 := -9 + 8 - (7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1686 := (-9 + 8) \times 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1687 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1688 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1689 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1690 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7!/6 - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1691 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1692 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!$$

$$1693 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1694 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1695 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1696 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1697 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1698 := (-9 \times 8 - 7!)/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1699 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1700 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1701 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1702 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1703 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1704 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1705 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1706 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$1707 := -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1708 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1709 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1710 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1711 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1712 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1713 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1714 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1715 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1716 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1717 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1718 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1719 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1720 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1721 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1722 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1723 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1724 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1725 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1726 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1727 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1728 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1729 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1730 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1731 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1732 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1733 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1734 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1735 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1736 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1737 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1738 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1739 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1740 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1741 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1742 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1743 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5!) / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1744 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1745 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1746 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! \times 4/5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1708 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1709 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1710 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!) / (6 - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1711 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1712 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
1713 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1714 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! \times 5! / 6!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1715 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1716 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! / 4) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1717 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1718 &:= -9 - (8 - 7)^6 + (5 + 4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
1719 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1720 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1721 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1722 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 65) \times (4 - 3!) \times 21 \\
1723 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1724 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! / 6 - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1725 &:= 987 + 6! - 5 + 4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
1726 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6!) / 5) \times \sqrt{4! / (3 + 2 + 1)} \\
1727 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1728 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 54 \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\
1729 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) \times 4! / 5! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1730 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1731 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1732 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1733 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) / 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1734 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1735 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1736 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
1737 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1738 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 4 \times 3 \times (2 - 1) / 5 \\
1739 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1740 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1741 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1742 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1743 &:= 98 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4! \times 3 \times 21 \\
1744 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1) \\
1745 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1746 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 - (3!! - 2) \times 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1747 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1748 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1749 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1750 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1751 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1752 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1753 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1754 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
1755 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1756 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1757 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1758 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1759 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1760 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1761 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1762 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1763 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1764 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) \\
1765 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1766 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1767 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1768 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1769 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1770 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1771 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1772 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1773 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1774 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1775 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1776 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1777 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1778 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
1779 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1780 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1781 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1782 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1783 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1784 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
1785 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1747 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1748 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
1749 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1750 &:= (\sqrt{9} - 87) \times (5 - 4 - 3! \times 21)/6 \\
1751 &:= 9 + 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4 - 3!) + 2 \times 1 \\
1752 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5 \times 4!/3 \times 21 \\
1753 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1754 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3))/(2 + 1) \\
1755 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1756 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
1757 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1758 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1759 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1760 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
1761 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1762 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6!)/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1763 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1764 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1765 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
1766 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1767 &:= 9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1768 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1769 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1770 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1771 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1772 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
1773 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1774 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
1775 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 \times 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1776 &:= \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6 + 5 + 43^2 \times 1 \\
1777 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1778 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!) + 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
1779 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1780 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1781 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6!) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1782 &:= (9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!)/(2 + 1) \\
1783 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 - 6!) \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1784 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
1785 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1786 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 5/\sqrt{4} + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1786 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5)/\sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1787 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1787 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1788 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))/\sqrt{4} & 1788 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1789 &:= 12 + 3!^4 + 56 \times 7 + 89 & 1789 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1790 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 1790 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1791 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1791 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
1792 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^{5/(6+7+8+9)} & 1792 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! \times 5/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1793 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1793 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1794 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 1794 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1795 &:= (1 + 2)^{3!} - (4^5 + 6 \times 7) \times (8 - 9) & 1795 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1796 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) & 1796 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1797 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1797 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6! \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1798 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1798 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1799 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1799 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1800 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1800 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6 \\
1801 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1801 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1802 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 1802 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1803 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1803 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1804 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1804 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6! \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1805 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 5/4 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 & 1805 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1806 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1806 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1807 &:= (-1 - \sqrt{(2 + 3)! + 4!}) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 1807 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1808 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/\sqrt{4}) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1808 &:= 9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1809 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1809 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1810 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 + 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1810 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1811 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1811 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1812 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1812 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6! \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1813 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 + 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 1813 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1814 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! \times 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 1814 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!/6 + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1815 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1815 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1816 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 1816 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 76 - \sqrt{54 \times 3/2} + 1 \\
1817 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1817 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1818 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1818 &:= 9 \times (87 - 6 + 5!) - 4! + 32 + 1 \\
1819 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 1819 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 5!/6 + 4 - 3! + 21 \\
1820 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/\sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1820 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1821 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1821 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1822 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 1822 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 8) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1823 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1823 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1824 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1824 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1825 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1826 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1827 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1828 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1829 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1830 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1831 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1832 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1833 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1834 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1835 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1836 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1837 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1838 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1839 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1840 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1841 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1842 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1843 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1844 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
1845 &:= 1 \times 234 \times 5 + 6! - (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \\
1846 &:= (12 \times 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + 567 - 8 - 9 \\
1847 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1848 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1849 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1850 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1851 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1852 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1853 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 - 4!) \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1854 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1855 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1856 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) \times 6 / (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1857 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1858 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1859 &:= 12 \times 3 + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
1860 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1861 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1862 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1825 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1826 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 + 6!) \times 5) / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1827 &:= \sqrt{9^{8-7+6}} - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3!! / 2 \times 1 \\
1828 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) - 65 + 43^2 - 1 \\
1829 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1830 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1831 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 + 5 - 4 \times (3!! - 2 \times 1) \\
1832 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
1833 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
1834 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7! / 6 - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1835 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
1836 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
1837 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1838 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1839 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1840 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
1841 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1842 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1843 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1844 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1845 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1846 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6 + 5!) / \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1847 &:= 987 + 6! - (5 - (4 \times 3)^2 - 1) \\
1848 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1849 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1850 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! / 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
1851 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1852 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3) / (2 + 1) \\
1853 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1854 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
1855 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1856 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1857 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1858 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1859 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!) / 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1860 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1861 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1862 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6) - 5 \times (4 - 3!!) / 2 \times 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1863 &:= 34 \times 56 + 12 - 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
1864 &:= 12 \times ((4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 89)/3 \\
1865 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1866 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1867 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1868 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1869 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1870 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1871 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1872 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1873 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1874 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1875 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1876 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1877 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - (4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
1878 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3^4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1879 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
1880 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1881 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1882 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1883 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
1884 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
1885 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1886 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1887 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1888 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1889 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1890 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1891 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1892 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
1893 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1894 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
1895 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1896 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
1897 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1898 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1899 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
1900 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
1901 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1863 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1864 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1865 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1866 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1867 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1868 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (6 \times 5 + 7)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1869 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1870 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
1871 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1872 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1873 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1874 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
1875 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1876 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
1877 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1878 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1879 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1880 &:= (98 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 + 1) \\
1881 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1882 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 54 + 3!! \times 2 - 1 \\
1883 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1884 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4! \times (3! - 2 + 1) \\
1885 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1886 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
1887 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1888 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
1889 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1890 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1891 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1892 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4 - 3)/(2 + 1) \\
1893 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1894 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 54 \times (3!^2 - 1) \\
1895 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1896 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1897 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
1898 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - (5! - 4 - 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
1899 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
1900 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
1901 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6^5/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$1902 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1903 := -1 - 2^3! \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1904 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1905 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1906 := -1 \times 2 + (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1907 := -1 + (2 \times (3 + 4) - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1908 := (-1 + (2 + 3) \times \sqrt{4^5}) \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$1909 := (1 + 2)! \times 4^5 / 3 - 67 - 8 \times 9$$

$$1910 := -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1911 := (-1 - 2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1912 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5! / 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1913 := -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6$$

$$1914 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1915 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6$$

$$1916 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1917 := (-1 - 2) \times 3^4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1918 := -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6$$

$$1919 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1920 := -1 \times 2^3! \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1921 := -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / (\sqrt{4} - 5 - 6)$$

$$1922 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4! \times 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1923 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! / 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1924 := -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6$$

$$1925 := -1 - (2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1926 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4 + 5) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$1927 := -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6$$

$$1928 := (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1929 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$1930 := -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1931 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$1932 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) / 4 - 8 - 9$$

$$1933 := -1 - (2 - 3!! / 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1934 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1935 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1936 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6)$$

$$1937 := 1 \times (234 + \sqrt{56 - 7}) \times 8 + 9$$

$$1938 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1939 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! / 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1940 := (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1902 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 / 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1903 := -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1904 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) / (2 + 1)$$

$$1905 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1906 := (9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 54 \times 3!) - 2 \times 1$$

$$1907 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1908 := (98 + 76 + 5! + 4!) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$1909 := -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1910 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1911 := -9 + 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1912 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1913 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1914 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1915 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 - 5 + 4)!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1916 := -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + (4 + 3)!) / (2 + 1)$$

$$1917 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1918 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1919 := -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1920 := (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6!)! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1921 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6! / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!)!$$

$$1922 := (-9 + 8 - 7! / 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1923 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1924 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1925 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1926 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1927 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1928 := 98 / 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4! - 3^2 + 1)$$

$$1929 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 76 - 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 \times 1)$$

$$1930 := (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1931 := (-9 - 8) \times (7! / 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1932 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) / 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1933 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1934 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 4!$$

$$1935 := (9 - 8 - 76 + 5!) \times 43 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$1936 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1937 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1938 := (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1939 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1940 := (98 - 76 + 5^4) \times 3! / 2 - 1$$

$$1941 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1942 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1943 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1944 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1945 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1946 := 1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8) \times 9$$

$$1947 := -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1948 := (-1 - 2 \times 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1949 := -1 + (2^{3!} - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1950 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! - \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1951 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)})$$

$$1952 := -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1953 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1954 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1955 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1956 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1957 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1958 := -1 + (2 + 3! + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$1959 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1960 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5!/6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1961 := (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1962 := (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1963 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$1964 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1965 := -(-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1966 := (1 + 2)! + 3!^4 - 5 + 678 - 9$$

$$1967 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1968 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1969 := 12 + 34 \times 56 + 7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$1970 := (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$1971 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$1972 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$1973 := -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$1974 := (1 + 2)! \times 3!! + 4! - 5 \times 6 \times (8 \times 9 + 7)$$

$$1975 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1976 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$1977 := -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1978 := -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1979 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1941 := -9 + (8 + 7!/6!) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1942 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4!$$

$$1943 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1944 := -9 \times 8 + 7! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5 + 4)$$

$$1945 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1946 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1947 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1948 := \sqrt{9} - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!/4) \times 3 \times 21$$

$$1949 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1950 := (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 - 7)^{65} \times (4 + 321)$$

$$1951 := 9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1952 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1953 := 9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^3 \times 21$$

$$1954 := (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1955 := (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1956 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}})$$

$$1957 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1958 := ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - 5! - (4 + 3)!))/(2 + 1)$$

$$1959 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1960 := ((-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1961 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1962 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!$$

$$1963 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1964 := (-9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1965 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1966 := -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1967 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1968 := -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1969 := -9 - (8 - 7)!/((6 - 5) \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1970 := -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3))/(2 + 1)$$

$$1971 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$1972 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6!/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$1973 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1974 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5)/4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$1975 := -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1976 := (-9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1977 := (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1978 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1979 := -9 + 8 + 7!/((6 - 5) \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1980 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1981 := 1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5 + 678 + 9$$

$$1982 := (1 \times 2 + 3 + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1983 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1984 := -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1985 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1986 := (-1 - 2) \times ((3! + 4) \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1987 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1988 := -1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1989 := -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1990 := -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1991 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$1992 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1993 := 1 \times 2 - (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$1994 := -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1995 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$1996 := -1 + (2 \times 3)^4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1997 := -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$1998 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$1999 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2000 := 1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2001 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2002 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2003 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2004 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2005 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2006 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2007 := -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2008 := -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2009 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2010 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2011 := -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2012 := 1 - 2 + 3! + 4 \times (56 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$2013 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2014 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2015 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2016 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2017 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2018 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$1980 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1981 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1982 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$1983 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1984 := ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1985 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1986 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$1987 := -9 - 8 \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1988 := (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 - 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1989 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$1990 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6!/5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1})$$

$$1991 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$1992 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$1993 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1994 := (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 - 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1995 := -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1996 := (-9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$1997 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$1998 := (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times (43 - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$1999 := -9 - 8 + 7! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5 + 4)$$

$$2000 := (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2001 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2002 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$2003 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2004 := (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6)^{5-\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2005 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2006 := -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2007 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2008 := -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2009 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2010 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2011 := 9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2012 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2013 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2014 := (-9 + 8 - 7! + 6) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/5$$

$$2015 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5 + 4)$$

$$2016 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2017 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2018 := (-9 + 8 - 7 \times 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2019 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2020 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2021 := -1 - 2 + (3! - 4)^{5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2022 := (12 - 3!) \times (456 - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$2023 := 1 - 2 + (3! - 4)^{5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2024 := \sqrt{(-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^{5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$2025 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2026 := 1^{23} + \sqrt{4+5} \times 678 - 9$$

$$2027 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2028 := (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2029 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2030 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2031 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2032 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2033 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2034 := ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2035 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2036 := -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2037 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2038 := -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2039 := -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2040 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2041 := -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2042 := -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2043 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2044 := -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2045 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2046 := -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2047 := -1 + 2^{(3+4+5!)/(6+7+8+9)}$$

$$2048 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2049 := -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2050 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2051 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2052 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2053 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2054 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2055 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 + 5) - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2056 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2057 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!/(4! - 5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$2019 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2020 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2021 := -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2022 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2023 := -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2024 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$2025 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2026 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$2027 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2028 := 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 \times 321$$

$$2029 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2030 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$2031 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2032 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2033 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2034 := -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2035 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2036 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2037 := -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2038 := -9 \times 8 - 7! + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2039 := -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2040 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2041 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2042 := -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2043 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$2044 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2045 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2046 := 9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 + 5! - 4! - 3) \times 21$$

$$2047 := (9 + 8 + 7)/6 - 5 + 4^{3!}/2 \times 1$$

$$2048 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2049 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$2050 := (\sqrt{9} + 7 \times 6 - 8 - 5) \times (\sqrt{4^{3!}} + 2 \times 1)$$

$$2051 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2052 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2053 := -9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$2054 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$2055 := -9 + (8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2056 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$2057 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2058 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2059 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2060 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times 4^5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$2061 := -1 - 2 + (3!/(4 + 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2062 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2063 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2064 := -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2065 := (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2066 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2067 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2068 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2069 := -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2070 := 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^5 - 6 + 7 + 8) - 9$$

$$2071 := 12 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 \times 7)/3 - 8 - 9$$

$$2072 := 1 - 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times 6 - 789$$

$$2073 := -1 + 2 + (3! - 4)^{5+6} + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2074 := 1 + 23 - (4! - 5 + 6) \times (7 - 89)$$

$$2075 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2076 := (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2077 := (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2078 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2079 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2080 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2081 := -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2082 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$2083 := 1^2 - 3! + 4 \times 5! + 67 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$2084 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2085 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2086 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2087 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2088 := (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$2089 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$2090 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2091 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$2092 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2093 := -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2094 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$2095 := -1 - 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2096 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2058 := (6 \times 5 + 987) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 21$$

$$2059 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2060 := -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2061 := (98 \times 7 - 6 + 5 + 4) \times 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$2062 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$2063 := -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$2064 := (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2065 := (9 + 8) \times (7!/(6 \times 5) - 4) - 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$2066 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$2067 := -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2068 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2069 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2070 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2071 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2072 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$2073 := (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$2074 := 9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5 \times 4) \times 3 + 21$$

$$2075 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2076 := -9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2077 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2078 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$2079 := -9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$2080 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$2081 := -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2082 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!/4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$2083 := 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5/4 + 3! - 2 \times 1$$

$$2084 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2085 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6!/5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$2086 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - (6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$2087 := -9 + (8 - (7! - 6! - 5!))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2088 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2089 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2090 := (98 - 76) \times 5 \times (4 - 3! + 21)$$

$$2091 := -9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2092 := (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$2093 := -9 - 8 - 7! + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2094 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!/4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$2095 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$2096 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2097 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2098 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2099 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2100 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / \sqrt{4} \\
2101 &:= 12^3 - (\sqrt{4} - 56) \times 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9} \\
2102 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! - (5 - 6) \times (7 - 89) \\
2103 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 + 5) - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2104 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2105 &:= 12 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 \times 7) / 3 + 8 + 9 \\
2106 &:= (12 - 3! - 4 - 5 + 6) \times 78 \times 9 \\
2107 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2108 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2109 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2110 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2111 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2112 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2113 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3)! - 4! - 5 + 6! + 78 \times 9 \\
2114 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2115 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2116 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2117 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5! \times 7 / 6 + 8 + 9 \\
2118 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2119 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2120 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2121 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2122 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2123 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2124 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2125 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2126 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2127 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2128 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2129 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2130 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2131 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2132 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2133 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2134 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2135 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2097 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2098 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
2099 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 \times 321 \\
2100 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2101 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2102 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2103 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2104 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2105 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!) \\
2106 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2107 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2108 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2109 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2110 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7! - (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2111 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2112 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2113 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2114 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2115 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2116 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2117 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2118 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5) / 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2119 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! \times \sqrt{4} / 5 + 32 - 1 \\
2120 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2121 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! / 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2122 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2123 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2124 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5) \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 4! \\
2125 &:= 98 + 7! - 6 - 5! - 4 \times (3!! + 2) + 1 \\
2126 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2127 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2128 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2129 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2130 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2131 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2132 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2133 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2134 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2135 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2136 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2137 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2138 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2139 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2140 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2141 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2142 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2143 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2144 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2145 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2146 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2147 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2148 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2149 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2150 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2151 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2152 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2153 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2154 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2155 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2156 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2157 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2158 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2159 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2160 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2161 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2162 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2163 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2164 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2165 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2166 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2167 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2168 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2169 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2170 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2171 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2172 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2173 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2174 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2175 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 + 5 - 6)!!) + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2136 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2137 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2138 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2139 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2140 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2141 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2142 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2143 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2144 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2145 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2146 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2147 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2148 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2149 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2150 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2151 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2152 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2153 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2154 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2155 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2156 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2157 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2158 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! - 5!))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2159 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2160 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2161 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2162 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
2163 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2164 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2165 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2166 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2167 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2168 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2169 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2170 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2171 &:= 9 + 8 - 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4 \times (3! - 2!) \\
2172 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2173 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2174 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2175 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2176 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2177 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2178 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2179 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2180 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2181 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2182 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2183 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2184 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2185 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2186 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2187 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2188 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2189 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2190 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2191 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2192 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2193 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2194 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2195 &:= -1 - (2 + (3! + 4 - 5)!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2196 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2197 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2198 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2199 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2200 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2201 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2202 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2203 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2204 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2205 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2206 &:= (1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 - 678 + 9 \\
2207 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2208 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2209 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \sqrt{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
2210 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5! - 6!)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
2211 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2212 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2213 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2214 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2176 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2177 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2178 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2179 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2180 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3! - 2 + 1) \\
2181 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2182 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + (5 + 4 - 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
2183 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2184 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2185 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2186 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2187 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2188 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2189 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2190 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2191 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2192 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1)) \\
2193 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2194 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2195 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2196 &:= (9 - 8 - 7) \times 6 + (5! + 4) \times 3! \times (2 + 1) \\
2197 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2198 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
2199 &:= -9 + (8 - 7!)/(-5 \times 4 + 6) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2200 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2201 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2202 &:= 9 + 87 + (6! + 5 - 4!) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2203 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2204 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2205 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2206 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2207 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2208 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2209 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2210 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7! - (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2211 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + 5! \times 4! + 3^{2+1} \\
2212 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2213 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2214 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 54 \times 3! + 2) + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2215 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2216 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2217 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2218 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2219 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times \sqrt{4! + 5!}) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2220 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2221 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2222 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2223 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2224 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2225 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2226 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2227 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2228 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2229 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2230 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2231 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2232 &:= 12^3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 - (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2233 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2234 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2235 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2236 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2237 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2238 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2239 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2240 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
2241 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2242 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2243 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2244 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2245 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2246 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2247 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2248 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2249 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2250 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2251 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2252 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2253 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2215 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2216 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6! + 5^4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2217 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6!/5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2218 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!! \\
2219 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2220 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2221 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2222 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
2223 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2224 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2225 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6^5/4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2226 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!)/\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2227 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2228 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
2229 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2230 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2231 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2232 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 + 5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2233 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2234 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
2235 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2236 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4)/3)/(2 + 1) \\
2237 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2238 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2239 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2240 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!/(5 + 4) + 3!! + (2 + 1)!! \\
2241 &:= \sqrt{9^8} - 7! + 6! \times (5 - \sqrt{4})/3! \times 2 \times 1 \\
2242 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
2243 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2244 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2245 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2246 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2247 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + (5! - 4) \times 3! \times 2 \times 1 \\
2248 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2249 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2250 &:= 98 + 7! - 6 + 5 - 4 \times (3!! + 2) + 1 \\
2251 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! \times 5!/6! - 4! + 3!! \times 2 \times 1 \\
2252 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) - 5) \times (\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2253 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2254 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2255 &:= 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8 - 9) \\
2256 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2257 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2258 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2259 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2260 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2261 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2262 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2263 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2264 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2265 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2266 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2267 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3 + 4)! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2268 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2269 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2270 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
2271 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2272 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2273 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2274 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2275 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2276 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2277 &:= 1 \times 23 \times (4 + 5! - 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2278 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2279 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2280 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2281 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 89) \\
2282 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2283 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2284 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2285 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2286 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6)/4! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2287 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2288 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2289 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2290 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2291 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2292 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2293 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2254 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2255 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2256 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2257 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2258 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2259 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2260 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2261 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2262 &:= 9 \times 87 - 6 - 5 \times (4! - 321) \\
2263 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2264 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2265 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2266 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
2267 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 54 - 3! \times (2 + 1) \\
2268 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2269 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2270 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6! - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2271 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2272 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6! - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2273 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6! - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2274 &:= (9 + 8) \times (76 - 5 + \sqrt{4^{3!}}) - 21 \\
2275 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2276 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2277 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2278 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2279 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2280 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2281 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2282 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
2283 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2284 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2285 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2286 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6! - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2287 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2288 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 - 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2289 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + \sqrt{4}) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2290 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
2291 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2292 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2293 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2294 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
2295 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2296 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2297 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2298 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2299 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2300 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2301 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2302 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2303 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2304 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2305 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2306 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2307 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2308 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2309 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2310 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2311 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2312 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2313 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2314 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2315 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2316 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - \sqrt{4}) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2317 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2318 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2319 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2320 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2321 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2322 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2323 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2324 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2325 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2326 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2327 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2328 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2329 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2330 &:= 1 \times (23 - 4) \times 5! + 67 - 8 - 9 \\
2331 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2332 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2294 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2295 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2296 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2297 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2298 &:= 9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5! - 4 + 3!) \times 21 \\
2299 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2300 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2301 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2302 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
2303 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2304 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2305 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2306 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2307 &:= (-6 \times 5 + 9 + 87) \times 4! + 3!! + 2 + 1 \\
2308 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2309 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2310 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2311 &:= -9 - (8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2312 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2313 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2314 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2315 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2316 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2317 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2318 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 \times 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2319 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2320 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2321 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2322 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7 + 65 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
2323 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
2324 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2325 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2326 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2327 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2328 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2329 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2330 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
2331 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2332 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2333 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2334 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (5 + 6)/4! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2335 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2336 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2337 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)/4 \\
2338 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)/4 \\
2339 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2340 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2341 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)/4 \\
2342 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2343 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2344 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2345 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2346 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2347 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2348 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2349 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3^4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2350 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2351 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - \sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2352 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 \times 4! \times (5! + 67 - 89) \\
2353 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!/4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2354 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2355 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2356 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2357 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2358 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2359 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2360 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2361 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
2362 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2363 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2364 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - \sqrt{4}) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2365 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2366 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2367 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2368 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - 4 \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2369 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2370 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2333 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2334 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5 - 4!) \\
2335 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2336 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
2337 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2338 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2339 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2340 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2341 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2342 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
2343 &:= 98 + 7! - 65 \times \sqrt{43^2} \times 1 \\
2344 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3!) - (2 + 1)! \\
2345 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
2346 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2347 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2348 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2349 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times \sqrt{6! + 5 + 4}) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2350 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2351 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2352 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2353 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2354 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2355 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2356 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2357 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times \sqrt{4}) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2358 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2359 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6^5/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2360 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2361 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2362 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2363 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2364 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2365 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2366 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2367 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + (765 + 4) \times 3 - 21} \\
2368 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2369 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2370 &:= (9 \times (8 - 7 + 65) \times \sqrt{4} - 3) \times 2 \times 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2371 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - 4 \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2372 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
2373 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2374 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2375 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
2376 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2377 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2378 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2379 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2380 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2381 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2382 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2383 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4 \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2384 &:= (1 \times 23 - 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2385 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
2386 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2387 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2388 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2389 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2390 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2391 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2392 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2393 &:= 1 + 2345 + (7 \times 8 - 6) - \sqrt{9} \\
2394 &:= (\sqrt{12 \times 3} + \sqrt{4^5}) \times (6 - 7 + 8) \times 9 \\
2395 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2396 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
2397 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
2398 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
2399 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
2400 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
2401 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
2402 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
2403 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + \sqrt{5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
2404 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2405 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2406 &:= 1^2 + (3 + \sqrt{4}) \times (56 \times 7 + 89) \\
2407 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2408 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2371 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2372 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2373 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2374 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2375 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6^5/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2376 &:= (9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 32 + 1) \\
2377 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2378 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2379 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2380 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2381 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2382 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2383 &:= -9 - 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2384 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2385 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2386 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2387 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2388 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2389 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2390 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6 \times 5!) + \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1 \\
2391 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2392 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2393 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2394 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! - 4!/3) \times 21 \\
2395 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7 + 6 - 5))^4 - 3!) \times (2 - 1) \\
2396 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2397 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2398 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2399 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2400 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2401 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
2402 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2403 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2404 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2405 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2406 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2407 &:= 9 - 8 - 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4^3 - 2) \times 1 \\
2408 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2409 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
2410 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2411 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2412 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2413 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2414 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2415 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2416 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2417 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2418 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2419 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2420 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
2421 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2422 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2423 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2424 &:= ((1 + 2)! + 3!) \times (4 - (56 - 78) \times 9) \\
2425 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2426 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2427 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2428 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2429 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2430 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!!/(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2431 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2432 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2433 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2434 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2435 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2436 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2437 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2438 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2439 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2440 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2441 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2442 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2443 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2444 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2445 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2446 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2447 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! + 4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2409 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2410 &:= 987 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3!! - 21 \\
2411 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2412 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 + 54) \times 3/(2 + 1)! \\
2413 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!^{2+1}) \\
2414 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2415 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2416 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2417 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2418 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2419 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2420 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2421 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2422 &:= (98 \times 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 + 3!)/2 \times 1 \\
2423 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2424 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!)/(6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2425 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2426 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
2427 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2428 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2429 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
2430 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2431 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6!/5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2432 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
2433 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2434 &:= (9876 - 5!)/4 - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
2435 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! + 6!/5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2436 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2437 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2438 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2439 &:= (9876 - 5!)/4 - 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2440 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2441 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2442 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2443 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2444 &:= -9 + (8 - (7! - 6 - 5!))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2445 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6) \times (5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2446 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! + 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2447 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2448 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2449 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2450 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2451 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2452 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2453 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 2454 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2455 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 2456 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 2457 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2458 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2459 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2460 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2461 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2462 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times ((4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
 2463 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4! - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 2464 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
 2465 &:= -1 - (2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2466 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2467 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
 2468 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 2469 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2470 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2471 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2472 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(4 - 5 - 6) \\
 2473 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2474 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 2475 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 2476 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 2477 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 2478 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2479 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 2480 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 2481 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 2482 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 2483 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 2484 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 2485 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 2486 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2448 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + (8 + 7 - 6) \times 5) \times 4! \times (3 - 2 + 1) \\
 2449 &:= 9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5!/4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 2450 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! - 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2451 &:= (98 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 + 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
 2452 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2453 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 2454 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 2455 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + (5 + 4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 2456 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2457 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 2458 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2459 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2460 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2461 &:= ((9 - 8) \times 7! - 6 - 5! + 4!/3)/2 \times 1 \\
 2462 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! + 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2463 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2464 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 2465 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!/5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2466 &:= (9 + 87 - 6 - 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2) + 1 \\
 2467 &:= -9 - 8 + (7!/6 - 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 2468 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2469 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2470 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5!} \times (\sqrt{4} - 3 - 21) \\
 2471 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2472 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2473 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!/5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 2474 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4) + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 2475 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2476 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/5) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
 2477 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 \times (5 - \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}}) \\
 2478 &:= (-8 \times 7 + 9) \times 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2479 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6^5/4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 2480 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
 2481 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 2482 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6!/(5 - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1) \\
 2483 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 2484 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/6 \\
 2485 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 2486 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5 - 4) \times 3 - (2 + 1)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2487 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2488 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2489 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2490 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2491 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2492 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2493 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2494 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2495 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2496 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2497 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2498 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!!/(4 + 5) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2499 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2500 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2501 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2502 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2503 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2504 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)^4) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2505 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2506 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2507 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2508 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2509 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2510 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2511 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2512 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2513 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/\sqrt{4} + 5 - \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
2514 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2515 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2516 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2517 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2518 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2519 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2520 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2521 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2522 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2523 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2524 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2525 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2487 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2488 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6 \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2489 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2490 &:= (98 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 - 3 + 2) \times 1 \\
2491 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
2492 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! + 6 \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2493 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2494 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
2495 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2496 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2497 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/(6!/5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2498 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
2499 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2500 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2501 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2502 &:= -9 \times 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2503 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2504 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6 \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2505 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2506 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! + 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2507 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/6 \\
2508 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2509 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2510 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! - 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2511 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2512 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2513 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2514 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2515 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/6 \\
2516 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2517 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2518 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times 6! + 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2519 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2520 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6!))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2521 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2522 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! + 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2523 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! + 6 + 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2524 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
2525 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/(6!/5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2526 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2527 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2528 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2529 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2530 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2531 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2532 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2533 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2534 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2535 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2536 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2537 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2538 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2539 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2540 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2541 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2542 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2543 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) \\
2544 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2545 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2546 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2547 &:= -1 - 2 - ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2548 &:= -1 \times 2 - ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2549 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2550 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2551 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2552 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2553 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2554 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2555 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2556 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2557 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2558 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2559 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2560 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2561 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - 5! \times 6/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
2562 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2563 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2564 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2526 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! - 6 - 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2527 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3)/2 - 1 \\
2528 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6 + 5))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2529 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2530 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! + 6 \times 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2531 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times 6! - 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2532 &:= (9 - 87) \times (-5 \times 4 + 6) + 3!! \times 2 \times 1 \\
2533 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2534 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! - 6 - 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2535 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2536 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2537 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2538 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2539 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2540 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2541 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2542 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 8) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2543 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2544 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2545 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2546 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6! + 5))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2547 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2548 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2549 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2550 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 - 4 + 3)!/2 \times 1 \\
2551 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2552 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2553 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2554 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
2555 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2556 &:= -9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2557 &:= -9 - 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2558 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2559 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7! - 6!/5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2560 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2561 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2562 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2563 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2564 &:= -9 + (8 - (7! - 6 + 5!))/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2565 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2566 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2567 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2568 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2569 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2570 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2571 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2572 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2573 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2574 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2575 &:= -1 - 2^{3!+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2576 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2577 &:= (1 + 2)^{3!+4} - 5 \times (6 \times 7 - (8 - \sqrt{9})!) \\
2578 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3)! \times 4 - 56 \times 7 + 89 \\
2579 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2580 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4 + 5 + 67 + 8 \times 9) \\
2581 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 - (5! + 67)/(8 + 9) \\
2582 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2583 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2584 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2585 &:= (-1 + 2^{3^{\sqrt{4}}}) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2586 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times \sqrt{5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
2587 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2588 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2589 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2590 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2591 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) \\
2592 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2593 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2594 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} - 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
2595 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2596 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2597 &:= (1 - 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5 \times (6 - 7) \times 8 - 9) \\
2598 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2599 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2600 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2601 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2602 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2603 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2565 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6!/5 + 4^3 + 21) \\
2566 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! + 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2567 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2568 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2569 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
2570 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! - 6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2571 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2572 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2573 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2574 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2575 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2576 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2577 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2578 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! + 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2579 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times 6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2580 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2581 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2582 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! + 6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2583 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2584 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
2585 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2586 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2587 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! + 6!/5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2588 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2589 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2590 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2591 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2592 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2593 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
2594 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2595 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2596 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2597 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2598 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
2599 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2600 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2601 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2602 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
2603 &:= -9 - 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2604 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2605 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2606 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2607 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2608 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2609 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2610 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2611 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2612 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2613 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2614 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2615 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2616 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2617 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2618 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2619 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2620 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2621 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2622 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2623 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2624 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - (5 - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
2625 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
2626 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2627 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2628 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2629 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2630 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2631 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2632 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2633 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2634 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2635 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2636 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2637 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2638 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2639 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2640 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2641 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2642 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2643 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2604 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2605 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2606 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2607 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2608 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2609 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2610 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4! + 3 - 2 \times 1) \\
2611 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3! - 2) - 1 \\
2612 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2613 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2614 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2615 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2616 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2617 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2618 &:= (9 - 8 + 76) \times (5 - (\sqrt{4} - 32 + 1)) \\
2619 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2620 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2621 &:= -9 - (7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2622 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 87 + 6^5)/((4 - 3 + 2) \times 1) \\
2623 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - ((6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2624 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2625 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2626 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2627 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times 6 - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2628 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2629 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - ((6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2630 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2631 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2632 &:= (987 + 6 - 5! + 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\
2633 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2634 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2635 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2636 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2637 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2638 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2639 &:= 9 + 87 \times 6 \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 + 1 \\
2640 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2641 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 - 5 + 4)!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2642 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6! + 5 + 4)/3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
2643 &:= -9 - 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2644 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2644 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2645 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 2645 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2646 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2646 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3^{2+1} \\
2647 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2647 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2648 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 2648 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
2649 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5!) + (6 + 7 - 8)! + \sqrt{9} & 2649 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2650 &:= (1 - 2 - 3! \times 45 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 2650 &:= (98 - 76) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2651 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2651 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2652 &:= -1 - 2 - 3^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2652 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
2653 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2653 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2654 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2654 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2655 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - (4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2655 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2656 &:= -1 + 2 - 3^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2656 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2657 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2657 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2658 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2658 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2659 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2659 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2660 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2660 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2661 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2661 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2662 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2662 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5)/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2663 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2663 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - ((6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2664 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2664 &:= (\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} - 7) \times (65 - 4! - 3 \times 2 + 1) \\
2665 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2665 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2666 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2666 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2667 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 2667 &:= 8 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
2668 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 2668 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2669 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3! \times 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2669 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2670 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2670 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4! - (3 - 2 + 1)) \\
2671 &:= -1 + 2 - ((3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2671 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2672 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 2672 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
2673 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2673 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2674 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 2674 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2675 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 2675 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2676 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4!) + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 2676 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2677 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 2677 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + (6 - 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2678 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!)) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 2678 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
2679 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2679 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2680 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 2680 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
2681 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2681 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2682 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2683 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2684 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2685 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2686 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2687 &:= -1 + (2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2688 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2689 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2690 &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3) - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
2691 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
2692 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
2693 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2694 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2695 &:= -1 - 2^{3!+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2696 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2697 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2698 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2699 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))/4 \\
2700 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2701 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2702 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
2703 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2704 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2705 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)!/4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2706 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2707 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2708 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2709 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 - 4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2710 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2711 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2712 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2713 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2714 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2715 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2716 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2717 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2718 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2719 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2720 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2682 &:= (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + (7 \times 6! + 5! + 4!)/\sqrt{3 + 2 - 1} \\
2683 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2684 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2685 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2686 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2687 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2688 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2689 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2690 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3!^{2+1}) \\
2691 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4! - 32 \times 1 \\
2692 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
2693 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + (6 - 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2694 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 54 \times 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
2695 &:= (9 - 8 + 76) \times (5!/4 + 3 + 2 \times 1) \\
2696 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2697 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2698 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2699 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
2700 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2701 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2702 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5 + 4)^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
2703 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2704 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
2705 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2706 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2707 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!^{2+1}) \\
2708 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2709 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2710 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! \times 5/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2711 &:= -9 + 8 - (7!/6! - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2712 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2713 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2714 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2715 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2716 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4 - 3!!/(2 + 1)! \\
2717 &:= -7 \times 6 - 9 + 8 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2718 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2719 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2720 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2721 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2722 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2723 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2724 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2725 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2726 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2727 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2728 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2729 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2730 &:= (123 + 4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7) \times (8 - 9) \\
2731 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2732 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2733 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2734 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2735 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6)!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2736 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2737 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2738 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2739 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2740 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2741 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2742 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2743 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2744 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2745 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2746 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2747 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2748 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2749 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2750 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
2751 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2752 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2753 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2754 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2755 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2756 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2757 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2758 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2759 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2760 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2721 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2722 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2723 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2724 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2725 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2726 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2727 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2728 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2729 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2730 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2731 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2732 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2733 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2734 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2735 &:= 9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4! + (3!/2 \times 1)! \\
2736 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2737 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2738 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2739 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2740 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2741 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2742 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2743 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2744 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2745 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2746 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2747 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2748 &:= (98 + 7) \times (5 \times 4 + 6) + 3! \times (2 + 1) \\
2749 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2750 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2751 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2752 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2753 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2754 &:= 9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 + (2 \times 1 - 4 + 3) \\
2755 &:= (\sqrt{9})! + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - (\sqrt{4} - 3! - 2 + 1) \\
2756 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2757 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2758 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2759 &:= -9/(8 + 7 - 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2760 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (6!/5 + 4 - 32 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2761 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2762 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2763 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2764 &:= 1 \times ((2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6) - (7 + 8) \times 9 \\
2765 &:= 1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 - (7 + 8) \times 9 \\
2766 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2767 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2768 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2769 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2770 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2771 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2772 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2773 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2774 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2775 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2776 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2777 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2778 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2779 &:= 1 - 2345 - 6 + 7! + 89 \\
2780 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2781 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2782 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2783 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2784 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2785 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2786 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2787 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2788 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2789 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2790 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2791 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2792 &:= (1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 + 7 - 89 \\
2793 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2794 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2795 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2796 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2797 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2798 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2799 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2800 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2761 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2762 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2763 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6! / 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2764 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2765 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2766 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2767 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2768 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!) / 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2769 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2770 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2771 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2772 &:= -9 \times \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2773 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2774 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2775 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2776 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2777 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2778 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! - 6!) / (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2779 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2780 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7! / 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2781 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 + 54) \times 3^2 \times 1 \\
2782 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
2783 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2784 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) / (7 + 6 + 5) \\
2785 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2786 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2787 &:= (98 \times 7 - 6 + 5 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
2788 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2789 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2790 &:= 987 - 6! + 5! \times (4! - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
2791 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 6! \\
2792 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2793 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2794 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2795 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2796 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2797 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2798 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2799 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2800 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - (8 - 76) \times 5 + 4) \times (3! + 2 \times 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2801 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2802 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2803 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2804 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2805 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2806 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2807 &:= ((1 + 2)!! - 3!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
2808 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2809 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2810 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2811 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2812 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2813 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2814 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2815 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2816 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
2817 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2818 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2819 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2820 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2821 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2822 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2823 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2824 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2825 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2826 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2827 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2828 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2829 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2830 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2831 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2832 &:= (1 + 2) \times (34 + 5! + 6! + 7!/(8 \times 9)) \\
2833 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2834 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2835 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2836 &:= 1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5) \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
2837 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2838 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2839 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2840 &:= 1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 56 - 7) \times 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2801 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2802 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2803 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2804 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2805 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2806 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2807 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2808 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2809 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2810 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2811 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2812 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2813 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2814 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2815 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2816 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2817 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2818 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2819 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2820 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
2821 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2822 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2823 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2824 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2825 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2826 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2827 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2828 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2829 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6)!/5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2830 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2831 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2832 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(5 + 4) \\
2833 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2834 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2835 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2836 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
2837 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2838 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2839 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2840 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2841 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2842 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2843 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2844 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2845 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2846 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2847 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2848 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2849 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2850 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2851 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2852 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2853 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2854 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2855 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2856 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2857 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2858 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2859 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2860 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2861 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2862 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2863 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2864 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2865 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2866 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2867 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2868 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2869 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2870 &:= 1^2 \times (3 + 4 + 567) \times (8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
2871 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2872 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2873 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2874 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2875 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2876 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2877 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2878 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2879 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2880 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2841 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2842 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2843 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (6 \times 5 + 7) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2844 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2845 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2846 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2847 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2848 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2849 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2850 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2851 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2852 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2853 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2854 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2855 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2856 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2857 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2858 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2859 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2860 &:= (((\sqrt{9})! - 8) \times (7 - 6!) + 5 + \sqrt{4} - 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
2861 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2862 &:= 9 + 87 + 6 + 5! \times (4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1) \\
2863 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2864 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/(7 + 6 + 5) \\
2865 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2866 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2867 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2868 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2869 &:= -9 + 8/(7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2870 &:= (9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) \times (5! + 4^3 + 21) \\
2871 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7!/6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2872 &:= -9 + (8 - 7)^{65} + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2873 &:= -9 - 8/(7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2874 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2875 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2876 &:= -9 \times 8/(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2877 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2878 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2879 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2880 &:= -(-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! \times (-5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2881 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2882 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2883 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2884 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2885 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2886 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2887 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2888 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2889 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2890 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2891 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2892 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2893 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2894 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2895 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2896 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2897 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2898 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2899 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2900 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2901 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2902 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2903 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2904 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + 4! + 5 \times 67) \times 8 + 9 \\
2905 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2906 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2907 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2908 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2909 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2910 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2911 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2912 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2913 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2914 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2915 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2916 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2917 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2918 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2919 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2920 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2881 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2882 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2883 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2884 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2885 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2886 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2887 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2888 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
2889 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2890 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2891 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! / 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2892 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2893 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2894 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7! / 6!)! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2895 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2896 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2897 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2898 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! / (6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
2899 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) / 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2900 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2901 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2902 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2903 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2904 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2905 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2906 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2907 &:= \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 65)} \times (\sqrt{4} + (3 + 2)! - 1) \\
2908 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2909 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2910 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2911 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2912 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2913 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2914 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2915 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2916 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2917 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2918 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2919 &:= 98 + 7 + (6 + 5! + 4! / 3) \times 21 \\
2920 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2921 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2922 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2923 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2924 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2925 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2926 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2927 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2928 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2929 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times \sqrt{4} - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2930 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2931 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - (4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2932 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2933 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2934 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2935 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2936 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2937 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2938 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2939 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2940 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2941 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2942 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
2943 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2944 &:= -1 + 2 - 3^4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2945 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2946 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2947 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2948 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2949 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2950 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2951 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2952 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
2953 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2954 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2955 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2956 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2957 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2958 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2959 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2960 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2921 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2922 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2923 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2924 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2925 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2926 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2929 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2930 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2931 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2932 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2933 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2934 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2935 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2936 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
2937 &:= 98 - 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\
2938 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2939 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6! + 5!) / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2940 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2941 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2942 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2943 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2944 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2945 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2946 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6 + 5 + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2947 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2948 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2949 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 76 + 54 + 321) \\
2950 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2951 &:= 9 - 87 + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\
2952 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6! / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2953 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2954 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6 + 5 + 4)) + 3! / (2 + 1) \\
2955 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2956 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2957 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2958 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6 + 5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2959 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2960 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4^{3+2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2961 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2962 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2963 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2964 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2965 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2966 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2967 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2968 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2969 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2970 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2971 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2972 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2973 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2974 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2975 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2976 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2977 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2978 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2979 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 \times 89 \\
2980 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2981 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 45 \times (-7 \times 8 + 6) + 9 \\
2982 &:= 1^2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 67 - 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\
2983 &:= 1^2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2984 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2985 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2986 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
2987 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2988 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2989 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
2990 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2991 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2992 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2993 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! / 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2994 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
2995 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
2996 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2997 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2998 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2999 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3000 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2961 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
2962 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
2963 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2964 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2965 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2966 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2967 &:= 987 \times (6 - 5 - 4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)! \\
2968 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
2969 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2970 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2971 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2972 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! / 6 - (5 + 4 - 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
2973 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 \times 6! / 5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
2974 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2975 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2976 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2977 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
2978 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! + 3!!)) - 2 - 1) \\
2979 &:= -9 \times (\sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
2980 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2981 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
2982 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2983 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2984 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2985 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
2986 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2987 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2988 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2989 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
2990 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2991 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2992 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2993 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
2994 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2995 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2996 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2997 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
2998 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
2999 &:= -9 / (8 + 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3000 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3002 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3003 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3004 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3005 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3006 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3007 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3008 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3009 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3010 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3011 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3012 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3013 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3014 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3015 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3016 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3017 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3018 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3019 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3020 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3021 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3022 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3023 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + (4 + 5 - 6)!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3024 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3025 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3026 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3027 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3028 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3029 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3030 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3031 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3032 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3033 &:= 1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3034 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3035 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3036 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3037 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3038 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3039 &:= (12 - 3 \times (-5 \times 67 + 4) + 8) \times \sqrt{9}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3002 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3003 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3004 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3005 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! / 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3006 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!) / (6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3007 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4!) + 32 \times 1 \\
3008 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3009 &:= 9 / (8 + 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3!! + 2 \times 1) \\
3010 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3011 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3012 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3013 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3014 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3015 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3016 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3017 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3018 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3019 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times (4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
3020 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3021 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 - \sqrt{4} - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
3022 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3023 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3024 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3025 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3026 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
3027 &:= (9 - 8 + 7! \times 3 / (6 + 5 + 4)) \times (2 + 1) \\
3028 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! / 5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
3029 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3030 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3031 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! / 6! + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3032 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - (5! - 4 - 3))) / (2 + 1) \\
3033 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3034 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! / (5 + 4) - 3! - (2 + 1)!! \\
3035 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3036 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3037 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! / 6! + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3038 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3039 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3040 &:= 123 \times 4! - 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 \\
3041 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3042 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7) \times 89) \\
3043 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3! + 4) \times (5! + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3044 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3045 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3046 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3047 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3048 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
3049 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3050 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3051 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3052 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3053 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3054 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4 - (56 + 7) \times 8 - 9) \\
3055 &:= ((12 + 3!) \times 4! - 56 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
3056 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3057 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3058 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3059 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3060 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3061 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3062 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3063 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - \sqrt{4^{5!/\sqrt{6 \times (7+8+9)}}}) \\
3064 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4^5} - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3065 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3066 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3067 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3068 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3069 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - (4 - 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3070 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3071 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
3072 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3073 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - (4 - 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3074 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + (\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3075 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3076 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3077 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3040 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3041 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3042 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3043 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4) \\
3044 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3045 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3046 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3047 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3048 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3049 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7^{(6-5) \times 4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3050 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3051 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3052 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3053 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3054 &:= ((9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5 - \sqrt{4}) - 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
3055 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3056 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
3057 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3058 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3059 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3060 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3061 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3062 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3063 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3064 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3065 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3066 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3067 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
3068 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3069 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3070 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3071 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3072 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3073 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3074 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3075 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3076 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3077 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$3078 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3079 := -1 + (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3080 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3081 := ((1 + 2)! - 3) \times 4^5 \times (6 - 7)^8 + 9$$

$$3082 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3083 := -1 + 2^{3!} - 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3084 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3085 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3086 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3087 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3088 := -1 \times 2^{3^{\sqrt{4}}} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3089 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3090 := (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!}) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3091 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3092 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3093 := 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times 56 + 78 - 9$$

$$3094 := -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3095 := (1 \times 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! + 7 + 89)$$

$$3096 := -1 + 2 + (3 + \sqrt{4})^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3097 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3098 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$3099 := -1 - ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3100 := -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3101 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3102 := 1 - 2 - 3! \times 4 + 56 \times 7 \times 8 - 9$$

$$3103 := 12 \times 3 - \sqrt{4} + (6 \times 7 \times 8 + 5) \times 9$$

$$3104 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3105 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3106 := -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3107 := (1 + 23) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 \times 7 + 89$$

$$3108 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3109 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)})$$

$$3110 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3111 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3112 := -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3113 := -1 + (2 - 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3114 := -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3115 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3078 := -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))/6!$$

$$3079 := -9 - (8 - 7 + 6)!/5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3080 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3081 := -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3082 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3083 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$3084 := (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3085 := (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3086 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3087 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3088 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3089 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3090 := (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3091 := (9 - 8 + 765) \times 4 + 3! + 21$$

$$3092 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3093 := -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3094 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3095 := -9 + (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$3096 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3097 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$3098 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3099 := -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3100 := (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3101 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6^5/4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$3102 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times \sqrt{(6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}} \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3103 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3104 := ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!) \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3105 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3106 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3107 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3108 := (-9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3109 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3110 := 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 + 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$3111 := -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3112 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3113 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3114 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3115 := \sqrt{(7 \times 6 - 9 - 8)^5} - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3116 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3117 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3! - \sqrt{4} - 5 + 6) \times 7 \times 89 \\
3118 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3119 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3120 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3121 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3122 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (-5 \times 6 + 4) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3123 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3124 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3125 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3126 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)^{(4-5+6)!/(7+8+9)} \\
3127 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 - (5! - 6 \times 78) \times 9 \\
3128 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3129 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3130 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3131 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3132 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3133 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3134 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
3135 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3136 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3137 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3138 &:= (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3139 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3140 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3141 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3142 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3143 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3144 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3145 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3146 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5! \times 6/(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3147 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3148 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3149 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3150 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3151 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3152 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3153 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 \\
3154 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3116 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
3117 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3118 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3119 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3120 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3121 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3122 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3123 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5/6!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3124 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3125 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3126 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6 - 5 + 4!) - 3^2 - 1 \\
3127 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3128 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5 - (4! + 3!)) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3129 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
3130 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3131 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3132 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3133 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3134 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5^4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
3135 &:= \sqrt{(7 \times 6 - 9 - 8)^5} + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3136 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6!) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3137 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3138 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3139 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3140 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 + 3!^{2+1} \\
3141 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3142 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3143 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3144 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
3145 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3146 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6 - 5 + 4!) + 3^2 + 1 \\
3147 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3148 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3149 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3150 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3151 &:= (9 + 87)/6 + (5! - 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
3152 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5^4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)! \\
3153 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3154 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3155 &:= (1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5) \times 6 \times 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
3156 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3157 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3158 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9 \\
3159 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 - 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3160 &:= 12 \times 3! \times 45 - (6! + 7!)/(8 \times 9) \\
3161 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3162 &:= (1 + 2) \times 34 \times (5! + (6 - 7) \times 89) \\
3163 &:= (1 + 2)!! \times 3! + (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times 89 \\
3164 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3165 &:= (1 + 2)! - (34 + 5) \times (6 - 78 - 9) \\
3166 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3167 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3168 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3169 &:= (1 + 2)!! + 34 \times (5 + 67) - 8 + 9 \\
3170 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (-5 \times 6 + 4) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3171 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
3172 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3173 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3174 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3175 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3176 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3177 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3178 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3179 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4) - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3180 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3181 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3182 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3183 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3184 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3185 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3186 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3187 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3188 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3189 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3190 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3191 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3192 &:= (1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5) \times 6 \times 7 \times (8 - 9) \\
3193 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3155 &:= \sqrt{9} + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3! + 2 \times 1 \\
3156 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5)/\sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3157 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3158 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
3159 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3160 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6!/5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3161 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
3162 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3163 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3164 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 + 3!!/(2 + 1) \\
3165 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3166 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3167 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3168 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3169 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3170 &:= -9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3171 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3172 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
3173 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
3174 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3175 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3176 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5)/\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3177 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 + 6! - 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3178 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
3179 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3180 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3181 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3182 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3183 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3184 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! \times 5!/6! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3185 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3186 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3187 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3188 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3189 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3190 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3191 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/(6 + 5!) \\
3192 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3193 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3194 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4} + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3195 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 - (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
3196 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3197 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3198 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4^5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3199 &:= (1 - 2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 67 \times 89 \\
3200 &:= 1 + 2 - 3! + 4! + (5! + 67) \times (8 + 9) \\
3201 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3202 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3203 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3204 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3205 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!!/4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3206 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4} + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3207 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3208 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3209 &:= -1 + (2 - (3 - 4!) \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3210 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3211 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3212 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3213 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3214 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 - (4 - 5 \times (6! - 78) - 9) \\
3215 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3216 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) + 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3217 &:= 1^{23} + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 \times 9) \\
3218 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3219 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3220 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3221 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3222 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3223 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3224 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3225 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
3226 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! - 6 - 7)/4 + 8 + 9 \\
3227 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3228 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3229 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
3230 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3231 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3232 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3194 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3195 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3196 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3197 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3198 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3199 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3200 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4)) \times (2 + 1)/3! \\
3201 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4! + 32 + 1) \\
3202 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3203 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3204 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3205 &:= 9 - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! - 4! - (3 - 2 + 1)) \\
3206 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
3207 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3208 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4)) \times (2 + 1)/3! \\
3209 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3210 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3211 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3212 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3213 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3214 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3215 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3216 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3217 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3218 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
3219 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3220 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3!!/(2 + 1) \\
3221 &:= -9 + (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3222 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6!) \\
3223 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3224 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
3225 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3226 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3227 &:= 9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3228 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! + 6! \times 5)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3229 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3230 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3231 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3232 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3233 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3234 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3235 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3236 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3237 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3238 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3239 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3240 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3241 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3242 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3243 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3244 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3^4) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3245 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3246 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3247 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3248 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
3249 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3250 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3251 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3252 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3253 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
3254 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6 + 7) / 4 + 8 + 9 \\
3255 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3256 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3257 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3258 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3259 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3260 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3!! - 4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3261 &:= -1 - 2 - ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3262 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3263 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3264 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3265 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3266 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3267 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3268 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3269 &:= -1 - (2 + 3^{\sqrt{4}} - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3270 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3271 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3233 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3234 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3235 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3236 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3237 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! / 6! + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3238 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
3239 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3240 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3241 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4! + 3) - 2 + 1 \\
3242 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6!) + 5) / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3243 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3244 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3245 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3246 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3247 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3248 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3249 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + (6 - 5!) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3250 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3251 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7! / 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3252 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3253 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
3254 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3255 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3256 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7! \times 5! / 6! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3257 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3258 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) \times (65 - 4! + 321) \\
3259 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3260 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! / 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3261 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3262 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3263 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
3264 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3265 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3266 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! / 6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3267 &:= -9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3268 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! / 6 - 5) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3269 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3270 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6! / 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3271 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3272 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3273 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
3274 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3^4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
3275 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3276 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3277 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3278 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3279 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3280 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3281 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3282 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3283 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
3284 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3285 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
3286 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3287 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4! + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3288 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3289 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3290 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 - \sqrt{4} + (5 \times 6 + 7) \times 89 \\
3291 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3292 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3293 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3294 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3295 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3296 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4)!/5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
3297 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3298 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3299 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3300 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3301 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3302 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3303 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3304 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3305 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3306 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3307 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3308 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3309 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3310 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3272 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3273 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3274 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3275 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3276 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 32 \times 1) \\
3277 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3278 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3279 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3280 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3281 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4) + 3)/2 \times 1 \\
3282 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3283 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
3284 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3285 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3286 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3287 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3288 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3289 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3290 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
3291 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3292 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3293 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 - 6!/5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3294 &:= \sqrt{9 \times (87 - 6)} \times 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3^{2+1} \\
3295 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + (6! + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3296 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
3297 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3298 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3299 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3300 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6! - 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3301 &:= 98 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 43^2 + 1 \\
3302 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3303 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3304 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3305 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) + 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3306 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6)!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3307 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3308 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3309 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3310 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) - 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3311 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3312 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3313 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3314 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3315 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3316 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3317 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3318 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3319 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3320 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3321 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3322 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
3323 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3324 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3325 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3326 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3327 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3328 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3329 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3330 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3331 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3332 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) \\
3333 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3334 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3335 &:= (1 \times 23 \times 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 - 9) \\
3336 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3337 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3338 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) + 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
3339 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3340 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3341 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3342 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3343 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3344 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3345 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3346 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3347 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3348 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!/4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3349 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3311 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3312 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/(5 + 4) \\
3313 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3314 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3315 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3316 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) \times 4/5 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3317 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3318 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3319 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3320 &:= (98 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 \times 3/(2 + 1) \\
3321 &:= -9 - ((8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3322 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3323 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3324 &:= 9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3325 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3326 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3327 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3328 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3329 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
3330 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/6!) \\
3331 &:= 98 - 7 - 6 \times 5! \times (3 - 21)/4 \\
3332 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3333 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3334 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3335 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3336 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 - (5!/\sqrt{4} - 3!!) \times 2 \times 1 \\
3337 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3338 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3339 &:= (9 - (8 \times 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!/3)) \times 21 \\
3340 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3341 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3342 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3343 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3344 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3345 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3346 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3347 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3348 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3349 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3350 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times \sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3351 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3352 &:= -1 \times (2^{3+4} - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3353 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9) \\
3354 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3355 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3356 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3357 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3358 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
3359 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3360 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3361 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
3362 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3363 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3364 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3365 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3366 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3367 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3368 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3369 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
3370 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 6/(4 + 5) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3371 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3372 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3373 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
3374 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
3375 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3376 &:= -1 \times (2 \times 3)! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
3377 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
3378 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3379 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3380 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3381 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3382 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3383 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3384 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3385 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3386 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3387 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3388 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3350 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3351 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
3352 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3353 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3354 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3355 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3356 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3357 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3358 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3359 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3360 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3361 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3362 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3363 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3364 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3365 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3366 &:= 9 \times (76 \times 5 + 8) - (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
3367 &:= -9 + 8^{7+6-5-4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3368 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3369 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3370 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3371 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7!/6 + 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3372 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3373 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3374 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3375 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3376 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3377 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3378 &:= (9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3379 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3380 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3381 &:= 98 \times 6 \times 5 \times 4!/(7 \times 3) + 21 \\
3382 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3383 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times 4!/5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3384 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! + 6!))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3385 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3386 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
3387 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3388 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$3389 := -1 - ((2 - 3! - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3390 := (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3391 := -1 + 2 - (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3392 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3393 := -1 - 2 - 3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3394 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3395 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! - 6)/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3396 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3397 := -1 + 2 - 3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3398 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3399 := -1 + 2^{3+4+5} - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3400 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3401 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3402 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3403 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 - 6! + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3404 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3405 := -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3406 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3407 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3408 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3409 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3410 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$3411 := -1 - 2^{3!} - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3412 := -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$3413 := -1 - 2 \times 3^4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3414 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3415 := -1 - 2^{3!} - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3416 := -1 \times (2^{3!} + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3417 := -1 - 2 - 3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3418 := -1 \times 2 - 3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3419 := -1 - ((2 - 3 + 4)! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3420 := (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3421 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3422 := -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$3423 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3424 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3425 := -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3426 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3427 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3389 := -9 + 8 - (7!/6! - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3390 := (9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3391 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$3392 := -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3393 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3394 := (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3395 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$3396 := 98 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!$$

$$3397 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3398 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - (5 \times (4! - 3!!)) - 2 - 1$$

$$3399 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3400 := -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6! \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1})$$

$$3401 := \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 \times 54 - 3!! + (2 + 1)!$$

$$3402 := (9 - 8)^7! \times 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3 \times 21$$

$$3403 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3404 := -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3405 := -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3406 := -9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3407 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3408 := (-9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3409 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3410 := -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3411 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3412 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3413 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3414 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3415 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3416 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3417 := -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3418 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3419 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3420 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3421 := -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$3422 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5 + 4)^{3!-2-1}$$

$$3423 := -9 - (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3424 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3425 := 9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! - 4! \times 3 - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$3426 := (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3427 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3428 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3429 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3430 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3431 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3432 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
3433 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3434 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3435 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3436 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3437 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3438 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3439 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3440 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3441 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3442 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! / 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3443 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! - 6) / 4 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3444 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3445 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3446 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3447 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3448 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3449 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3450 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3451 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3452 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3453 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3454 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3455 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3456 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3457 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3458 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3459 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3460 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3461 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3462 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3463 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3464 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3465 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3466 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3467 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3428 &:= 8 \times 7 - 9 - 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3429 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6^5 / 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3430 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4 - 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
3431 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3432 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! / 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3433 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 4 / 5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3434 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7! + 6!) / 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
3435 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3436 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3437 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3438 &:= (987 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
3439 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3440 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 4! / 5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3441 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3442 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 4! / 5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3443 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 4! / 5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3444 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! / 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3445 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3446 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3447 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 \times 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3448 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 5 \\
3449 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 5 \\
3450 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! / (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3451 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3452 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3453 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3454 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 4! / 5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3455 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3456 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times 6! / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3457 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3458 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6!) / 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3459 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3460 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3461 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3462 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3463 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3464 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3465 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3466 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3467 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3468 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3469 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3470 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3471 &:= -1 - 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3472 &:= -1 \times (2^{3+4} - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3473 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3474 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3475 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3476 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3477 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3478 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3479 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3480 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3481 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3482 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3483 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3484 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3485 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3486 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3487 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3488 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3489 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3490 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3491 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3492 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3493 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3494 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3495 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3496 &:= -1 \times (2^{3+4} - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3497 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3498 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3499 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3500 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3501 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (\sqrt{4} - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3502 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3503 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3504 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3505 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3506 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4^5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3507 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3468 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 4!/5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3469 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3470 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3471 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3472 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3473 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3474 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3475 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3476 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 8)^7 + 6! \times 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
3477 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - (6! - 5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3478 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3479 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3480 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3481 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3482 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3483 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3484 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3485 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3486 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!)/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3487 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3488 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3489 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3490 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3491 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3492 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3493 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3494 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
3495 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3496 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3497 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3498 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3499 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3500 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3501 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3502 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3503 &:= -9 \times 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3504 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3505 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3506 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3507 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3508 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3509 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3510 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3511 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3512 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3513 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9) \\
3514 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4! - 5 - 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9) \\
3515 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3516 &:= -1 - 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3517 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3518 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
3519 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3520 &:= -1 + 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3521 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3522 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3523 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3524 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3525 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3526 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3527 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3528 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3529 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3530 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3531 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3532 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3533 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3534 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3535 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3536 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3537 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3538 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3539 &:= -1 - (2 - (3! + 4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3540 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3541 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3542 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3543 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3544 &:= -1 + 2 - (3^4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3545 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3546 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3547 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3508 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6) \times 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3509 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3510 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (54 - 321) \\
3511 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3512 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3513 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 4!/5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3514 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3515 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3516 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3517 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3518 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3519 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3520 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5)) \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
3521 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3522 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3523 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3524 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3525 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3526 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3527 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3528 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times (5! \times 3/4 - (2 + 1)!) \\
3529 &:= 9 - 4 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3530 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3531 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3532 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3533 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6! - 5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3534 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3535 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3536 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3537 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3538 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3539 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3540 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3541 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3542 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3543 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3544 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3545 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3546 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3547 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3548 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3549 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3550 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3551 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3552 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3553 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3554 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3555 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3556 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3557 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3558 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3559 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3560 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3561 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3562 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3563 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3564 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3565 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3566 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3567 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3568 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3569 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3570 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3! + 4 + 5)!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3571 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3572 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3573 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3574 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3575 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3576 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3577 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3578 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3579 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3580 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3581 &:= 2 \times 3 - 1 - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3582 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3583 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3584 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3585 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3586 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3587 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3548 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3549 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3550 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3551 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3552 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3553 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3554 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3555 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3556 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3557 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3558 &:= -9 - 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3559 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3560 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3561 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3! - (2 + 1)!)! \\
3562 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3563 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3564 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3565 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3566 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3567 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3568 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3569 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3570 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3571 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3572 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3573 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3574 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3575 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3576 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3577 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3578 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3579 &:= -9 / (8 + 7 - 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3580 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3581 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3582 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3583 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3584 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3585 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3586 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3587 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3588 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3589 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3590 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3591 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3592 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3593 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3594 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3595 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3596 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3597 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3598 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3599 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! + 4 + 5)! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3600 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3! + 4 + 5))! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3601 &:= (-1 + 2)^{(3+4)!} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3602 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3603 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3604 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3605 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3606 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3607 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3608 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3609 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3610 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3611 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3612 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3613 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3614 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3615 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3616 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3617 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3618 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3619 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3620 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3621 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3622 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3623 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3624 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3625 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3626 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3627 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3588 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3589 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3590 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3591 &:= -9 - (8 - 7) \times 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3592 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3593 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3594 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 - 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3595 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3596 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3597 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3598 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3599 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3600 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7! - 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3601 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3602 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3603 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3604 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3605 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3606 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3607 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3608 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3609 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3610 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3611 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3612 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3613 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3614 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3615 &:= 9 \times (87 - 6) \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3616 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3617 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3618 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3619 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3620 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3621 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3622 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3623 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3624 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3625 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3626 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3627 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3628 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3629 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3630 &:= ((-1 + 2)^{(3+4)!} + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3631 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3632 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3633 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3634 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3635 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3636 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3637 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3638 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3639 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3640 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3641 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3642 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3643 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3644 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3645 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3646 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3647 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3648 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3649 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3650 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3651 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3652 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3653 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3654 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3655 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3656 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3657 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3658 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3659 &:= -1 + (2 + (3! + 4 - 5)!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3660 &:= (\sqrt{-1 - 2 + 3 + 4} + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3661 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3662 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3663 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3664 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6))) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3665 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4!) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3666 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) + 4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3628 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3629 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3630 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3631 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3632 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3633 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3634 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3635 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3636 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3637 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3638 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3639 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3640 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3641 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3642 &:= (-9 + 8 \times \sqrt{(7 \times (6 + 5))^{\sqrt{4}}} \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3643 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3644 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3645 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3646 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3647 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3648 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3649 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3650 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3651 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (\sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3652 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3653 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3654 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3655 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3656 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3657 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3658 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3659 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)!! \\
3660 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3661 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3662 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3663 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3664 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3665 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3666 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3667 &:= -1 + 2^3! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3668 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3669 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3670 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3671 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3672 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3673 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3674 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3675 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3676 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3677 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3678 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3679 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3680 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3681 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3682 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3683 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! - 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3684 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3685 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3686 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3687 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3688 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3689 &:= 1^2 \times ((3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! - 7!) + 89 \\
3690 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3691 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3692 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3693 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3694 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3695 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3696 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3697 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 - 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3698 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3699 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3700 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3701 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3702 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3703 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3704 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3667 &:= 98 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
3668 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3669 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! - 4!) \times (32 + 1) \\
3670 &:= \sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} + 6! \times 5 - 4/(3 + 2 - 1) \\
3671 &:= 98 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 21 \\
3672 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3673 &:= (9 - 8 - 76 + 5^4 \times 3! - 2) \times 1 \\
3674 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
3675 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3676 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3677 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3678 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3679 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3680 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)^5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
3681 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3682 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
3683 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3684 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3685 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - (6! - 5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3686 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3687 &:= -9 + 8 \times \sqrt{(7 \times (6 + 5))}^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3688 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3689 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3690 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3691 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! \times 4! \times (3 - 2) + 1 \\
3692 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3693 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5! + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3694 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3695 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3696 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3697 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3698 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3699 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3700 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3701 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3702 &:= \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6! \times 5 - 4! + 3!^2 \times 1 \\
3703 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6) \times 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3704 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3705 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3706 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3707 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3708 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3709 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3710 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3711 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3712 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3713 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3714 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3715 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3716 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3717 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3718 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3719 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3720 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3721 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3722 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3723 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3724 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3725 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3726 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3727 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3728 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3729 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3730 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3731 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3732 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3733 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3734 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3735 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3736 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3737 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3738 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3739 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3740 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3741 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3742 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3743 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3744 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3705 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3706 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3707 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3708 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3709 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3710 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3711 &:= 98 - 7 + 6! \times 5 - (4 - 3 - 21) \\
3712 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3713 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3714 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3715 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3716 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3717 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3718 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3719 &:= -9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3720 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3721 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3722 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
3723 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3724 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3725 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3726 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5!/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3727 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3728 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
3729 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - (6! - 5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3730 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3731 &:= -9 - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3732 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3733 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3734 &:= 98/7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 32 + 1) \\
3735 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3736 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 65 - (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1 \\
3737 &:= (9 - (8 - 7)^{65})^4 - 3!!/2 + 1 \\
3738 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3739 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3740 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3741 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3742 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
3743 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3744 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3745 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3746 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3747 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3748 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3749 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3750 &:= (-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3751 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3752 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
3753 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3754 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3755 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3756 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3757 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3758 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3759 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3760 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3761 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3762 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3763 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3764 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3765 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3766 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3767 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3768 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3769 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3770 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
3771 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4! \times 5!) \times (8 + 9)/(6 + 7) \\
3772 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
3773 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3774 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3775 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3776 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
3777 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3778 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3779 &:= -1 + ((2 - 3 + 4)! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3780 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3781 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3782 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3783 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3745 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3746 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7! - 6^{5-4+3} + 2 \times 1 \\
3747 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3748 &:= (9 - 87) \times 6 + 5! + (4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
3749 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 \times (54 - 3 - 2) + 1 \\
3750 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3751 &:= 9 - 8 - 7! + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)! \\
3752 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6!)/(5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
3753 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3754 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3755 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3756 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 32 + 1 \\
3757 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3758 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4) - 3!/(2 + 1) \\
3759 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3760 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3761 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3762 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3763 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3764 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3765 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3766 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3767 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3768 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3769 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4! + 3!! + 2 - 1 \\
3770 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3771 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3772 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3773 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3774 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3775 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3776 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5! - 4) \times (32 - 1) \\
3777 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3778 &:= 9 \times (8 + 76) \times 5 - (\sqrt{4} + 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3779 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3780 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3781 &:= 9 + 87 \times 6 + ((5 - 4!) \times 3)^2 + 1 \\
3782 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times ((5! - 4!) \times 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3783 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3784 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3785 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3^4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3786 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5)! + 6 \times 7 \times 89 \\
3787 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3788 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^{4+5-6} + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3789 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3790 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3791 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3792 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3793 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3794 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3795 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3796 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3797 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (5 + 6 + 7)/4! + 8 + 9 \\
3798 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 + (56 + 78) \times 9 \\
3799 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3800 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3801 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3802 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3803 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! + 6)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3804 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3805 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3806 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3807 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3808 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3809 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3810 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3811 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3812 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5) + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3813 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3814 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
3815 &:= (-2 \times 3 + 1) \times (\sqrt{4^5} - 6 - 789) \\
3816 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!)/(\sqrt{4} - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3817 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3818 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3819 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3820 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3821 &:= (-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3822 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3784 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)! \\
3785 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3786 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3787 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3788 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3789 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1}) \\
3790 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5 \times 4 - 321) \\
3791 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3792 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3793 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3794 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3!!) - 2 - 1) \\
3795 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4! + 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
3796 &:= (98 \times 76 + 5! + (4!/3!))/2 \times 1 \\
3797 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
3798 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3799 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3800 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 - 5) \times 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
3801 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\
3802 &:= -9 - ((8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
3803 &:= 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 \times (4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1) \\
3804 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3805 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3806 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5^4 - 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
3807 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3808 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3809 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3810 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3811 &:= 98 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 \times 1)! \\
3812 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3813 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!/5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3814 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (5 \times 4 + 6) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3815 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3816 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3817 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3818 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
3819 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3820 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3821 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3822 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5) \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3823 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3824 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3 - 4 + 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3825 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - (5 - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
3826 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3827 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
3828 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
3829 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
3830 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3831 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4! + 5 \times 678 + 9 \\
3832 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3833 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
3834 &:= (1^2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (-8 \times 9 + 5 + 6 + 7) \\
3835 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3836 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3837 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3838 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3839 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3840 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3841 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3842 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3843 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3844 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3845 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
3846 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3847 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3848 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
3849 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3850 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3851 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
3852 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3853 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3854 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3855 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3856 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3857 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3858 &:= (1 + 23 + 4) \times 5! + (7 \times 8 \times 9 - 6) \\
3859 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3860 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3861 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3823 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3824 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
3825 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3826 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4!) - 3! - 2 \times 1 \\
3827 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 \times 65 + 4!) - 3^2 + 1 \\
3828 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3829 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3830 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3831 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3832 &:= (98/7 - 6) \times 5! \times 4 - 3^2 + 1 \\
3833 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3834 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3835 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3836 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3837 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3838 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3839 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3840 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3841 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3842 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3843 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!)/(5 + 4 + 3)) - 2 - 1 \\
3844 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3845 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3846 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
3847 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3848 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3849 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
3850 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3851 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!) + 5^{\sqrt{4+3}} - 2 + 1 \\
3852 &:= -9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3853 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3854 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) + 3!/(2 + 1)) \\
3855 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3856 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3857 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3858 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3859 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3860 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
3861 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$3862 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3863 := 1^2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3864 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3865 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3866 := (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3867 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3868 := -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3869 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3870 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3871 := -1 + (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3872 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3873 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3874 := (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3875 := -1 + \sqrt{(2 + 3!!)} \times \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$3876 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3877 := -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$3878 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$3879 := (-1 + 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3880 := (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$3881 := -1 + 2 \times 3^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3882 := (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$3883 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3884 := -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3885 := (1 - 2 + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 + 6! + 7 \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$3886 := 1 + 23 + 4 + 5! + 6 \times 7 \times 89$$

$$3887 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3888 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3889 := (1 \times 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 78 - 9)$$

$$3890 := -1 - (2 - 3!!/4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$3891 := -1 + (2 - 3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3892 := 1^2 + 3 + 4! + 56 \times (78 - 9)$$

$$3893 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$3894 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3895 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3896 := -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$3897 := -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3898 := -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3899 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3862 := 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3!! + 2) - 1$$

$$3863 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3864 := 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 65 + 4! \times 3^2 - 1$$

$$3865 := -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3866 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5^4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$3867 := ((\sqrt{9})!)/(8 + 7) + 6! \times 5 - 4 + 32 - 1$$

$$3868 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$3869 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3870 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$3871 := -9 - (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3872 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$3873 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3874 := -9 - 8 - ((7! + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$3875 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3876 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3877 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3878 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5)/\sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$3879 := -9 + (8 + (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3880 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3881 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3882 := (-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3883 := -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3884 := (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3885 := \sqrt{9} \times (87 \times (6 + 5 + 4) - 3^2 - 1)$$

$$3886 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5/\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3887 := -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3888 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3889 := (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3890 := -9 + 8 - ((7! + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$3891 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$3892 := (9 - 8) \times 7! - 6! + 5 - 432 - 1$$

$$3893 := -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3894 := (\sqrt{9})! + \sqrt{87 - 6} \times 54 \times (3! + 2 \times 1)$$

$$3895 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$3896 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!/(5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$3897 := -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$3898 := (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$3899 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3900 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3901 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3902 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! / (4 + 5) - 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3903 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4^5 + 6 + 7) / (8 + 9) \\
3904 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3905 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! \times (5! + 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3906 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3907 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
3908 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3909 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3 - \sqrt{4})^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3910 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3911 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (5 + 6) / 4 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3912 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3913 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9) \\
3914 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3915 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3916 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3917 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3918 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3919 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5!) - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
3920 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
3921 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9) \\
3922 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3923 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)) \\
3924 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)) \\
3925 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! / 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3926 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
3927 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3928 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3929 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3930 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3931 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3932 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3933 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3934 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3935 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3936 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3937 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3938 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3900 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3901 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3902 &:= 9 \times 87 - 6 + 5^{(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{3^2 \times 1})} \\
3903 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3904 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3905 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3906 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5!) \times (4 - 32 + 1) \\
3907 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! / 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3908 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3909 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
3910 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7! / 6 - 5! - 4!) / 3 - 2 \times 1) \\
3911 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3912 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times 4^{3-2+1} \\
3913 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3914 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4)^3 / (2 + 1) \\
3915 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
3916 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3917 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3918 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3919 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) \times 4 / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3920 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
3921 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3922 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 65^{\sqrt{4}} - 321 \\
3923 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
3924 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3925 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3926 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6! - 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3928 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! / 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3929 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3930 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
3931 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3932 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3933 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3934 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3)! - 2 \times 1 \\
3935 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3936 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3937 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4) - 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3938 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3939 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3940 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3941 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3942 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3943 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3944 &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3) - 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3945 &:= 1^2 \times 3!! + 4! \times (56 + 78) + 9 \\
3946 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (5 + 6)/\sqrt{4} - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3947 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)) \\
3948 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3949 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3950 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3951 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/\sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3952 &:= \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4!+5!}} - 6} \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3953 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) - 9 \\
3954 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)!/4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
3955 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
3956 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3957 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3958 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3959 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3960 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! \times (\sqrt{4} - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3961 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3962 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3963 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4!)^5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
3964 &:= (-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4))^5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
3965 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
3966 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!)) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3967 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3968 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3969 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!})^{4 \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
3970 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
3971 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
3972 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3973 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3974 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3975 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3939 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - 6!)/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3940 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3941 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3942 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/\sqrt{6!}/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3943 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3944 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3945 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3946 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 32 \times 1) \\
3947 &:= \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6! \times 5 + 432 - 1 \\
3948 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3949 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
3950 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 543 \times 2 + 1 \\
3951 &:= 9 \times (876 - 5! + 4 - 321) \\
3952 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 - 5! - 43 - 2 + 1 \\
3953 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4) - 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
3954 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3955 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3956 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/6!) - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3957 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3958 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3959 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3960 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3961 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
3962 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3963 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3964 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
3965 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
3966 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5)/\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3967 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3968 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1}) \\
3969 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3970 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4! + 3)) \times (2 - 1) \\
3971 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3972 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times ((7 \times 6 + 8 + 5) \times \sqrt{4} \times 3! + 2 \times 1) \\
3973 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3974 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3975 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3976 &:= (1 + 23 + 4) \times (5! - 67 + 89) \\
3977 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3978 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3979 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3980 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times 4! - 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3981 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3982 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3983 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3984 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3985 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
3986 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3987 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
3988 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
3989 &:= 12 \times 3 + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
3990 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3991 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times ((4! + 5) \times 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
3992 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3993 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3994 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4} + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
3995 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3996 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
3997 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3998 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
3999 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4000 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4001 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4002 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! / 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4003 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4004 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 + 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4005 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4006 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! + 6 + 7) / 4 + 8 + 9 \\
4007 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! / 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4008 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4009 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
4010 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - 5 - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
4011 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4012 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4013 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3976 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3977 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3978 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5) - \sqrt{4})) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3979 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 - (5! - 4^{3!} - 2 - 1) \\
3980 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3981 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3982 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 - 5) - 4 - 3!! \times 2 - 1 \\
3983 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3984 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
3985 &:= \sqrt{-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6} - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3986 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4! \times 32 + 1) \\
3987 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
3988 &:= -9 \times \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3989 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3990 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
3991 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 - (5! + 4 + 3 - 2) \times 1 \\
3992 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 - 5! - 4 - 3 + 2 + 1 \\
3993 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
3994 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
3995 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3996 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3997 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 - 4 - (3! - 2 + 1)! \\
3998 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4^{3!} + 2 + 1 \\
3999 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4000 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! / (5 + 4) + 3!! / (2 + 1) \\
4001 &:= 9 - (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4^{3!} + 2 - 1 \\
4002 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4003 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4004 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4005 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4006 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - 432 \times 1 \\
4007 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! / 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4008 &:= 9 - 87 - 6 - 5 + 4^{3!} + 2 - 1 \\
4009 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 4! / (6 \times 5) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4010 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6! / 5 + 4^{3!} - 21 \\
4011 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4012 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4013 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$4014 := (-1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!)) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$4015 := 1 + 2 + 3 - 4^5 - (6 - 7! - 8 + 9)$$

$$4016 := -1 \times (2^{3!+4} - ((5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9)!)$$

$$4017 := -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4018 := -1 - 2 - ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$4019 := -1 + (2 \times (3 + 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4020 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4021 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4022 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (5 \times 6 + 4) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4023 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4024 := ((1 + 2)!/3)^{4+56/7} - 8 \times 9$$

$$4025 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4026 := (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$4027 := -1 - 2 \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4028 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$4029 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(5 \times 6)$$

$$4030 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(5 \times 6)$$

$$4031 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4032 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$4033 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/(5 \times 6)$$

$$4034 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4035 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5 \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$4036 := -1 - 2 - 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$4037 := -1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$4038 := -1 + ((2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$4039 := -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4040 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4041 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - (\sqrt{4^{5+6}} - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4042 := (-1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6!)) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$4043 := -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$4044 := (-1 - 2 - (3 + 4)!/5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4045 := -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$4046 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4047 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4048 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4049 := (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5! + 6) + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$4050 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4051 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4014 := (9 - 8)^7! \times (6! - 54 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$4015 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4016 := \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) - (\sqrt{4} + 3!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$4017 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4018 := 98 \times (7 + 65 + \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1)$$

$$4019 := 9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4^{3!} - 2 + 1$$

$$4020 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4021 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4022 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$4023 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4024 := 98 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 - 3!^{2+1}$$

$$4025 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times 4!/(6 \times 5) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$4026 := ((\sqrt{9})!! - (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + \sqrt{4})) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$4027 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4028 := (98 \times 7 \times 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3! + 2)) \times 1$$

$$4029 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4030 := (-9 - 8 + 7!/\sqrt{6!/5}) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4031 := 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4032 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$4033 := -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6)^5) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4034 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$4035 := -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4036 := (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4037 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times 4!/(6 \times 5) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$4038 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4039 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4040 := (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4041 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4042 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4043 := 9 + 8 - 7 - 65 + 4^{3!} + 2 \times 1$$

$$4044 := (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4045 := -9 - (8 - 7 + 6)!/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4046 := (-9 - (8 - 7)^6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4047 := -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4048 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4049 := ((\sqrt{9})! - 8)^7 - 6!/5 + 4321$$

$$4050 := (9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4) - 3^{(2+1)!})$$

$$4051 := -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4052 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4053 := -1 - 2 + (3!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4054 := -1 \times 2 + (3!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4055 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4056 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4057 := -1 + 2 + (3!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4058 := -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4 - 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$4059 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4060 := 1 - (2 - 3!)^4 - 5 - 6! - 7! \times (8 - 9)$$

$$4061 := -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4062 := (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4063 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4064 := -1 + 2 - (3! - (4! + 5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$4065 := 1 - (2 + 3 \times 45 - 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4066 := \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4!+5!}}} - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4067 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4068 := (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$4069 := -1 - (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4070 := 1 + 2 \times 3! \times (5 \times 67 + 4) - 8 + 9$$

$$4071 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$4072 := (-1 + 2 + 3)^{(4+5-6)!} - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4073 := 1 \times 23 + 45 \times 6!/(7 - 8 + 9)$$

$$4074 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$4075 := 1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 89)$$

$$4076 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4077 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + \sqrt{4^{5+6}}) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4078 := \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4!+5!}}} + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4079 := -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4080 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4081 := -1 + 2 - (3! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$4082 := 1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5!) - 6 + 7! - 89$$

$$4083 := -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$4084 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$4085 := -1 + 2 \times (3^{\sqrt{4+5}} - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4086 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4087 := 1^2 + 3! - 4! + (5! + 6 \times 7 \times 8) \times 9$$

$$4088 := -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$4052 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4053 := (98 + 7 + 65) \times 4! - 3^{2+1}$$

$$4054 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4055 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4056 := ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4057 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4058 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4059 := (98 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4! \times 3) - 21$$

$$4060 := ((6 \times 5 + 987) \times 4 - 3! - 2) \times 1$$

$$4061 := -9 - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4062 := 9 + 87 + 6 + 5! \times (4 \times 3 + 21)$$

$$4063 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4064 := -9 \times 8 + 7!/(6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4065 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$4066 := -9 - 8 - 7 - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4067 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4068 := -9 \times ((8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$4069 := 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 54 \times 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$4070 := -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4071 := (98 + 7 + 65) \times 4! - 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$4072 := 987 \times 6!/5! - 43^2 - 1$$

$$4073 := 9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - 4^3 \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$4074 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$4075 := -9 - \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4076 := (6 \times 5 + 987) \times 4 + (3! + 2) \times 1$$

$$4077 := (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^6 - 5! + (4 + 3!)^2 + 1$$

$$4078 := \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 - 6!/5! + \sqrt{4^{3! \times 2 \times 1}}$$

$$4079 := (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! \times 5! \times 4/6! - 3! - 2 - 1$$

$$4080 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7! - 6!)/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$4081 := -9 - ((-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4082 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4083 := ((98 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 32) \times 1$$

$$4084 := (-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4085 := -9 - \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6 - 5} + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4086 := 9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$4087 := \sqrt{9} - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! + (\sqrt{4} + 3!)/2 \times 1$$

$$4088 := (987 + 6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4089 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4089 &:= -9 + \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6 - 5} + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4090 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (5 \times 6 + 4) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4090 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4^{3!} + 2 - 1 \\
4091 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4091 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 - (7 - 6! / 5! - 4^{3!} - 2 + 1) \\
4092 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4092 &:= (9 - 8 - 7 + 65 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (32 + 1) \\
4093 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! / 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4093 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 76 \times 54 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4094 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 - 5) \sqrt{6 \times (7+8+9)} & 4094 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6)^5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4095 &:= -1 + 2^{(3+4)!/5! - (6+7+8+9)} & 4095 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 \times 54 - 32 - 1 \\
4096 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4)^{5! / (6+7+8+9)} & 4096 &:= (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7)^{6+5} + 4^{3!} / 2 \times 1 \\
4097 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} & 4097 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 + 5 \times 4! - 3!! - 2 + 1 \\
4098 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4098 &:= (9 - 8) \times \sqrt{-7 + 6 + 5} + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4099 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4099 &:= -9 + \sqrt{8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)} + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4100 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4100 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^{6 \times 5 - 4!} + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
4101 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4101 &:= 98 - 7 - 65 + 4^{3!} - 21 \\
4102 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} & 4102 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4103 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! / 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4103 &:= \sqrt{9} - (-76 \times 54 + 8 - 3 - 2) - 1 \\
4104 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4104 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4105 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4105 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! / 6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4106 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 4106 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4107 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} & 4107 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4108 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4!) - (5 + 6 - 7) \times 89 & 4108 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4109 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4109 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! / 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4110 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4110 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4111 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4111 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4112 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 4112 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 - (5 - 4)^{3!} - 2 - 1 \\
4113 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - \sqrt{4^{5+6}}) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4113 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4114 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - \sqrt{4^{5+6}}) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4114 &:= 9 - (8 - 76 \times 54 - 3! - 2 - 1) \\
4115 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4115 &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 \times 54 + 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
4116 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4116 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4117 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! / 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4117 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4118 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 + 678 + 9) & 4118 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4119 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 4119 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4120 &:= (1 + 2)! + 3! + 4 + (5! + 6 \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 & 4120 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4121 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4121 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4122 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4122 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4123 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4123 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4124 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4124 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4125 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 - 4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 - 89 & 4125 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! / 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$4126 := \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{\sqrt{4!+5!}}} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$4127 := -1 + 2 \times (3!/(4 + 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4128 := (1 + 2 + 3!/(4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4129 := -1 - 2 - 3^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$4130 := 12 + 3 + 4 - 5! - 6! + 7! - 89$$

$$4131 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - \sqrt{4^{5+6}} - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4132 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - \sqrt{4^{5+6}} - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$4133 := -1 + (2 + 3! - 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4134 := (-1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4135 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$4136 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$4137 := -1 - 2 - (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4138 := -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4139 := -1 - (2 \times 3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4140 := (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4141 := -1 + 2 - (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4142 := -1 - 2 \times 3!/(4 + 5) - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$4143 := -1 + 2 \times ((3! - 4)^{5+6} + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4144 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times (\sqrt{4^{5+6}} + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4145 := -1 - (2 - 3 + 4)! \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4146 := (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4147 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4148 := (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4149 := -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4150 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4151 := (1 + 2)! - (3! \times 5/4 - 6 - 7! - 8 + 9)$$

$$4152 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) + (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4153 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4154 := (1 + 2)! \times 3! + \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{56 - 7} \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$4155 := -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4156 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4157 := -1 - 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4158 := (-1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4159 := -1 + 2^{3!} + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$4160 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4161 := (-1 - 2 + 3! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4162 := -1 - 2 + (3!/(4 + 5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$4163 := (-1 + 2 + 3!/(4)) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$4126 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4127 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4128 := -9 \times 8 - 7! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))/6$$

$$4129 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4130 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 5/6 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4131 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$4132 := 987 + (6 + 5!) \times 4! + (3 + 2)! + 1$$

$$4133 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 \times (5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$4134 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!/4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$4135 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$4136 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4137 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$4138 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$4139 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4140 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4141 := -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4142 := 9 \times 87 + (6! + 5!) \times 4 - 3!/(2 + 1)!$$

$$4143 := -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4144 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 43 - 2 - 1$$

$$4145 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4146 := 98 \times 7 \times 6 - (5 - \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1)$$

$$4147 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$4148 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4149 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$4150 := (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 5/6 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$4151 := -9 + (8 - 7!/6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4152 := -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4153 := -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5 - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$4154 := (8 \times 7 + 9) \times (65 - 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$4155 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$4156 := (9 - 8) \times (76 + 5 + 4^{3!} - 21)$$

$$4157 := -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$4158 := (9 - 8) \times 7! - 6! - (5 + 4) \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$4159 := -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$4160 := 9 \times (7 \times 65 + 8) + 4! - 32 + 1$$

$$4161 := -9 - ((8 - 7!/6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4162 := 9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5 - \sqrt{4} \times 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$4163 := -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4164 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4165 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4166 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4167 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4168 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4169 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4170 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4171 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4172 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4173 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4174 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4175 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4176 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4177 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4178 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4179 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4180 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4181 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4182 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4183 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4184 &:= (-1 + 2)^{(3+4)!} - 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4185 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4186 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4187 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4188 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4189 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4190 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4191 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!!/4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4192 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4193 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4194 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4195 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4196 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4197 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4198 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4199 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4200 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4201 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4202 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4203 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4164 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 + (5 - 4 + 3!)^2 - 1 \\
4165 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4166 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6! \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4167 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4168 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4169 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4170 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4171 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4172 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7! \times 5/6 + 4 - 32 \times 1 \\
4173 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4174 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4175 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4176 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4177 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4178 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4179 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4180 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4181 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4182 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4183 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))/6 \\
4184 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
4185 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4186 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! \times 5/6 - 4 \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4187 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4188 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4189 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4190 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4191 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4192 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4193 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4194 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4195 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4196 &:= ((9 \times 8 - 7) \times 65 - 4! - 3 - 2) \times 1 \\
4197 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4198 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4199 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))/6 \\
4200 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))/6 \\
4201 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4202 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4203 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4204 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4205 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4206 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)/4 \\
4207 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4208 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4209 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4210 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4211 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4212 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! - \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4213 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4214 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4215 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4216 &:= (1 \times (2 + 3))^4 - 5 \times 6! \times (7 - 8) - 9 \\
4217 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4218 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4219 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4220 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4221 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4222 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4223 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4224 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4225 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4226 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5 + 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4227 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4228 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4229 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4230 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4231 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4232 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4233 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4234 &:= 12 \times (4 + 5!)/3 + 6 \times 7 \times 89 \\
4235 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4236 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4237 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4238 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4239 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 \times 5! + 6 - 78 - 9 \\
4240 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4241 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4242 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4204 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4205 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4206 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4207 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4208 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4209 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4210 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4211 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4212 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4213 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4214 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4215 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4216 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5))! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4217 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4218 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4219 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4220 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4221 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4222 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4223 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4224 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4225 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4226 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4227 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4228 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4229 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4230 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4231 &:= -9 - (8 + 7!/6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4232 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4233 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4234 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!)/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4235 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4236 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4237 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4238 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4239 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4240 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4241 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4242 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4243 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4244 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4245 &:= (12/3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\
4246 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + (4! + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4247 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4248 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4249 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + (4! + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4250 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4251 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4252 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4253 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4254 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4255 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4256 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4257 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4258 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4259 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4260 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4261 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4262 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4263 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4264 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4265 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4266 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4267 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4268 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4269 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4270 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4271 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4272 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4273 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4274 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4275 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4276 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4277 &:= -1 - ((2 - (3!! - 4 - 5)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4278 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4279 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4) \times (5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9 \\
4280 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4281 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4282 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4243 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4244 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4245 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4246 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4247 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4248 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4249 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4250 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4251 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4252 &:= (98 \times 7 - 6 \times 5! \times (4 - 3!)) \times 2 \times 1 \\
4253 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4254 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4255 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4256 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4257 &:= -9 - (8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4258 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4259 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4260 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4261 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4262 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4263 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4264 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4265 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4266 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4267 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4268 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4269 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4270 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4271 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6! - 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4272 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4273 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4274 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4275 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4276 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - \sqrt{5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!} \\
4277 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4278 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4279 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4280 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4281 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4282 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4283 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4284 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4285 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4286 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! \times 4! / (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4287 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4288 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4289 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4290 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! / 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4291 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4292 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4293 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4294 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4295 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4296 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4297 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4298 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4299 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4300 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4301 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4302 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / 5! \\
4303 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4304 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4305 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4306 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4307 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4308 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4309 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! / 4) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4310 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - (4! \times 5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4311 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4312 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4313 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4314 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4315 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4316 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4317 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4318 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4319 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4320 &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4321 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4322 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4283 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4284 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
4285 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! / 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4286 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4287 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4288 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4289 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4290 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4291 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4292 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4293 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4294 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4295 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4296 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4297 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4298 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4299 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4300 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4301 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4302 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4303 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
4304 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4305 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4306 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4307 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4308 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4309 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4310 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4311 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4312 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4313 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4314 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4315 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4316 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4317 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4318 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4319 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
4320 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4321 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
4322 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4323 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4324 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4325 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4326 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4327 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4328 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4329 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4330 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4331 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4332 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6)! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4333 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4334 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9 \\
4335 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4336 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4337 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4338 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5 - 6)! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4339 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4340 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4341 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4342 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4343 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4344 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4345 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4346 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4347 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4348 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4349 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4350 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4351 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4352 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4353 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4354 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4355 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6)! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4356 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4357 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4358 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4^{5+6-7} \times (8 + 9) \\
4359 &:= (1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4360 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4361 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4362 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4323 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4324 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4325 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4326 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
4327 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4328 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4329 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4330 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4331 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4332 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4333 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4334 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4335 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4336 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4337 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4338 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4339 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4340 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4341 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4342 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4343 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4344 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4345 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4346 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4347 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4348 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4349 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4350 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4351 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4352 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4353 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4354 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4355 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4356 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4357 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4358 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4359 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4360 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4361 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4362 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4363 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4364 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4365 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4366 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4367 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4368 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3! - 4 - 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4369 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4370 &:= 12 \times 3 - (4! \times 5 \times 6 - 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \\
4371 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4372 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4373 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4374 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6!)/4 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4375 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4376 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4377 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4378 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4379 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4380 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4381 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4382 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4383 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4384 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4385 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4386 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4387 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)^4 + 5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
4388 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4389 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4390 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4391 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4392 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5 - 67 - 8 + 9) \\
4393 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4394 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! - 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4395 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4396 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4397 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4398 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4399 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4400 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5) - 6! + 7! - 8 \times 9 \\
4401 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4363 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4364 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4365 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4366 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4367 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4368 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4369 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4370 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4371 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4372 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 \times \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4373 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4374 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4375 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4376 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4) + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
4377 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4378 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4379 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4380 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4381 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4382 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4383 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4384 &:= (987 + 6 - 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2) - 1 \\
4385 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4386 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4387 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4388 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4389 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
4390 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4391 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4392 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4393 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
4394 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 654 + 3! + 2 - 1 \\
4395 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4396 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4397 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4398 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4399 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4400 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4401 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4402 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (\sqrt{4} \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4402 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4403 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4403 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4404 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4404 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4405 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4405 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4406 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4406 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
4407 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4407 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4408 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4408 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4409 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4409 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
4410 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4410 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4411 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4411 &:= -9 - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4412 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4412 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4413 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4413 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4414 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4414 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4415 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 + 4 - (5! \times 6 - 7! - 89) & 4415 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4416 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4416 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4417 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4417 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4418 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + \sqrt{4} + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4418 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}}) \\
4419 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4419 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4420 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4420 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
4421 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4421 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4422 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4422 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4423 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4423 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4424 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4424 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4425 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4425 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4426 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4426 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4427 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4427 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4428 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4428 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4429 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 4429 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4430 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 4430 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4431 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4431 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4432 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4432 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4433 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4433 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4434 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4434 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4435 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4435 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4436 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4436 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4437 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4437 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4438 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4438 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4439 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4439 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4440 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4440 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4441 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4442 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4443 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4444 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4445 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4446 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4447 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4448 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4449 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4450 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4451 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4452 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4453 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4454 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4455 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4456 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4457 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4458 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4459 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4460 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4461 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4462 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4463 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4464 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4465 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4466 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 - (6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4467 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4468 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4469 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4470 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4471 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4472 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4473 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4474 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4475 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4476 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4477 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4478 &:= (-1 - 2^3) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4479 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4480 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4441 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4442 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4443 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4444 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4445 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4446 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4447 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4448 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4449 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4450 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4451 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4452 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4453 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4454 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4455 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4456 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4457 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4458 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4459 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4460 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4461 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4462 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4463 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4464 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!)/((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4465 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4466 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3!!)) - 2 - 1 \\
4467 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4468 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4469 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4470 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4471 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7!/(6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4472 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4^{3+2+1} \\
4473 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - ((6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4474 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
4475 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4476 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4477 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4478 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4479 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4480 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4481 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4482 &:= (-1 - 2^{3+4} - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4483 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4484 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4485 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4486 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4487 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4488 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4489 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4490 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
4491 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4492 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
4493 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4494 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)/4 \\
4495 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4496 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4497 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))/4 \\
4498 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))/4 \\
4499 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4 \\
4500 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4501 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))/4 \\
4502 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4503 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4504 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4^5} + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4505 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4506 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4507 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4508 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4509 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4510 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4511 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4512 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4513 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
4514 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4515 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4516 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4517 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4518 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4519 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4520 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4481 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4482 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4483 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4484 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4485 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4486 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4487 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4488 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4489 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4490 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4491 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4492 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4493 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4494 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4495 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4496 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + (5!/4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
4497 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5!/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4498 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4499 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4500 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4501 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times 3! \times (2 - 1)/4 \\
4502 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
4503 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6! - 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4504 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
4505 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4506 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4507 &:= 9 - (8 - 7! - 6) - 543 + 2 + 1 \\
4508 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4509 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5! - 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4510 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4511 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/5! \\
4512 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4513 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!/4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4514 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4515 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4516 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
4517 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4518 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!)/((6 - 5) \times 4)! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4519 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!)/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4520 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4521 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! + 4 - 5)! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4521 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4522 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 4522 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4523 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 4523 &:= 9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! + 3!)/2 - 1 \\
4524 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4524 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4525 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4525 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4526 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 4526 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4527 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) & 4527 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!/5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4528 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) & 4528 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4529 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4529 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!/4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4530 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4530 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4531 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 & 4531 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4532 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4532 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4533 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 4533 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4534 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 4534 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4535 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4535 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4536 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4536 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! + 4! \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
4537 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 - 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 4537 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! - 4! + (3! - 2 + 1)! \\
4538 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4538 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
4539 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4539 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3))/(2 + 1) \\
4540 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 4540 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4541 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4541 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4542 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4542 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5 - 4)! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4543 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4! \times (5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 4543 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4544 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) & 4544 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 - 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4545 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 4545 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4546 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 4546 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4547 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5!) \times 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 & 4547 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4548 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) & 4548 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4549 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4549 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4550 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4550 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)) \times 4/5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4551 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4551 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4552 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4552 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
4553 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 4553 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4554 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4554 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4555 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4555 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4556 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 & 4556 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4557 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 & 4557 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4558 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 & 4558 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4559 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4559 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4560 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4560 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!/6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4561 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
4562 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4563 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4564 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
4565 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4566 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4567 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4568 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4569 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4570 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!) + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
4571 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4572 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4573 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4574 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4575 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4576 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4577 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4578 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4579 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4580 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4581 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4582 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4583 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4584 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4585 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4586 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4587 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4588 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4589 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4590 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4591 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4592 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4593 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4594 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4595 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4596 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4597 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4598 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4599 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4600 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4561 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4562 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)) \times 4/5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4563 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4564 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4565 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4566 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6 + (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4567 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4568 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4569 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4570 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4571 &:= 9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4572 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4573 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4574 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
4575 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4576 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4577 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4578 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!/\sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4579 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4580 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
4581 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4582 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4583 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4584 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4585 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4586 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6!/5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4587 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4588 &:= -9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) - 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4589 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4590 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 87) \times (65 - 4 - 3^2 - 1) \\
4591 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4592 &:= -9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4593 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4594 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4595 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4596 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4597 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 4/5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4598 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4599 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4600 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4601 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4602 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4603 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4604 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4605 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4606 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4607 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4608 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4609 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4610 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! \times (5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4611 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4612 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4613 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
4614 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4615 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4616 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4617 &:= -1 \times ((2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4618 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4619 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4620 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4621 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times 4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
4622 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4623 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4624 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4625 &:= (1^2 + 3)! - 456 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4626 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times (4! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4627 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4628 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4629 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4630 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4631 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4632 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4633 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4634 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5! + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4635 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4636 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4637 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4638 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4639 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4601 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 4/5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4602 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4603 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4604 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4605 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
4606 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!) \\
4607 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4608 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4609 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - 432 + 1 \\
4610 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4611 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4612 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4613 &:= (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5/\sqrt{4} + 3!)^2 \times 1 \\
4614 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4615 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4616 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
4617 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4618 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4619 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4620 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4621 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
4622 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - 4)^3 - 2 - 1 \\
4623 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4624 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4625 &:= -9 + (8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4626 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6!/(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4627 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4628 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6!/5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4629 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 - 5) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
4630 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4631 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7! \times 5 \times 4/6! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4632 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!/\sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4633 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4634 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4) \times 3^{2+1} \\
4635 &:= 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - (5 \times 4)^{3-2+1} \\
4636 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4637 &:= -9 + (8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4638 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4639 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4640 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4641 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4642 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4643 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4644 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! - \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4645 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4646 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4647 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4648 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4649 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4650 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4651 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4652 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4653 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4654 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4655 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4656 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 - 5!/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4657 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4658 &:= (1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4659 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4660 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4661 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4662 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!^4) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)/5 \\
4663 &:= -1 \times (((2 + 3)! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4664 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4665 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4666 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4667 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4668 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4669 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4670 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4671 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4672 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4673 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4674 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4675 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4676 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4677 &:= -1 - 2 + (3^4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4678 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3^4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4640 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4641 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4642 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4643 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4644 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4645 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4646 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4647 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4648 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4649 &:= 98 + 7! - 6 - (5! \times 4 + 3) \times (2 - 1) \\
4650 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4651 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4652 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4653 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4654 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
4655 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4656 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4657 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4658 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6!/5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4659 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4660 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4661 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4662 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4663 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4664 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6!/5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
4665 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
4666 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4667 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4668 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4669 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6^5/4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4670 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
4671 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4672 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4673 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4674 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4675 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4676 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4677 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4678 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4679 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4679 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4680 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4680 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1) \\
4681 &:= -1 + 2 + (3^4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4681 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4682 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4682 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! / (5 - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
4683 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) & 4683 &:= 9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! / \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4684 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 4684 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4685 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! / 4 - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 4685 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4686 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4686 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4687 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4687 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4688 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4688 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4689 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 4689 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4690 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4690 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4691 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 4691 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
4692 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) / \sqrt{4} & 4692 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4693 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!! / 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4693 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4694 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 4694 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4695 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4695 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4696 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4696 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 5 / 6 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4697 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} \times 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4697 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4698 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4698 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4699 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4699 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4700 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4700 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5 \times 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4701 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6 & 4701 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4702 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6 & 4702 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4703 &:= -1 - (2 + (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4703 &:= (98 + 76 + 5!) \times 4! \times 2 / 3 - 1 \\
4704 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 4704 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4705 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) / 6 & 4705 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6^5 / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4706 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4706 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4707 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4707 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5! + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4708 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4708 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) - 2 - 1) \\
4709 &:= ((1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 4709 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4710 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 4710 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4711 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!^4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) & 4711 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4712 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 4712 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! / 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4713 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) & 4713 &:= -9 \times (7 \times 6 + 8) + 5! + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4714 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 4714 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
4715 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4715 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4716 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 4716 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5^4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4717 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 & 4717 &:= (\sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4! - 32) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4718 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!!/4 - 5 - 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4719 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4720 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4721 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
4722 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4723 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4724 &:= -1 - 2 - ((3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4725 &:= -1 - (2 - (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4726 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4727 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4^5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4728 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4729 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4730 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4731 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4732 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4733 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4734 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4735 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4736 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
4737 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4738 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4739 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4740 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4741 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4742 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4743 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4744 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4745 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4746 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4747 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4748 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4749 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4750 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4751 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4752 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4753 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4754 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4755 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
4756 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4757 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4718 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
4719 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4720 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4721 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6^5/4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4722 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4723 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4724 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! + 5 + 4 + 3)/(2 + 1) \\
4725 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4726 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4727 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
4728 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4729 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4730 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4731 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4732 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4733 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4734 &:= -9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4735 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
4736 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
4737 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4738 &:= -9 - 8 \times (6 \times 5 + 7) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
4739 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4740 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4741 &:= -9 - (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4742 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4743 &:= (9 \times (8 \times 76 - 5 + 4) - (3 \times 2)!) \times 1 \\
4744 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4745 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4746 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4747 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4748 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4749 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1) \\
4750 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 76 - 5 + 4 - (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\
4751 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
4752 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4753 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4754 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7!/(6!/5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4755 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4756 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
4757 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4758 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (8 + 9)/(5 + 6 + 7) \\
4759 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4760 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4761 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (8 + 9)/(5 + 6 + 7) \\
4762 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4763 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4764 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4765 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4766 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
4767 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4768 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4769 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4770 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4771 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4772 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4773 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4774 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4775 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4776 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4777 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4778 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4779 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4780 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4781 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4782 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4783 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4784 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
4785 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4786 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4787 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4788 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4789 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4790 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4791 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4792 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4793 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)!/(5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4794 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4795 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4796 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4797 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4 \times 5!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4758 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4759 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4760 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7! / ((6 - 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4761 &:= 9 \times (87 \times 6 + 5) + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4762 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4763 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4764 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4765 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4766 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7! / (6! / 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4767 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4768 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! / 6!) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4769 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4770 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4771 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4772 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
4773 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - (6! - 5! + 4))) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4774 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! / 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
4775 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4776 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4777 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4778 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4779 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4780 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
4781 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4782 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 \times (5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4783 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4784 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4785 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4786 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4787 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4788 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4789 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4790 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! \times 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4791 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4792 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4793 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4794 &:= 98 + 7! - (65 + 4) \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
4795 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4796 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! / 5)) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4797 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4798 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 \times 5!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
4799 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 + 5) \\
4800 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4801 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
4802 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4803 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4804 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4805 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4806 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4807 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4808 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4809 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4810 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4811 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
4812 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4813 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
4814 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
4815 &:= 1 - 2 + 3!! + (4! - \sqrt{5 + 67 - 8})^{\sqrt{9}} \\
4816 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
4817 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
4818 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4819 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4820 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4821 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4822 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4823 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4824 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4825 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4826 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4827 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4828 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4829 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4830 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4831 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4832 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4833 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!!/4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4834 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4835 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4836 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)!/4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4798 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 - (5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
4799 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4800 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4801 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4802 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4803 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4804 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4805 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4806 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4807 &:= -9 + 8^{7+6-5-4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4808 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4809 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - (5 + 4) \times (32 + 1) \\
4810 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4811 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4812 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4813 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4814 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4815 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4816 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4817 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4818 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4819 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4820 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4821 &:= (\sqrt{(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6})! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4822 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4823 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6^{5+4-3-2-1} \\
4824 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4825 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4826 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/5 - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4827 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4828 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4829 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4830 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4831 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4832 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4833 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!/5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4834 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4835 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4836 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4837 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3 + 4)!) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4838 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4839 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4840 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4841 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4842 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4843 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4844 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4845 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4846 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4847 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times (5 \times 6 + 4)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4848 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4849 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3^4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4850 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4851 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
4852 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4853 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4854 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4855 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4856 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4857 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!!/4 + ((5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9)! \\
4858 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4859 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4860 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4861 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4862 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4863 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4864 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4865 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4866 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4867 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4868 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4869 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4870 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4871 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4872 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4873 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4874 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4! - 5 - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4875 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
4876 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4837 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4838 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4839 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4840 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4841 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4842 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4843 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4844 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4845 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6^5 / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4846 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4847 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 - 5 + 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4848 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4849 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4850 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4851 &:= 98 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 43 - 2 - 1) \\
4852 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4853 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4854 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4855 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4856 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4857 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4858 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4859 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4860 &:= -9 \times ((8 \times 7 - 6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4861 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4862 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4863 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4864 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4865 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4866 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4867 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4868 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4869 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4870 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
4871 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4872 &:= (-9 - 8 / (7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4873 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4874 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4875 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4876 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4877 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4878 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4879 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4880 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times 5! / (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4881 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! / 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4882 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
4883 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4884 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4885 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4886 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4887 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4888 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4889 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4890 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4891 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4892 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4893 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4894 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4895 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4896 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4897 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4898 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4899 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4900 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4901 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4902 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4903 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4904 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4905 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4906 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4907 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4908 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4909 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4910 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
4911 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4912 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4913 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4914 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4915 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4916 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4877 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4878 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4879 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4880 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4881 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 - 2 + 1 \\
4882 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4883 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4884 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4885 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4886 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4887 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4888 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4889 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! / 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4890 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4891 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6) \times 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4892 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4893 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4894 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4895 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4896 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4897 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4898 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4899 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4900 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7! \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! / 6! \\
4901 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4902 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4903 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4904 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 \times 3! - 2 \times 1 \\
4905 &:= 9 - (8 - 7! - 6) - 5! - 43 + 21 \\
4906 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4907 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4908 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 5! \\
4909 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4910 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4911 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
4912 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4913 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4914 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4915 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4916 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4917 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4918 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4919 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4920 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4921 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4922 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4923 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4924 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4925 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4926 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4927 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4928 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4929 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4930 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4931 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4932 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4933 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4934 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4935 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4936 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4937 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4938 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4939 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4940 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4941 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 - (5! - 6 - 7))) \times (8 + 9) \\
4942 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4943 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4944 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4945 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - (4^5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4946 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4947 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4948 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4949 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
4950 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4951 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4952 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
4953 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4954 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4955 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4956 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4917 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4918 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4919 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4920 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4921 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4922 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4923 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4924 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4925 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6 - 5 + 4)! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4926 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))! \\
4927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4928 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4929 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4930 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4931 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4932 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4933 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4934 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4935 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4936 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6!)! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4937 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4938 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4939 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4940 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
4941 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4942 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
4943 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4944 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1))! \\
4945 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4946 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4947 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4948 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4949 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4950 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4951 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4952 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! / 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4953 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4954 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4955 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4956 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4957 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4958 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
4959 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4960 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4961 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
4962 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4963 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
4964 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4965 &:= -1 - 2 + (3^4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4966 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3^4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4967 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4968 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4969 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4970 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4971 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4972 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4973 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!!/(4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4974 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4975 &:= 1^{2345} + 6 + 7! - 8 \times 9 \\
4976 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
4977 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
4978 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4979 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4980 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4981 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4982 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4983 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4984 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4985 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
4986 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4987 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4988 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
4989 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4990 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4991 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4992 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
4993 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4994 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
4995 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
4996 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4957 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4958 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4959 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4960 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
4961 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4962 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
4963 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4964 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4965 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4966 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
4967 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4968 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/(6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4969 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4970 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
4971 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4972 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4973 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4974 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
4975 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4976 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
4977 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4978 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4979 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
4980 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4981 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4982 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4983 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4984 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4985 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4986 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4987 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
4988 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4989 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
4990 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))! \\
4991 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4992 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
4993 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4994 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4995 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4996 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$4997 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4998 := (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4999 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5000 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$4997 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!)$$

$$4998 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4999 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5000 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5001 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5002 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5003 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5004 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5005 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5006 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5007 := -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5008 := -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5009 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5010 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5011 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5012 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5013 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5014 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$5015 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5016 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5017 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$5018 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5019 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5020 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!$$

$$5021 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5022 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5023 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5024 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5025 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5026 := -1 - 2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5027 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5028 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5029 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5030 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5031 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5032 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5033 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5034 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5035 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5001 := -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5002 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5003 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5004 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5005 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5006 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5007 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5008 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5009 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5010 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!)$$

$$5011 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5012 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5013 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5014 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5015 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5016 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5017 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!$$

$$5018 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5019 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5020 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5021 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5022 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5023 := -9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))!$$

$$5024 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5025 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!$$

$$5026 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5027 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5028 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5029 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5030 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5031 := -9 + (8 - (7 - 6)^{54321})!$$

$$5032 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5033 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!$$

$$5034 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5035 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5036 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5037 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5038 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5039 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5040 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5041 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5042 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5043 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5044 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5045 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5046 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / 5! \\
5047 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5048 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5049 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5050 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5051 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5052 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5053 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5054 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5055 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5056 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5057 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5058 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5059 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5060 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5061 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5062 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5063 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5064 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5065 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5066 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5067 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5068 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5069 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5070 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5071 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5072 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5073 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5074 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5! - 6!) / (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5075 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5036 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5037 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5038 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5039 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))! \\
5040 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (-7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
5041 &:= -9 + (8 - (7 - 6)^5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5042 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5043 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! / 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5044 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5045 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))! \\
5046 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5047 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5048 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5049 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5050 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5051 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5052 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5053 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5054 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5055 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! / 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5056 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5057 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5058 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5059 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5060 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5061 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1))! \\
5062 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5063 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5064 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5065 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
5066 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5067 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5068 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5069 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5070 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5071 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5072 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5073 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5074 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5075 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5076 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5077 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5078 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!!) \times (4 - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5079 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5080 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5081 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5082 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5083 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5084 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5085 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5086 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5087 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5088 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5089 &:= 12 - ((3 + 4)! + (6 \times 7 - 5)) \times (8 - 9) \\
5090 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5091 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5092 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5093 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5094 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5095 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5096 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5097 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5098 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5099 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5100 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5101 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
5102 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + \sqrt{4^5} + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5103 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5104 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5105 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!!/45 + 6) + 7! + 8 - 9 \\
5106 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5107 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
5108 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5109 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5110 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5111 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5112 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5113 &:= (1 + 2)! + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 + 9 \\
5114 &:= (1 - 2)^{3^4} + 56 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5115 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5076 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5077 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5078 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5079 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5080 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5081 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5082 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5083 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5084 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5085 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5086 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
5087 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5088 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5089 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5090 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5091 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5092 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5093 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5094 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5095 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5096 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5097 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5098 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5099 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
5100 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5101 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5102 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5103 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5104 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5105 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5106 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5107 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5108 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5109 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5110 &:= 9 + 8 + 7! + 65 - 4 - 3! - 2 \times 1 \\
5111 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5112 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5113 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5114 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5115 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5116 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) & 5116 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5117 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5117 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5118 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5118 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5119 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5119 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5120 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5120 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5121 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) + 4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 5121 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5122 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5122 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5123 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5123 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5124 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5124 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5125 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3 + 4! + 56 + 7! + 8 - 9 & 5125 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5126 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5126 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5127 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5127 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5128 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5128 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5129 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5129 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5130 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5130 &:= 98 + 7! + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3! + 2 - 1 \\
5131 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5131 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5132 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5132 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5133 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5133 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5134 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5134 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5135 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5135 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + (5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5136 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 5136 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5137 &:= (12 - 3 + 4 - 5) \times 6! - 7 \times 89 & 5137 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5138 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5138 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5139 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5139 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5140 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5140 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5141 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! - 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5141 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5142 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5142 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5143 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5143 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5144 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5144 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5145 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5145 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5146 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5146 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
5147 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5147 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5148 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5148 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5149 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5149 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5150 &:= 12 \times 3 - 4 - 5 - (6 - 7! - 89) & 5150 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5151 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5151 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5152 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 5152 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
5153 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 & 5153 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5154 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5154 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5155 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 5155 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5156 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 5157 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5158 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5159 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5160 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5161 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5162 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 5163 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5164 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5165 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 5166 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5167 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5168 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
 5169 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
 5170 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5171 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5172 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5173 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
 5174 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5175 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5176 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5177 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5178 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5179 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5180 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5181 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5182 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5183 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5184 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5185 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5186 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5187 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5188 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5189 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5190 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5191 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5192 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!^4) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 5193 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 5194 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5156 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5157 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5158 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
 5159 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5160 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5161 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5162 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5163 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5164 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 5165 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5 + 4)! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5166 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 5167 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5168 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5169 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5170 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 32 + 1) \\
 5171 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 5172 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5173 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5174 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 5175 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 5176 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 5177 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5178 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5179 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
 5180 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5181 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 5182 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5183 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 5184 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6^{5+4-3-2-1} \\
 5185 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5186 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 5187 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 5188 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5189 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 - 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 5190 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5191 &:= 98 + 7! - (6 - 54 - 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 5192 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 5193 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 5194 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5195 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5196 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!^4) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5197 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5198 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5199 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4^5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5200 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! \times 5!/(6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5201 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5202 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5203 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5204 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5205 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5206 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5207 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3 - 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5208 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5209 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5210 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + (\sqrt{4} + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5211 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!^4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5212 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5213 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5214 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5215 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5216 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5217 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5218 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5219 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5220 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5221 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5222 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5223 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!!/4 - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5224 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5225 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)!!/4 - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5226 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5227 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!!/4 - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5228 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5229 &:= -1 - (2^{3^{\sqrt{4}}} + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
5230 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5231 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5232 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5233 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5234 &:= 1 - (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5195 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5196 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5197 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5198 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5199 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5200 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5201 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5202 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5203 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times (3 + 2 + 1)!/(5! \times 4!) \\
5204 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! - 5 - 4 - 3)/(2 + 1) \\
5205 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5206 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5207 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5208 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5209 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5210 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5211 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5212 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! + 5 + 4 + 3)/(2 + 1) \\
5213 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5214 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5215 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5216 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1 \\
5217 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 8) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5218 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5219 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (3 + 2 + 1)!/(5! \times 4!) \\
5220 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5221 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5222 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
5223 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5224 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4 + 3!^{2+1} \\
5225 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times (5! + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5226 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5227 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5228 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
5229 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5230 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
5231 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5232 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5233 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5234 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5235 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 5235 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5236 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5236 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + (4 \times 32 - 5) + 1 \\
5237 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) & 5237 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5238 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5238 &:= 98 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2) + 1 \\
5239 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5239 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^{5+4-3-2-1} \\
5240 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5240 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
5241 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5241 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5242 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 5242 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5243 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5243 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5244 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5244 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5245 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5245 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
5246 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5246 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
5247 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5247 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5248 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5248 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5249 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5249 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5250 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5250 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5251 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5251 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5252 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5252 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5253 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5253 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5254 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5254 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
5255 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5255 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5256 &:= 1^{234} + 5! + 6 + 7! + 89 & 5256 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
5257 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5257 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5258 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5258 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
5259 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 5259 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5260 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5260 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5261 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5261 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5262 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5262 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5263 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3! - 4 + 5)! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5263 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5264 &:= (12 + 3!) \times 45/6 + 7! + 89 & 5264 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
5265 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) & 5265 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5266 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 5266 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
5267 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5267 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5268 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5268 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5269 &:= 1^2 + 3 + 4 \times 56 + 7! - 8 + 9 & 5269 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5270 &:= 1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6 + 789) & 5270 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
5271 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5271 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5272 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^{4+5-6} + 7! + 8 + 9 & 5272 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
5273 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5273 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5274 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5275 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5276 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5277 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5278 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5279 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times (4! + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5280 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5281 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5282 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5283 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5284 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5285 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5286 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5287 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5288 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4^5} + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5289 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5290 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5291 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5292 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5293 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5294 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
5295 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5296 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
5297 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5298 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5299 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5300 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5301 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5302 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5303 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5304 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5305 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5306 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5308 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5309 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5310 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5311 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! + 4) - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5312 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5274 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5275 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5276 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5277 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5278 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
5279 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5280 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5281 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5282 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
5283 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5284 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5285 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5286 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5287 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5288 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! + (5 + 4) \times 3)/(2 + 1) \\
5289 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5290 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
5291 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5292 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5293 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5294 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
5295 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5296 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
5297 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5298 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5299 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5300 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
5301 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5302 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5303 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5304 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5305 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5306 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
5307 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5! + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5308 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
5309 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5310 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5311 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)/5 \\
5312 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5313 &:= (1 - 2 - 3)^4 - ((5 - 6) \times 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5314 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5315 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5316 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5317 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5318 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!!/4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5319 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5320 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5321 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 - 4 + 5)! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5322 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5323 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5324 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
5325 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5326 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5327 &:= 12 \times 3!!/45 + 6 + 7! + 89 \\
5328 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5329 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5330 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5331 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5332 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5333 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5334 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5335 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5336 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5337 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 - 4 + 5)! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5338 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5339 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5340 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5341 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5342 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5343 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5344 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5345 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5346 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5347 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5348 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5349 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5350 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5351 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
5352 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5313 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
5314 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
5315 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5316 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
5317 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! - 5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5318 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5319 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
5320 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
5321 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5322 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5323 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5324 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5325 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5326 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!) \\
5327 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5328 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5329 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
5330 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5331 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5332 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
5333 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5334 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5335 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
5336 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
5337 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5338 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1) \\
5339 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5340 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
5341 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5342 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) + 3!!/(2 + 1) \\
5343 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5344 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
5345 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5346 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5347 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5348 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5349 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5! - 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5350 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5351 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
5352 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$5353 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (\sqrt{4} - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5354 := -1 + (2 + 3!!/4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5355 := ((12 - 34) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$5356 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times (\sqrt{4} - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5357 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5358 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! \times 5/4) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5359 := -1 - 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5360 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$5361 := (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^5 - (6! - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$5362 := -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5363 := -1 + (2 - 3!!/4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5364 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5365 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$5366 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5367 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! - (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5368 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5369 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$5370 := (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5371 := (1 + 2)! \times (3! - 4 + 56) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5372 := (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5373 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5374 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5375 := -1 - (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5376 := -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5377 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5378 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5379 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5380 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5381 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5382 := (-1 + 2 - 3!!/4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5383 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5384 := -1 - 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$5385 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5386 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5387 := -1 + (2 + 3!! \times 5/4) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5388 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5389 := ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5390 := -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5391 := -1 \times ((2^{3!} - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$5353 := -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5354 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1)$$

$$5355 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5356 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5357 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5358 := -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5359 := -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5360 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5361 := -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5362 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5363 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5364 := -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5365 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) / 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$5366 := -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5367 := -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5368 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! - 5!) \times 4 / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5369 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5370 := (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5371 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$5372 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5373 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5374 := -9 + (8 - (7 - 6)^5)! + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$5375 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5376 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5377 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$5378 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5379 := -9 - (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5380 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5381 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5382 := -9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5383 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5384 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5385 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5386 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! / (5 - 4 - 3) - 2 - 1)$$

$$5387 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5388 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5389 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5390 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5391 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5392 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times 6 + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$5393 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/(4 + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$5394 := (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5395 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + 5! - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5396 := -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5397 := -1 - 2 - (3!/4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5398 := -1 \times 2 - (3!/4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5399 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5400 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5401 := -1 + 2 - (3!/4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5402 := -1 + 2 + (3! + (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5403 := -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5404 := -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5405 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5406 := (-1 + 2 + 3!/4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5407 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$5408 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$5409 := (-1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5)) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5410 := (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5411 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5412 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5413 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5414 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5415 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$5416 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$5417 := -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5418 := (-1 - (2 \times 3)!/4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5419 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5420 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5421 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5422 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5423 := -1 - ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5424 := -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5425 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 5 \times 6/4 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5426 := -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5427 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5428 := -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5429 := -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5430 := (-1 + 2 + 3!/4) \times 5! \times 6/(7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5431 := -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5392 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$5393 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$5394 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5395 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5396 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5397 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5398 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5399 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5400 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5401 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5402 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5403 := ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5404 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5405 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5!/4)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5406 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5407 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5408 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5409 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5410 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5411 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$5412 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$5413 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$5414 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5415 := -9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!)$$

$$5416 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$5417 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5418 := -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5419 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6^5/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5420 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5421 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5422 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$5423 := -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5424 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5425 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! \times 5/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5426 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5427 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5428 := (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$5429 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$5430 := 9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4^3 + 2) - 1$$

$$5431 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5432 := -1 - 2 + (3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5433 := (-1 - 2) \times ((3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$5434 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$5435 := -1 - (2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5436 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!!/4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5437 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5438 := -1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$5439 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times (8 + 9)/(5 + 6 + 7)$$

$$5440 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5441 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5442 := (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5443 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5444 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$5445 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5446 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5447 := -1 - (((2 + 3)! - 4^5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5448 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5449 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5450 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$5451 := -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5452 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5453 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5! - 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$5454 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5455 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5456 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5457 := -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5458 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5459 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5460 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5461 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5462 := -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5463 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times 5!/6 + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$5464 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5465 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5466 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5467 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5468 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5469 := -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5470 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$5432 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$5433 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5! + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5434 := (-9 - 8) \times (-6 \times 5 + 7) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$5435 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6^5/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$5436 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5437 := (-9 - 8) \times (-6 \times 5 + 7) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!$$

$$5438 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5439 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5440 := (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 - 5 - 4) + 3!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$5441 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! \times 5/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5442 := 9 + (7 \times 6 - 8) + 5! \times (43 + 2) - 1$$

$$5443 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5444 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4) \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$5445 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5446 := (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times (5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5447 := -9 + (8 + 7! - 6^5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5448 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5449 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5450 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6!/5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5451 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5452 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5453 := (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5454 := -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5455 := -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5456 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$5457 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6! - 5 - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$5458 := (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$5459 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5460 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5461 := -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!/4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5462 := -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$5463 := -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$5464 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$5465 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$5466 := (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5467 := (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!$$

$$5468 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$5469 := -9 - (8 \times (7 - (6! - 5 - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$5470 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5^4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5471 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5472 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5473 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5474 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5475 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5476 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5477 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5478 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5479 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5480 &:= -1 - (2 - (3 + 4!))/(5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5481 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5482 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5483 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5484 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5485 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5486 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5487 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5488 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5489 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5490 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5491 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5492 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5493 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5494 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5495 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5496 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5497 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/(4 + 5)) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5498 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5499 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
5500 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5501 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5502 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5503 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5504 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5505 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5506 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5507 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5508 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5509 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5510 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5471 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6^5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5472 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5473 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5474 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6^5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5475 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5! + 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5476 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5477 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
5478 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5479 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5480 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5481 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5482 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5483 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6!/(5 + 4) - 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
5484 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/6! - 5^4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5485 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - ((6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5486 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
5487 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5488 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5489 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5490 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5491 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5492 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6!/5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
5493 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
5494 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)) \\
5495 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5496 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5497 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5498 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
5499 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5500 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
5501 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5502 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5503 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5504 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5505 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5506 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6^5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5507 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5508 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5509 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5510 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5511 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5512 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5513 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5514 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5515 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5516 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5517 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5518 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5519 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5520 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5521 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5522 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5523 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5!) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5524 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
5525 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5526 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4^5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5527 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! - 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5528 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5529 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5530 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5531 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5532 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5533 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5534 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5535 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
5536 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5537 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5538 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5539 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
5540 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5541 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5542 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5543 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5544 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5545 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5546 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5547 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5548 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5549 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5550 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5511 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5512 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5513 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5514 &:= (-9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5515 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5516 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5517 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5518 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5519 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5520 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5521 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5522 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 - 4)/3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
5523 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4! - 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
5524 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - (5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
5525 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5526 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5527 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5528 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5529 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5530 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1 \\
5531 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5532 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4) - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
5533 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5534 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
5535 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5536 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5537 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5538 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - (5 - \sqrt{4})!!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5539 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5540 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5541 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5542 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
5543 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5544 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - (6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5545 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5546 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6!) \times (5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5547 &:= 9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5548 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5549 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5550 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - (5 - \sqrt{4})!!) + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5551 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5552 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5553 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!)/6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5554 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5555 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5556 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5557 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5558 &:= -1 + (2 + (3! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5559 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5560 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5561 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5562 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5563 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
5564 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5565 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
5566 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
5567 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5568 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5569 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5570 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5571 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5572 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5573 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5574 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5575 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5576 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5577 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5578 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6)) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5579 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5580 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5581 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
5582 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5583 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5584 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5585 &:= -1 \times (((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
5586 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5!)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5587 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5588 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5589 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5590 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5551 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5552 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5553 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5554 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5555 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5556 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5557 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5558 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5559 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5560 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5561 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!/4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5562 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2)! \times 1 \\
5563 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5564 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5565 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5566 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5567 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5568 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5569 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5570 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5571 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5572 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5573 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5574 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5575 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5576 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5577 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5578 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5579 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5580 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5581 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5582 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
5583 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5584 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5585 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5586 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5587 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
5588 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
5589 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5590 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5591 &:= -1 + (2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5592 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5593 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5594 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5595 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5596 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5597 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5598 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) + 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5599 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5600 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5601 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5602 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5603 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5604 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5605 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5606 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5607 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5608 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5609 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5610 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5611 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! / (4 + 5) - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5612 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5613 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5614 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5615 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5616 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5617 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5618 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5619 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5620 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5621 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5622 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5623 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5624 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5625 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5626 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5627 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5628 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5629 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5630 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5591 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5592 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5593 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5594 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5595 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5596 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5597 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 - (5! - (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
5598 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 876 + 54) \times 3! \times (2 - 1) \\
5599 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5600 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! / 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5601 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5602 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - (6! - 5 - 4 - 3))) - 2 - 1) \\
5603 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5604 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5605 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5606 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5607 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7! - (6 - 5 - 4)^3 \times 21 \\
5608 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5609 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5610 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5611 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5612 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5613 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5614 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5615 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5616 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5617 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5618 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5619 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5620 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! / 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5621 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5622 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5623 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! / 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5624 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5625 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5626 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5627 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5628 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5629 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5630 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6!) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5631 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5632 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5633 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5634 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times 4! - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5635 &:= (1 - 2 - 3!) \times (4 - (5 - 6 + 7)! - 89) \\
5636 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5637 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5638 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5639 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5640 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5641 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5642 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5643 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5644 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5645 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5646 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5647 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5648 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5649 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5650 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 + 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5651 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5652 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5653 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5654 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5655 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!^4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5656 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
5657 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5658 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5659 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5660 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5661 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5662 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5663 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5664 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5665 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5666 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5667 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5668 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5669 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5670 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5631 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5632 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
5633 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5634 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5635 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5636 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5637 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5638 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5639 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! / 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5640 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5641 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5642 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6!) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5643 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5644 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5645 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5646 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5647 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
5648 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5649 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5650 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6!) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5651 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
5652 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5653 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5654 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5655 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5656 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5657 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5658 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5659 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5660 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5661 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5662 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5663 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! / (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5664 &:= (9 + 87) \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 - 2 + 1)) \\
5665 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5666 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5667 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
5668 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5669 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5670 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5671 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5672 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5673 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5674 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5675 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5676 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4 \times 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5677 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5678 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5679 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5680 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5681 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
5682 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5683 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5684 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5685 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5! - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5686 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5! - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5687 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5688 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5689 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5690 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5691 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5692 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5693 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5694 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5695 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! - 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5696 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5697 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5698 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5699 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5700 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5701 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5702 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5703 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5704 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5705 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5706 &:= ((-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5707 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5708 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5709 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5710 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5671 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5672 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5673 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5674 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5675 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5676 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5677 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5678 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5679 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5680 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5681 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5682 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
5683 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5684 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5685 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5686 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5687 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5688 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
5689 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
5690 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5691 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5692 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5693 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5694 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
5695 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!!) \\
5696 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5697 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5698 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5699 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5700 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5701 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
5702 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!)) - 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5703 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5704 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5705 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 \times 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5706 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5707 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5708 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5709 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5710 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5711 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5711 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5712 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))!) & 5712 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
5713 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5713 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5)! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5714 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 & 5714 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5715 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5715 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5716 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5716 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5717 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5717 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5718 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5718 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5719 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5719 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5720 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5720 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5721 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5721 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5722 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 & 5722 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5723 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5723 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5724 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5724 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5725 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5725 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5726 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5726 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5727 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5727 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5728 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5728 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5729 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5729 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5730 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5730 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5731 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5731 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5732 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 5732 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5733 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5733 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5734 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5734 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5735 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! & 5735 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5736 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5736 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5737 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5737 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
5738 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5738 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5739 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5739 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5740 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5740 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5741 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5741 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5742 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5742 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5743 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5743 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
5744 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5744 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5745 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5745 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5746 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5746 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5747 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5747 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5748 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5748 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5749 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5749 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5750 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5750 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5751 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5752 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5753 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5754 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5755 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5756 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4! \times 5/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5757 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5758 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5759 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
5760 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5761 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5762 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5763 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5764 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 \times 5! - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5765 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5766 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5767 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5768 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5769 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5770 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5771 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5772 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5773 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5774 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5775 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5776 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5777 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5778 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5779 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5780 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5781 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5782 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5783 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
5784 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5785 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5786 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5787 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5788 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5789 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5790 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5751 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5752 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5753 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5754 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5755 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5756 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5757 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5758 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5759 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))!! \\
5760 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5761 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5762 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5763 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5764 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5765 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
5766 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5767 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5768 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5769 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5770 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5771 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5772 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5773 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5774 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5775 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5776 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
5777 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5778 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 654 + 3! \times 2 \times 1 \\
5779 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5780 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5781 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5782 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5783 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5784 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5785 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5786 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5787 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5788 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5789 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5790 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5791 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5792 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5793 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5794 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5795 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5796 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5797 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
5798 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5799 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5800 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5801 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5802 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5803 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5804 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5805 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5806 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5807 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5808 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5809 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5810 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5811 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5812 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5813 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5814 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5815 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5816 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5817 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!))) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5818 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5819 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5820 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5821 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5822 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5823 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3! - 4) \times (5 + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5824 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5825 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5826 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5827 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5828 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5829 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5830 &:= (12/3)! + 45 + 6! + 7! - 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5791 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5792 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5793 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5794 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5795 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5796 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5 + 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5797 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5798 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5799 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5800 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5801 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
5802 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5803 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5804 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5805 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5806 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5807 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))! \\
5808 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4)!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5809 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5810 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5811 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5812 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5813 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5814 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5815 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5816 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5817 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5818 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5819 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5820 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5821 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5822 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5823 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5824 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! + \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5825 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!)) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5826 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5827 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5828 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5829 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5830 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5831 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5831 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5)! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5832 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - (\sqrt{4} - 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 5832 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5833 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5833 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5834 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 - 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 & 5834 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5835 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5835 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
5836 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5836 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5837 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 5837 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5838 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 5838 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5839 &:= (1 + 2)!! \times 4!/3 - (5 - 67 - 8 - 9) & 5839 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5840 &:= 12 \times 4 \times 5/3 + 6! \times (7 - 8 + 9) & 5840 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5841 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5841 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5842 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 5842 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5843 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5843 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5844 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + (4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 5844 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5845 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6! - 7) + 8 + 9 & 5845 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5846 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5846 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5847 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5847 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5848 &:= \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times (4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5848 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
5849 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5849 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5850 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5850 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5851 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9) & 5851 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
5852 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5852 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5853 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5853 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5854 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5854 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5855 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5855 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
5856 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 5856 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5857 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5857 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5858 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5858 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5859 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4}) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5859 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5860 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5860 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5861 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 5861 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5862 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 5862 &:= (-9 - (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5863 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5863 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5864 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 & 5864 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5865 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 5865 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5866 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 5866 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5867 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5867 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5868 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 & 5868 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5869 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 5869 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5870 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5871 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5872 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5873 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5874 &:= (-1 - 2^3) \times (4! - 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5875 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5876 &:= (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5877 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5878 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5879 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5880 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5881 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5882 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5883 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5884 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5885 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5886 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5887 &:= -1 + 2^3! \times 4 \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5888 &:= 1 \times 2^3! \times 4 \times (5! - 6! + 7 \times 89) \\
5889 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5890 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 - 5 - 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5891 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5892 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5893 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5894 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5895 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5896 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5897 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5898 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5899 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5900 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5901 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5902 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5903 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5904 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5905 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5906 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5907 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5908 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5909 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5870 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5871 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5872 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5873 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5874 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5875 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5876 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5877 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5878 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5879 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5880 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5881 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5882 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5883 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5884 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
5885 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5886 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5887 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5888 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
5889 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5890 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
5891 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5892 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5893 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5894 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6!/5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
5895 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5896 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
5897 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5898 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5899 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5900 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5901 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5902 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5903 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5904 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5905 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5906 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
5907 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
5908 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5909 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5910 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5911 &:= -1 + (2 - 3! - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5912 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5913 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5914 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5915 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5916 &:= 12 + (3! + 4 + 5 + 67) \times 8 \times 9 \\
5917 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5918 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5919 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5920 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5921 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5922 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5923 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
5924 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5925 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5926 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5927 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5928 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5929 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
5930 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5931 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5932 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5933 &:= 1 - (2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5934 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5935 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
5936 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
5937 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
5938 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! + 5!) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
5939 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5940 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5941 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5942 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
5943 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5944 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5945 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5946 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5947 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5948 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5949 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5910 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5911 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5912 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5913 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5914 &:= 98 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! \times 3 - 21 \\
5915 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5916 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5917 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5918 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5919 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5920 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5921 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5922 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
5923 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5924 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5925 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5926 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5928 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5929 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5930 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5931 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5932 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5933 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5934 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5935 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5936 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3!! / (2 + 1)! \\
5937 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5938 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
5939 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5940 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5941 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5942 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1) \\
5943 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5944 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5945 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 / 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5946 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5947 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5948 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! / 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5949 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5950 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5951 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5952 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times (4 + 5)) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5953 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
5954 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5955 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
5956 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times (5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5957 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5958 &:= (-1 - (2^{3!} + \sqrt{4}) \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5959 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5960 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5961 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5962 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5963 &:= (1 \times 23 + 4!) \times 5! / 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
5964 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5965 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5966 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
5967 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5968 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5969 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5970 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5971 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5972 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5973 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5974 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5975 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5976 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! - (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5977 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5978 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (4 - 5! - 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
5979 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5980 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5981 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5982 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5983 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5984 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5985 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5986 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5987 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5988 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5989 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5950 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5951 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5952 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5953 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! / 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5954 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
5955 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5956 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5957 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5958 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5959 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5960 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5961 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5962 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5963 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5964 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5965 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5966 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5967 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5968 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
5969 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! / 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5970 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
5971 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5972 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5973 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5974 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5975 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5976 &:= \sqrt{9^8} + (7 + 65) \times \sqrt{4} - 3^{(2+1)!} \\
5977 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
5978 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5979 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
5980 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5981 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5982 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
5983 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5984 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
5985 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
5986 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5987 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5988 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5989 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5990 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
5991 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5992 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5993 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5994 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5995 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
5996 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
5997 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5998 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5999 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6000 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6001 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6002 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6003 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6004 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6005 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6006 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6007 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6008 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6009 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6010 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6011 &:= -1 - (2 - (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6012 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6013 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + (5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6014 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6015 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6016 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6017 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6018 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6019 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5!) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6020 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6021 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6022 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6023 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6024 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6025 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6026 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6027 &:= -1 - 2 + (3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6028 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6029 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5990 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5991 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
5992 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5993 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5994 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
5995 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5996 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5997 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
5998 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5999 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6000 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6 \\
6001 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6002 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6003 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6004 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6005 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6006 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6007 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6008 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6009 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6010 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6011 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6012 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6013 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
6014 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
6015 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6016 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6017 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
6018 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6019 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6020 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6021 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6022 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
6023 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6024 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6025 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6026 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6027 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!/4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6028 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6029 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + (5 + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6030 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6031 &:= -1 + 2 + (3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6032 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 + 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6033 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6034 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6035 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6036 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6037 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6038 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6039 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6040 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6041 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6042 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6043 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6044 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6045 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
6046 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
6047 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6048 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6049 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)/5! \\
6050 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6051 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6052 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6053 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6054 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6055 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + 4^5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6056 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4^5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6057 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6058 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6059 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6060 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6061 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6062 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6063 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + ((5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9)! \\
6064 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6065 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6066 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 + \sqrt{4})!/5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6067 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6068 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6030 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6031 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6032 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6033 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6034 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6035 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6036 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6037 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6038 &:= 9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2-1} \\
6039 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6040 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)^6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6041 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6042 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/(6 - 5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6043 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6044 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6045 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6046 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6047 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6048 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6049 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
6050 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
6051 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6052 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6053 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6054 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
6055 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6!/5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6056 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6057 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7!/6! - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6058 &:= 987 + 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1 \\
6059 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6060 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6061 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)!) \\
6062 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! \times (3! + (2 + 1)!) \\
6063 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6064 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3!) - (2 + 1)! \\
6065 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1) \\
6066 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6067 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6068 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 - 4)^3 \times (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6069 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6070 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6071 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6072 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6073 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 6/5 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6074 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 - 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6075 &:= (1 - 2)^{3!} \times (4^5 \times 6 - 78 + 9) \\
6076 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6077 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5! + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6078 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6079 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6080 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6081 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6082 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6083 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3!!/4 - 5) - 6 + 7! + 8 - 9 \\
6084 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4)\sqrt{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6085 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6086 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! \times 4/(5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6087 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6088 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6089 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6090 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6091 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6092 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
6093 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6094 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6095 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4} + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6096 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6097 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6098 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4^5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6099 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! \times 7/(8 \times 9)) \\
6100 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
6101 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6102 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4^5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6103 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6104 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4^5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6105 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5)/6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6106 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6107 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 + \sqrt{4})^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6069 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6070 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + (5! - 4!)) \times 3 \times 21 \\
6071 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6!/5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6072 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6073 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6074 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!/4) - (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6075 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6076 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
6077 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3!)) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
6078 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - 5 - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6079 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6080 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6081 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6082 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6083 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6084 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6085 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6086 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6087 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6088 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
6089 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6090 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6091 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6092 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6093 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6094 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6095 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6096 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6097 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6098 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6099 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
6100 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6101 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
6102 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6/5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6103 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6104 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6105 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6106 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6107 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6108 &:= (-\sqrt{-1+2+3+4^5}) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6109 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6110 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6111 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6112 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6113 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\
6114 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6115 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6116 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6117 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6118 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times \sqrt{4^{5+6}} - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6119 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6120 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6121 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6122 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6123 &:= 1 - (2 \times 3! - 4^5 \times 6 - 7 + 8) - 9 \\
6124 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3!! / 4 - 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})! \\
6125 &:= 1 - 2 \times 3! + 4^5 \times 6 - 7 + 8 - 9 \\
6126 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6127 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6128 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6129 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6130 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6131 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
6132 &:= (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3 + 4^5}) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6133 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6134 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 - 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6135 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6136 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}) / \sqrt{4} \\
6137 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + (6 - 7)^{89}) \\
6138 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3! + 4^5 - 6) - 7 - 8 + 9 \\
6139 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3 + 4)! / 5 + 67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\
6140 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6141 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6142 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6143 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6144 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6145 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6108 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6109 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6110 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6!) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6111 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6112 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
6113 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
6114 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7! / (-5 \times 4 + 6) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6115 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6116 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6117 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
6118 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
6119 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6120 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6121 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! / 5) - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!) \\
6122 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6123 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6124 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6125 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6126 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6127 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6128 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6129 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6130 &:= 9 + 8 \times 765 + (4! \times (3 - 2 - 1))! \\
6131 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!) \\
6132 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6133 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6134 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4^3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6135 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6136 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
6137 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6! - 5) / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6138 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6139 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
6140 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
6141 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6142 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6143 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6144 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6145 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6146 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6147 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6148 &:= 1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (-6 + 7)^{89} \\
6149 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3 + 4)!/5 + 8 \times (6 + 7) - \sqrt{9} \\
6150 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6151 &:= 1^2 \times (3! + 4) \times 5! + 6! \times 7 - 89 \\
6152 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6153 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6154 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6155 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
6156 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 + 4^5 - 6 + 7! + 89 \\
6157 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6158 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6159 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6160 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6161 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6162 &:= ((1 + 2)! + 3! - 4 + 5) \times 6 \times (8 \times 9 + 7) \\
6163 &:= (1 + 2)! \times (3 + 4)!/5 + 67 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
6164 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6165 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6166 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times \sqrt{4^{5+6}} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6167 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6168 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6169 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6170 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6171 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6172 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6173 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6174 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6175 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6176 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6177 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6178 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6179 &:= ((1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6180 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6181 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6182 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6183 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6146 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3)) + 2 + 1 \\
6147 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6148 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6149 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
6150 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6151 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 76 \times 54 \times 3/2 \times 1 \\
6152 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
6153 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - (6! - 5 + 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6154 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6155 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6156 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6157 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6158 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6159 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6160 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
6161 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6162 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6163 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6164 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
6165 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6166 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6167 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6168 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6169 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6170 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
6171 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6172 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6173 &:= 98 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4^3 - 2 + 1) \\
6174 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6175 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6176 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
6177 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6178 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6179 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6180 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6181 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6182 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!))/5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
6183 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6184 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^{5-6+7} - 8 \times 9 \\
6185 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6186 &:= 1234 - 5 + 6 + 7! - 89 \\
6187 &:= 12^3 \times 4 + 5 - 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6188 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6) \\
6189 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6190 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6191 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6192 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6193 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6194 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6195 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6196 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6197 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4! - (5 - 6! - 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
6198 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - \sqrt{4^{5+6}} - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6199 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6200 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6201 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6202 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6203 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6204 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6205 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6206 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6207 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6208 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6209 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6210 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6211 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6212 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6213 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6214 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6215 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6216 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6217 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6218 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6219 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6220 &:= ((-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6221 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6222 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6184 &:= 9 \times (87 \times 6 + 5) + 4 \times 3!!/2 + 1 \\
6185 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6186 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6187 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6188 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6189 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6190 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5^{4!(3+2+1)}) \\
6191 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6!/5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6192 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6193 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6194 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
6195 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6196 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6197 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6198 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7! + 6)/5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6199 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6200 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3!^{2+1} \\
6201 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6) \times (5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6202 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
6203 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
6204 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5 - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6205 &:= -9 - ((8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6206 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6207 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6208 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 - 3! \times (2 + 1)!) \\
6209 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
6210 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6211 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3^{2+1} \\
6212 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
6213 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
6214 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4 - 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
6215 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6216 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6217 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6218 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
6219 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6220 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
6221 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6222 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6! + 5)/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6223 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6224 &:= (1 + 234) \times 5 + (6 - 7 + 8)! + 9 \\
6225 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + \sqrt{4})^5 - \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}) \\
6226 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6227 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6228 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6229 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6230 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6231 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4^5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6232 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6233 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6234 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6235 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6236 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
6237 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6238 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6239 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6240 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6241 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6242 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6243 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6244 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6245 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6246 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6247 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6248 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6249 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6250 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6251 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6252 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6253 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6254 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!!/\sqrt{4} - (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6255 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6256 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6257 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6258 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6259 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6260 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6261 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6262 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6223 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6224 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
6225 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6226 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
6227 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6228 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6229 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6230 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6231 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6232 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
6233 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6234 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6235 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6236 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6237 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6238 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6239 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6240 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! + 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6241 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6242 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6243 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6244 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!)/(2 + 1)!! \\
6245 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6246 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! - 32 \times 1 - 5 - 4) \\
6247 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
6248 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6249 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6250 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6251 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!) \\
6252 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!/4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6253 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
6254 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6255 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6256 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
6257 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6258 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6259 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6260 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6261 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6262 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$6263 := -1 - (2 - 3) \times (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6264 := (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6265 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6266 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6267 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6268 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6269 := -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6270 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6271 := -1 - 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6272 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6273 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$6274 := -1 - (2 - 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$6275 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6276 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5 \times 6/4! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$6277 := (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5! - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$6278 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$6279 := -1 - ((2 + 3)! - (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$6280 := -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$6281 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$6282 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$6283 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + (6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$6284 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 - (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6285 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6286 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6287 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6288 := (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6289 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6290 := (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$6291 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4! + 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$6292 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$6293 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$6294 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$6295 := -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$6296 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$6297 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$6298 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$6299 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$6300 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$6301 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$6302 := -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$6263 := -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6264 := 9 \times (-(8 - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4)! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$6265 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6266 := -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$6267 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$6268 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6269 := -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$6270 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$6271 := -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$6272 := (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$6273 := -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6)/5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$6274 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$6275 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$6276 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6277 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$6278 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$6279 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6280 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$6281 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$6282 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$6283 := -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6284 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$6285 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$6286 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$6287 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6288 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6289 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$6290 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6291 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!)$$

$$6292 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$6293 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$6294 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!/4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$6295 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6296 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6297 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$6298 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6299 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6300 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6301 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6302 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6303 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6304 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 5/4 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6305 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6306 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6307 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6308 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6309 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6310 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6311 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6312 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6313 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6314 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6315 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6316 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6317 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6318 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6319 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
6320 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6321 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6322 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6323 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 - 4! - 5! + (6! + 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
6324 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6325 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6326 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6327 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6328 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6329 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6330 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6331 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6332 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 - 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6333 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6334 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6335 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6336 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6337 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6338 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6339 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6340 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6341 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6303 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6304 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6305 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6306 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6307 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6308 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
6309 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - (5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6310 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6311 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6312 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6313 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6314 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6315 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6316 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6317 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6318 &:= -9 \times (8 - ((7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6319 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6320 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6321 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6322 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6323 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6^5 + 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6324 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6325 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6326 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6327 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6328 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6329 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6330 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6331 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6332 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6333 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6334 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5!/4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6335 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6336 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6337 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6338 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6339 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6340 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6341 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6342 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6343 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6344 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6345 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6346 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6347 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6348 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6349 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6350 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6351 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6352 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6353 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6354 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
6355 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6356 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3!!)) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6357 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6358 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6359 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6360 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6361 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6362 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6363 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6364 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6365 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6366 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6367 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6368 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6369 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6370 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6371 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6372 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6373 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6374 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6375 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6376 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6377 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6378 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6379 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6380 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6381 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6342 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6343 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6344 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 - 4)^{3^{21}} \\
6345 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))! \\
6346 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + (5 - 4)^{3^{21}} \\
6347 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6348 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6349 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6350 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6351 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6352 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6353 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6354 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6355 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6356 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6357 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6358 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6359 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - (6 + 5) \times 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6360 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6361 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6362 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6363 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5!) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6364 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6365 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6366 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6367 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6368 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6369 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6370 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6371 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6372 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6373 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6374 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6375 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6376 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6377 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6378 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6379 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6380 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6381 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6382 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6383 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6384 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6385 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! + 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6386 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6387 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6388 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
6389 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3!!/4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6390 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6391 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6392 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - ((4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6393 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6394 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
6395 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
6396 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6397 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6398 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6399 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6400 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6401 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6402 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6403 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6404 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6405 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6406 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6407 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6408 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
6409 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6410 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6411 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6412 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6413 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6414 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6415 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6416 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6417 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6418 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6419 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6420 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5! \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6421 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6382 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
6383 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6384 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6385 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6386 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6387 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6388 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6389 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6390 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6391 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6392 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6393 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6394 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6395 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6396 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6397 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
6398 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6399 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6400 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6401 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7!/6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6402 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6403 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6404 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6405 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6406 &:= -9 - 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6407 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6408 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6409 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6410 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6411 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6412 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6413 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6414 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6415 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
6416 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6417 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6418 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6419 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6420 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6421 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6422 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6423 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6424 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6425 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6426 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6427 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6428 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6429 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! \times 4! / (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6430 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6431 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6432 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6433 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6434 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5)) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6435 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6436 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6437 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6438 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6439 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6440 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6441 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6442 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6443 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6444 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6445 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + (5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8) \times 9 \\
6446 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + (5 + 6) \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6447 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6448 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6449 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6450 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6451 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6452 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6453 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6454 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6455 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6456 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6457 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + (4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6458 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6459 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6460 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6461 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6422 &:= -9 + 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6423 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6424 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!)) - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6425 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4 / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6426 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6427 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6428 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6429 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6430 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6431 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6432 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6433 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! / 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6434 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6435 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6436 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6437 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6438 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6439 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5)! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6440 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6441 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6442 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6443 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6444 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6445 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6446 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6447 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! / (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6448 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6449 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! / 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6450 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6451 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6452 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6453 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6454 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6455 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6456 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6457 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6458 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6459 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6460 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6461 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6462 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6462 &:= -9 \times (8/(7 + 6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6463 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6463 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
6464 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6464 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6465 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6465 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6466 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6466 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6467 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6467 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6468 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6468 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6469 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6469 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6470 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 & 6470 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6471 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6471 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))! \\
6472 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6472 &:= -9 + 8 - 7!/6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6473 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 & 6473 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6474 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6474 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6475 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6475 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6476 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6476 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6477 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6477 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6478 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6478 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6479 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6479 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
6480 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6480 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6481 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6481 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6482 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 & 6482 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6483 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6483 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6484 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6484 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6485 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 & 6485 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6486 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6486 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6487 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6487 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6488 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6488 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6489 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6489 &:= -9 \times (8/(7 - 6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6490 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6490 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6491 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6491 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6492 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6492 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6493 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 6493 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6494 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!)) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 6494 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6495 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6495 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6496 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6496 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6497 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6497 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6498 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6498 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6499 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!^4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6499 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6500 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6500 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6501 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6501 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6502 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6503 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6504 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6505 &:= (1 + 2 - 3)! + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6506 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6507 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6508 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6509 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6510 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6511 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6512 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6513 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6514 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6515 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6516 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6517 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6518 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6519 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6520 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6521 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6522 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6523 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6524 &:= (1 + 2)! - 3 - 4 - (5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8) \times 9 \\
6525 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6526 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6527 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6528 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6529 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6530 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
6531 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6532 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6533 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6534 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6535 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6536 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6537 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6538 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6539 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6540 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3^4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6541 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6502 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\
6503 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6504 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6505 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6506 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6507 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6508 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6509 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6510 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6511 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
6512 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6513 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6514 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6515 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
6516 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6517 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 \times \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6518 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6519 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6520 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6521 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6522 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6523 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6524 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6525 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6526 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6527 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
6528 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6529 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6530 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6531 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6532 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6533 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6534 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6535 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6536 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6537 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6538 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
6539 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6540 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6541 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6542 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5!)) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6543 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6544 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4 - 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6545 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6546 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6547 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6548 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6549 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6550 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6551 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6552 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3! - 4 - 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6553 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6554 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6555 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6556 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6557 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6558 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^{4+5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6559 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6560 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6561 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6562 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^{4+5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
6563 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6564 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6565 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6566 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6567 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6568 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6569 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6570 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6571 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6572 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6573 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6574 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6575 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6576 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6577 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6578 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!)) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6579 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5) \times (8 + 9)/(6 + 7) \\
6580 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6542 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6543 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6544 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6545 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6546 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6547 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6548 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6549 &:= (-8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6550 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6551 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6552 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6553 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6554 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5 + 4) \times 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
6555 &:= 9 \times (6! \times (8 - 7) + 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6556 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6557 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6558 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6559 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6560 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
6561 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6562 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6563 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6564 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6565 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6566 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6567 &:= \sqrt{9^8} + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
6568 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6569 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6570 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6571 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6572 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6573 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6574 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6575 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6576 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6577 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
6578 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6579 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6580 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! + 5 \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6581 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6582 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6583 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6584 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6585 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6586 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6587 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6588 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6589 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6590 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6591 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6592 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6593 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6594 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6595 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6596 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6597 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6598 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6599 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6600 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6601 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6602 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6603 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6604 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6605 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6606 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6607 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6608 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
6609 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6610 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6611 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6612 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6613 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6614 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6615 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6616 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6617 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6618 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6619 &:= 12 \times 3 \times 4 - 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8) \times 9 \\
6620 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6581 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6582 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
6583 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6584 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)!! \\
6585 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6586 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! / 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6587 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6588 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6589 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6590 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
6591 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6592 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5! + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
6593 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6594 &:= (-9 - (8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) / 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6595 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6596 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6597 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6598 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
6599 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6600 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6601 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6602 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
6603 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6604 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) - 2 - 1 \\
6605 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6606 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6607 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6608 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5! - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)) \\
6609 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6610 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6611 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5! / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6612 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6613 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6^5 / 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6614 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)) \\
6615 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 - 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6616 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6617 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6618 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6619 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + (5! + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)!) \\
6620 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6621 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6622 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6623 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6624 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6625 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6626 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4^5 + 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6627 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times (4! - 5) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6628 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6629 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6630 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)/4 \\
6631 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6632 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6633 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6634 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6635 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6636 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! \times 4 - (5 + 6!)) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6637 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + (5! + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6638 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6639 &:= \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{4+5}} \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6640 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6641 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6642 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6643 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6644 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (-6 \times 7 + 5)/4 - 8 - 9 \\
6645 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6646 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6647 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6648 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!)/5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6649 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4 - 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6650 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6651 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6652 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6653 &:= 1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6654 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6655 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6656 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 + 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6657 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6658 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6659 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6621 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!/4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6622 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - (4! - 3!!)/(2 + 1) \\
6623 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6624 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6625 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6626 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
6627 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6628 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6629 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6630 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6631 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6632 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!) \\
6633 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6634 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6635 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
6636 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5 + 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6637 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6638 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6639 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6640 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
6641 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6642 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6643 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6644 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6645 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6646 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6647 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6648 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
6649 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6650 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
6651 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6652 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6653 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6654 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6! + 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6655 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5 - 4)!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6656 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
6657 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6658 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6659 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6660 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6661 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 45 \times 6 + 7! + 8 - 9 \\
6662 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 - 4 - 5! + 6789 \\
6663 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6664 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6665 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6666 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6667 &:= (-1 \times (2 + 3) - \sqrt{4} + 5!) \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6668 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6669 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6670 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6671 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6672 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6673 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times 4! - 5 \times 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6674 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6675 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6676 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! \times (-6 \times 7 + 5)/4 + 8 + 9 \\
6677 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6678 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6679 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6680 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6681 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6682 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6683 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6684 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6685 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6686 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6687 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6688 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6689 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6690 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6691 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6692 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6693 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6694 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6695 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6696 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6697 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6698 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6699 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6660 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6661 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6662 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
6663 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
6664 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
6665 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6666 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6667 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6668 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)) \\
6669 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6670 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
6671 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6672 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6673 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6674 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6675 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6676 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6677 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6678 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5) - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6679 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6680 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 \times 5 - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
6681 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6682 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6683 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6684 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 - 9) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6685 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6686 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6687 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6688 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6689 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6690 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5^{\sqrt{4}}) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6691 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6692 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6693 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6694 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6695 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times 5!/6! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6696 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6697 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6698 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6699 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6700 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6701 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6702 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6703 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6704 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (6 \times 7 + 5) - 8 - 9 \\
6705 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6706 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6707 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6708 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6709 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6710 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6711 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6712 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6713 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6714 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6715 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6716 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6717 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6718 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6719 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6720 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6721 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6722 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
6723 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6724 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6725 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 + 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6726 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6727 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6728 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6729 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6730 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6731 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6732 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6733 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6734 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6735 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!) - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6736 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6737 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6!))) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6738 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6739 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6700 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6701 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times 5!/6! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6702 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6703 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6704 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6705 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6706 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6707 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6708 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6709 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6710 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 - 4)^{321} \\
6711 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6712 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + (5 - 4)^{321} \\
6713 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times 5!/6! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6714 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6715 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6716 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6717 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6718 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6719 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6720 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6721 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times 5!/6! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6722 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6723 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6724 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6725 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6726 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6727 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times 5!/6! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6728 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6729 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6730 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6731 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6732 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4)/6 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6733 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6734 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6735 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6736 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6737 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6738 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6739 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6740 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6741 &:= (3 \times 4 - 1 - 2) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6742 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6743 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6744 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6745 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + \sqrt{4}) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6746 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6747 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6748 &:= -1 + ((2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6749 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6750 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6751 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) \\
6752 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) \\
6753 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6754 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - (5! - 6! - 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6755 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6756 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6757 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6758 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6759 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6760 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6761 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6762 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6763 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4! - 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6764 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6765 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5!) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6766 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5!) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6767 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6768 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6769 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 \times (4! - 5!) + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6770 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6771 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6772 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6773 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6774 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6775 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6776 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6777 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6778 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6779 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6740 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6741 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6742 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3!^{2+1} \\
6743 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6744 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6745 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6746 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6747 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!/4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6748 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6749 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6750 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6751 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6752 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
6753 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6754 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6! - 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)) \\
6755 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6756 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6757 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6758 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6759 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
6760 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6761 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6762 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6763 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6764 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6765 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6766 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6767 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5 - 4)!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6768 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
6769 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6770 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6771 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6772 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6773 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6774 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6775 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6776 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
6777 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6778 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6779 &:= -9 \times 8 - ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6780 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6781 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6782 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6783 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6784 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6785 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! / 5 + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6786 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6787 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! / (4 \times 5) + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6788 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6789 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + (4! + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6790 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6791 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! / 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6792 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5!) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6793 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6794 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3^4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6795 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6796 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6797 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6798 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6799 &:= -1 - (2 - (3 + 4)! / 5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6800 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6801 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^5 + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6802 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6803 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times (4! - 5!) - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6804 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! \times 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6805 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6806 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6807 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6808 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6809 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5 \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) / 4 \\
6810 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6811 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6812 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6813 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6814 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
6815 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6816 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6817 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6818 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4! - (5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6780 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6781 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 + 5) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6782 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4 + 3!! / (2 + 1)) \\
6783 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6 \times (5 + 4)) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6784 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 + 5 + 4) + (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
6785 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6786 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!) \\
6787 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6788 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6789 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 + 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6790 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
6791 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times 5! / 6! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6792 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! / 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6793 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6794 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5 + 4! / 3)^{2+1} \\
6795 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6796 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5! - (4 + 3)!) / (2 + 1)! \\
6797 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6798 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6799 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6800 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7! / (6 - 5 - 4) - 3!!) / (2 + 1)! \\
6801 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 + 5! - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6802 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! - 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
6803 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!) \\
6804 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6805 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6806 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 - 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6807 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6 + 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6808 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6809 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 - 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6810 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6811 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6812 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6813 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6!) / (5! - 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)!! \\
6814 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6815 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6816 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6817 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6818 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6819 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6819 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6820 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6820 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6821 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!)/(4 \times 5) + 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9 & 6821 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6822 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 6822 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6823 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 6823 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6824 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 & 6824 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6825 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + (4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) & 6825 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6826 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 + 5!) - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6826 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
6827 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 6827 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6828 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6828 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6!) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6829 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) & 6829 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6830 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! \times 5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 & 6830 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6831 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 6831 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6832 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) & 6832 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
6833 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 6833 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6834 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6834 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6835 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 6835 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6836 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 & 6836 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
6837 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6837 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6838 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6838 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6839 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!!/4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6839 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6840 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6840 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6841 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 6841 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6842 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 & 6842 &:= -9 - 8 + (7!/6! + 5 + 4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6843 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 + 5!) - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6843 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
6844 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 6844 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! - (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
6845 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6845 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
6846 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6846 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6847 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6847 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6848 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6848 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! - 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
6849 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 6849 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6850 &:= 1 - (2 + 3!! + 45 - 6) \times (7 - 8) \times 9 & 6850 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6851 &:= 12/3! + 4 \times (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8) + 9 & 6851 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1)! \\
6852 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6852 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5! + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6853 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6853 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5! + 4!))) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6854 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 6854 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!) \times 4^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
6855 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 6855 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6856 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 6856 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6857 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & 6857 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6858 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6859 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6860 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6861 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6862 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6863 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6864 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6865 &:= 1 - (23 - 45) \times (6 + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\
6866 &:= ((12/3)^4 + 5 + 6!) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
6867 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6868 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6869 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6870 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6871 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6872 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6873 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6874 &:= 1 + (2^{3!} - 4) \times 5! - 6 \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\
6875 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
6876 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3! - 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6877 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9) \\
6878 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6879 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6880 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6881 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5! - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
6882 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6883 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6884 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6885 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6886 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6887 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6888 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))! \\
6889 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6890 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6891 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6892 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
6893 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6894 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6895 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6896 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6858 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4! + 32 + 1) \\
6859 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7! - 65 \times (4 - 32) - 1) \\
6860 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6861 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6862 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6863 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6864 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6865 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6866 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
6867 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6868 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6869 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6870 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 + 4) \times 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6871 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6872 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
6873 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6874 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
6875 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6876 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6877 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6878 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5^4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
6879 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6880 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6881 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6882 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6883 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6884 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6885 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6886 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
6887 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6888 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6889 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!/5)) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
6890 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6891 &:= -9 + (7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
6892 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6893 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6894 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6895 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6896 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6897 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6898 &:= 1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7) + 89 \\
6899 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6900 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6901 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
6902 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (5 \times 6 + 4 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6903 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6904 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6905 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6906 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6907 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6908 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6909 &:= -1 - 2 + ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6910 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6911 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6912 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6913 &:= -1 + 2 + ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6914 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6915 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4! - 5!) \times 6!/(7 - 8 - 9) \\
6916 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6917 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6918 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6919 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6920 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6921 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6922 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!^4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6923 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6924 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6925 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6926 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
6927 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6928 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9 \\
6929 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6930 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6931 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6932 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times 4! - (5 \times 6! - 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6933 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4! - 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6934 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4)) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6935 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6897 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6898 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
6899 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6900 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6901 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6902 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
6903 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7! - 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6904 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
6905 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6906 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6907 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
6908 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
6909 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6910 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6911 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/5! \\
6912 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6913 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6914 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6915 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
6916 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
6917 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6918 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6919 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6920 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3!)^{2+1} \\
6921 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6922 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3!)^{2+1}) \\
6923 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3!)^{2+1}) \\
6924 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
6925 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6926 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
6927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6928 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6929 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! \times (5! + 4)/6! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6930 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6931 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
6932 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5^4) \times (3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6933 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6934 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
6935 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6936 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
6937 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6938 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6939 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6940 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6941 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6942 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
6943 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6944 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6945 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6946 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6947 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6948 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6949 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4 + 5) + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6950 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6951 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6952 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6953 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6954 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6955 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6956 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6957 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6958 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6959 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6960 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6961 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6962 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6963 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6964 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 - 5!) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6965 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6966 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + \sqrt{4} \times 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6967 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
6968 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
6969 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6970 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6971 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6972 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6973 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6974 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6936 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6!/5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6937 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6938 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
6939 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5/6! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6940 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6941 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6942 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6943 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6944 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6945 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6946 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times 4^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6947 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6948 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6949 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6950 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6951 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6952 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
6953 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6954 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times (6!/5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6955 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6956 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6957 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6958 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
6959 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6960 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6961 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6962 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6!/5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6963 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! \times (4 + 3)/5 - 2 - 1) \\
6964 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6965 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times (5! + 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6966 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6967 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6968 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4^3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
6969 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6970 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
6971 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6972 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
6973 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6974 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) - (3 - 2 - 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6975 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6976 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
6977 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6978 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6979 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6980 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6981 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6982 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6983 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6984 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
6985 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6986 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 - 6) \times (8 + 9)/7 \\
6987 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times 4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
6988 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6989 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6990 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6991 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - (4 - 5!) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
6992 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
6993 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
6994 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6995 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
6996 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
6997 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
6998 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
6999 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7000 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7001 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7002 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7003 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7004 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7005 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7006 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7007 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7008 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7009 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7010 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7011 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7012 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6975 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5 + 4)/6! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6976 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6977 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
6978 &:= ((-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!))/5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6979 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4) \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!! \\
6980 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6981 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6982 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
6983 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! - 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6984 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6985 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
6986 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
6987 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6988 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6989 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
6990 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5) + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
6991 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6992 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4!/3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6993 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
6994 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1 \\
6995 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6996 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
6997 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! \times (4 + 3)/5 - (2 + 1)!) \\
6998 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
6999 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7000 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)^6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7001 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7002 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7003 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7004 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7005 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) + 2 + 1 \\
7006 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 + (4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
7007 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7008 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7009 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5!) - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7010 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7011 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7012 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3!) - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$7013 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$7014 := (-1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7015 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7016 := -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7017 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!/5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7018 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$7019 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7020 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7021 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7022 := -1 + 2 + (3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6) \times (8 + 9)/7$$

$$7023 := (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times 5 + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$7024 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7025 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$7026 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7027 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$7028 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$7029 := -1 - 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7030 := -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7031 := -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7032 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7033 := -1 + 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7034 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$7035 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7036 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7037 := -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7038 := -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7039 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7040 := (-1 + 2 - (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7041 := -1 + 2 - (3 - (4! - 5 - 6!)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7042 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7043 := -1 + (2 + 3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7044 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 5/4 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7045 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7046 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 + 5 - 6!)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7047 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$7048 := -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7049 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7050 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7013 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7014 := (-9 - (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7015 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7016 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7017 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$7018 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! \times (4 + 3)/5 - 2 - 1)$$

$$7019 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7020 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7021 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$7022 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7023 := -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7024 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7025 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7026 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$7027 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7028 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7029 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7030 := (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7031 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7032 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7033 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7034 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! \times (4 + 3)/5 - 2 - 1)$$

$$7035 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7036 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7037 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7038 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7039 := -9 - 8 \times (7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7040 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7041 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7042 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7043 := -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7044 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7045 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7046 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7047 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times ((6 - 5 + 4)! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7048 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7049 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7050 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7051 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7052 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7053 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7054 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7055 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7056 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7057 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7058 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7059 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4 + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7060 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7061 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7062 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7063 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7064 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7065 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7066 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7067 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7068 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7069 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7070 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7071 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7072 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7073 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7074 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7075 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7076 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7077 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7078 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7079 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7080 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7081 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7082 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7083 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7084 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3^4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7085 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7086 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7087 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) - 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7088 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7089 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7051 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7052 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7053 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7054 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7055 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7056 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7057 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7058 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7059 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7060 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7061 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7062 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7063 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7064 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7065 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7066 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7067 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7068 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7069 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7070 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7071 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7072 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7073 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7074 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7075 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7076 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7077 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7078 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7079 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7080 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7081 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7082 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
7083 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6! - 5 - 4 - 3)) + (2 + 1)!! \\
7084 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7085 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7086 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7087 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)!! \\
7088 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7089 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7090 &:= -1 \times ((2 - 3 + 4)!! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7091 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7092 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 7093 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7094 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 7095 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7096 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 - 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7097 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7098 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7099 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7100 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7101 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4} - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7102 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7103 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7104 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 7105 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7106 &:= (\sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} + \sqrt{4^5} \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 7107 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 - \sqrt{4} \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7108 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7109 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7110 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7111 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7112 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 7113 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 7114 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7115 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7116 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7117 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 + 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7118 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!!/(4 + 5) - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7119 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7120 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times (4! + 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 7121 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 7122 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7123 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7124 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7125 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4)) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7126 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7127 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7128 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7090 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7091 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7092 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - (6 + 5) \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 7093 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3!) + 2 + 1 \\
 7094 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7095 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7096 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
 7097 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! \times (4 + 3)/5 + (2 + 1)!) \\
 7098 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7099 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7100 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7101 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7102 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7103 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7104 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7105 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7106 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7107 &:= -9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7108 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7109 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!)) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
 7110 &:= (-9 + (8 - (7 - 6) \times 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7111 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7112 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!)) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7113 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7114 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7115 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7116 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 - 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7117 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 7118 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - (5 + 4) \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 7119 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7120 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7121 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7122 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7123 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7124 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7125 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
 7126 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7127 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5!)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7128 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7129 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7130 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7131 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7132 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7133 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7134 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7135 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7136 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + (4 + 5 - 6)!! \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7137 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7138 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7139 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7140 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7141 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7142 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 + (5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7143 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7144 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7145 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7146 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7147 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7148 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7149 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7150 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7151 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7152 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7153 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7154 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7155 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7156 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7157 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7158 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7159 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4)) \times 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7160 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!! - 4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7161 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7162 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7163 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7164 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4! - 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7165 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7166 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7167 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7168 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7129 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7130 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7131 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7132 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 - 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7133 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7134 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7135 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7136 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7137 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7138 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4 - 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
7139 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7140 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6!/5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7141 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7142 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7143 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7144 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7145 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
7146 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7147 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! - 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
7148 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7149 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
7150 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7151 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7152 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7153 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7154 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 + 4 - 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
7155 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
7156 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7157 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7158 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7159 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7160 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7161 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7162 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7163 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7164 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7165 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
7166 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7167 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7168 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7169 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7170 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7171 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times (4 - 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7172 &:= -1 \times 2 - ((3! + 4) \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7173 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7174 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7175 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7176 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7177 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7178 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7179 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7180 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7181 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7182 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7183 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7184 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + \sqrt{4} - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7185 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7186 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7187 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7188 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7189 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7190 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7191 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7192 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7193 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7194 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7195 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7196 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7197 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7198 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7199 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7200 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7201 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7202 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7203 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7204 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7205 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7206 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7207 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7208 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7169 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7170 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7171 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7172 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7173 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
7174 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7175 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5 - 4) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7176 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7177 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7178 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7179 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7180 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7181 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7182 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7183 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7184 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7185 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7186 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7187 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7188 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7189 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7190 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7191 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7192 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7193 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7194 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7195 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7196 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7197 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7198 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7199 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7200 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5)!! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7201 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7202 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!) \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7203 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7204 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7205 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7206 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7207 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (5 \times 4 + 6) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7208 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7209 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7210 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7211 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7212 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7213 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7214 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7215 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7216 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7217 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7218 &:= (-1 - (-3 \times 4 + 2) \times 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7219 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7220 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7221 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7222 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7223 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7224 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7225 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4!) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7226 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7227 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7228 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7229 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7230 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7231 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7232 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7233 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7234 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7235 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7236 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7237 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7238 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
 7239 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7240 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7241 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7242 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7243 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7244 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7245 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7246 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7247 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7248 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7209 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7210 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7211 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7212 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7213 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7214 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7215 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7216 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7217 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + (5 + 4 - 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 7218 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6!) \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7219 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7220 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7221 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 + 6! \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7222 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4^3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
 7223 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7224 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!! \\
 7225 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6^5 / (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 7226 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7227 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7228 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 7229 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 7230 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7231 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7232 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7233 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! / 6 - 5 - 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7234 &:= -9 - ((8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3!!)) - 2 - 1 \\
 7235 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! + 5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 7236 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 7237 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 7238 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! / 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7239 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 7240 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7241 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7242 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7243 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7244 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 7245 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7246 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7247 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7248 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7249 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7250 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7251 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7252 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7253 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7254 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3^4 + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7255 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!+4} + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7256 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7257 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7258 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7259 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7260 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 - \sqrt{4})^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7261 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7262 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7263 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7264 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7265 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7266 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7267 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7268 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7269 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7270 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7271 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7272 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4^5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7273 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7274 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7275 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7276 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7277 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7278 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7279 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7280 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!)) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7281 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7282 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7283 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7284 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7285 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7286 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7287 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7249 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7250 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7251 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7252 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
7253 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7254 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7255 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7256 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7257 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7258 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + (4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
7259 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7260 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7261 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
7262 &:= 98 \times 76 - 5! - 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
7263 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)) \\
7264 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! + (5 + 4) \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
7265 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7266 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7267 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 \times 4)^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
7268 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7269 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7270 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7271 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7272 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7273 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7274 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7275 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7276 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7277 &:= -9 - (8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7278 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7279 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7280 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7281 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)/5)^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7282 &:= 98 \times 76 - 5! - 43 - 2 - 1 \\
7283 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - 6! + (5 \times 4)^3 - 2 - 1 \\
7284 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7285 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7286 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7287 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7288 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7289 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 - \sqrt{4})^5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7290 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7291 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7292 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5! + (6! - 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
7293 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7294 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7295 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7296 &:= ((-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7297 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7298 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7299 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7300 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7301 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7302 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7303 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7304 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7305 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7306 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7308 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7309 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7310 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7311 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7312 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7313 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7314 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7315 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7316 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7317 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4 + 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7318 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 + 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7319 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7320 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7321 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4 + 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7322 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} - 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7323 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7324 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7325 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7326 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7288 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
7289 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\
7290 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! / (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
7291 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7292 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7293 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! \times 5/6!)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7294 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
7295 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5! / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7296 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7 + 6) \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7297 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7298 &:= 9 \times (87 + 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2) - 1 \\
7299 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 + 5) - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7300 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7301 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7302 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7303 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7304 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7305 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)! \\
7306 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) - 5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)! \\
7307 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7308 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7309 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
7310 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7311 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7312 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)! \\
7313 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! / 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3!! - (2 + 1)! \\
7314 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 + 5 \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7315 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7316 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)! \\
7317 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7318 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7319 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7320 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7321 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7! / 6! - 5! \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7322 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! / 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3!! + 2 + 1 \\
7323 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 - 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7324 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
7325 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
7326 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7327 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7328 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7329 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7330 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! + 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7331 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7332 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7333 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7334 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times ((5! - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7335 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7336 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7337 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7338 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7339 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7340 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7341 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7342 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7343 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7344 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7345 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7346 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4! - (5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7347 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7348 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7349 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7350 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4! \\
7351 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7352 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! \times 7/6) \times (8 + 9) \\
7353 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} - (4 + 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7354 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7355 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7356 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) + 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7357 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7358 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 - (4! - 5 + 6!)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7359 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7360 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7361 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7362 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7363 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7364 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
7365 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7327 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7328 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
7329 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7330 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7331 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7332 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5) \times \sqrt{4!/(3 + 2 + 1)} \\
7333 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7334 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
7335 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7336 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
7337 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
7338 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6!/5)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7339 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7340 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7341 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7342 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7343 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7344 &:= -9 \times 8 \times ((7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7345 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - (5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!)) \\
7346 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + (5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
7347 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7348 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! \times (4 + 3)/(2 + 1)! \\
7349 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7350 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5^4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7351 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7352 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) \times 4!/(5 \times 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
7353 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7354 &:= 98 + 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3!) - 2 + 1 \\
7355 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7356 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7357 &:= -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + (5 + 4) \times (3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
7358 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7359 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7360 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! + (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)) \\
7361 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
7362 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7363 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
7364 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7365 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7366 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7367 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7368 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7369 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7370 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7371 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times (4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7372 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7373 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 - (5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7374 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7375 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7376 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4)) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7377 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7378 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7379 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7380 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7381 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9)/4 \\
7382 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! - (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7383 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7384 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7385 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7386 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7387 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7388 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7389 &:= -1 + (-3 \times 4 + 2) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7390 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7391 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7392 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7393 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7394 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7395 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7396 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7397 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7398 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
7399 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
7400 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7401 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7402 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7403 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7404 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7405 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7366 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7367 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7368 &:= (-9 - (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7369 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
7370 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7371 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7372 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7373 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
7374 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7375 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times (5 + 4!)/6! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7376 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times 4!/3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7377 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - 5 - 4 - 3)) - 2 - 1 \\
7378 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7379 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
7380 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7381 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
7382 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
7383 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7384 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7385 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7386 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7387 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7388 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7389 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - (5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
7390 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7)^6) \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7391 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7392 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7393 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7394 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
7395 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7396 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
7397 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7398 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! \times 5!/6! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7399 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7400 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7401 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7402 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7403 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7404 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7405 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7406 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7407 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7408 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7409 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7410 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4} + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7411 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7412 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7413 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7414 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7415 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7416 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7417 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7418 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times 7 \times (8 + 9)/6 \\
7419 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7420 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7421 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7422 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7423 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7424 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7425 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7426 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7427 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7428 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7429 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7430 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7431 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7432 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7433 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7434 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7435 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7436 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7437 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7438 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4) \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7439 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4} + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7440 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7441 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7442 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7443 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7444 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7445 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7406 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7407 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4)))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7408 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7409 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!/5) \times (4 + 32 + 1) \\
7410 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7411 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7412 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7413 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7414 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7415 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7416 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (76 - (5 - 4! - 3! - 2)) \times 1 \\
7417 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7418 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7419 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7420 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7421 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7422 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7423 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7424 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7425 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5 - 4)!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7426 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7427 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7428 &:= (9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! - 5 \times 4!) \times 3!) \times 2 \times 1 \\
7429 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7430 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7431 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!! \\
7432 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7433 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7434 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
7435 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7436 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7437 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7438 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7439 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7440 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7441 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7442 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
7443 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7444 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
7445 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7446 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7447 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7448 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7449 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
7450 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7451 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7452 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7453 &:= -1 - (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7454 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7455 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7456 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7457 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7458 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7459 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7460 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7461 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7462 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7463 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7464 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3! \times (4 + 5))) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7465 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7466 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7467 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7468 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7469 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7470 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7471 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7472 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7473 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7474 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7475 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7476 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7477 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! - (4! + 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7478 &:= -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7479 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7480 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4!)) \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7481 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7482 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7483 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
7484 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7485 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7446 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7447 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7448 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7449 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7450 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7451 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7452 &:= -9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)) \\
7453 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7454 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4)/6 + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
7455 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 - 5 - 4^{3+2+1}) \\
7456 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1) \\
7457 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
7458 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4)/6 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7459 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7460 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7461 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7462 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7463 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7464 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3! - 2 + 1) \\
7465 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7466 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
7467 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7468 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7469 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7470 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7471 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7472 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7473 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7474 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7475 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7476 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7477 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5!/4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7478 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7479 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6)/(5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
7480 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7481 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7482 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
7483 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7484 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7485 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7486 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7487 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7488 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7489 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7490 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7491 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7492 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7493 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7494 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5) - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7495 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7496 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7497 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7498 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times (4! - 5) + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7499 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7500 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7501 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7502 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4!) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7503 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7504 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7505 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7506 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7507 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7508 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! - 4 \times (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7509 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! - (4! - 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7510 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7511 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! / 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7512 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3^4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7513 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7514 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! / 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7515 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7516 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8) - 9) \\
7517 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5! / 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7518 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7519 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7520 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)^4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7521 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7522 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7523 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7524 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7486 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5! / 6!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7487 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7488 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / (6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)!!)) \\
7489 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + (5 - 4)^{3^{21}} \\
7490 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5! / 6!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7491 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7492 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! / 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7493 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7494 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)! \\
7495 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! / 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7496 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
7497 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! + 6) / (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
7498 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5! / 6!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7499 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5! / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7500 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7501 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7502 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7503 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7504 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + (5! - 4!) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7505 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7! / 6!) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7506 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 \times 21 \\
7507 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7508 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7509 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7510 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7511 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7512 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5! / 6!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7513 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7514 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7515 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7516 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 - 3^{2+1} \\
7517 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7518 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 4 \\
7519 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7520 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5 \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
7521 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7522 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! + 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
7523 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 - 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7524 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7525 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7526 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7527 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7528 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7529 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7530 &:= (1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! \times 5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7531 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7532 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7533 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7534 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7535 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7536 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7537 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7538 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7539 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7540 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7541 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) \times 7/6 - 8 - 9 \\
7542 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7543 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
7544 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7545 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7546 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7547 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7548 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7549 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7550 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7551 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7552 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7553 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7554 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7555 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7556 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7557 &:= -1 - 2 - (3^4 \times 5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7558 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7559 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7560 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/(4 \times 5) \\
7561 &:= -1 + 2 - (3^4 \times 5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7562 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7563 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7564 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7525 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
7526 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
7527 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7528 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) - 5) \times 4!/(3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
7529 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7530 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!)) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7531 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7532 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7533 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7534 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6) \times (2 + 1)/(5 - 4 - 3) \\
7535 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7536 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
7537 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7538 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7539 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/((6 - 5) \times 4) \\
7540 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7541 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7542 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
7543 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7544 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7545 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7546 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! - \sqrt{4}) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7547 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7548 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7549 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7550 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6) \times (2 + 1)/(5 - 4 - 3) \\
7551 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5 - 4)!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7552 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! + 6) \times (2 + 1)/(5 - 4 - 3) \\
7553 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7554 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!)/((6 - 5) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7555 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7556 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
7557 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7558 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7559 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7560 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7561 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7562 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7563 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7564 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$7565 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7566 := ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7567 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7568 := -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7569 := -1 - (2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7570 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7571 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$7572 := (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7573 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5!) - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7574 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5) \times 7/6 + 8 + 9$$

$$7575 := -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7576 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) \times 7/6 + 8 + 9$$

$$7577 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times ((4! + 5 + 6)/7)! + 8 + 9$$

$$7578 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7579 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7580 := (-1 - 2 - 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7581 := -1 + 2 \times (3!^{4+5-6} + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7582 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7583 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7584 := (-1 + 2 - 3^4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7585 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7586 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$7587 := -1 - 2 - 3! \times ((4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$7588 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$7589 := -1 - 2 \times 3 \times ((4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$7590 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7591 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$7592 := -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 - 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$7593 := -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4^5 + 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7594 := -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$7595 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$7596 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 - 5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7597 := -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) \times 7/6 + 8 + 9$$

$$7598 := -1 + (2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7599 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7600 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7601 := (-3 \times 4 - 1 + 2) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$7602 := (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7603 := -1 - 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7565 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$7566 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$7567 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7568 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7569 := -9 \times (8 - (7! + 6 \times (5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7570 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4) + (3 - 2 - 1)!$$

$$7571 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)!$$

$$7572 := 9 \times (8 + 7!/6) + 5!/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$7573 := -9 + (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1})$$

$$7574 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$7575 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$7576 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$7577 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$7578 := -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5!/6! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7579 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7580 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! + 5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$7581 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$7582 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7!/6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7583 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7584 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7585 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + (5 + 4) \times 3!!/(2 + 1)!)$$

$$7586 := -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 + 3^{2+1}$$

$$7587 := -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$7588 := -8 \times 7 - 9 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$7589 := -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$7590 := (-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!)/5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7591 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7592 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4 \times 3!!/(2 + 1))$$

$$7593 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$7594 := -9 - 8 \times 7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!)) - 2 - 1$$

$$7595 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7596 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7597 := -8 \times 7 - 9 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$7598 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7599 := -9 + (8 + 7!/((6 - 5) \times 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7600 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5! \times 4/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7601 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)$$

$$7602 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! \times 5/4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$7603 := (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!/5)) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7604 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7605 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7606 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7607 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7608 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5 \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7609 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7610 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7611 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7612 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^5 + 67 \times 8 \times 9) \\
7613 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7614 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!!)/4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7615 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7616 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7617 &:= 12^3 \times 4 - 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7618 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5) + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7619 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7620 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4}) \times 5 \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
7621 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7622 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5! \times (6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7623 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7624 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7625 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7626 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7627 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 \times (5! - 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7628 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 \times (5! - 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7629 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7630 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7631 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7632 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7633 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7634 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7635 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7636 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7637 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7638 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7639 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7640 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7641 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7642 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8)) \times 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7604 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7605 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7606 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7607 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7608 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7609 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7610 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7611 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7612 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7613 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7614 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7615 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5! \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
7616 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
7617 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7618 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7619 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7620 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7621 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7622 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7623 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7624 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7625 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7626 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7627 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7628 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7629 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7630 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7631 &:= 98 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 - 3^{2+1} \\
7632 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7633 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7634 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7635 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7636 &:= 9 \times 876 - (5! + 4) \times (3 - 2 + 1) \\
7637 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7638 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7639 &:= 98 \times 76 - (5^4 - 3!!) \times 2 + 1 \\
7640 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7641 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7642 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7643 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7644 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
 7645 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7646 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7647 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7648 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7649 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7650 &:= (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7651 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7652 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 7653 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7654 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
 7655 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7656 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7657 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7658 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7659 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 7660 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 7661 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7662 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7663 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
 7664 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7665 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7666 &:= -1 + ((2 - 3!) \times (4 - 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 7667 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 7668 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!!/4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 7669 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7670 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7671 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7672 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 7673 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5! - 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 7674 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7675 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 7676 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 7677 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7678 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7679 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7680 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 7681 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7643 &:= 9 - (87 - 6^5 + 4!) - 32 + 1 \\
 7644 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 7645 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7646 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7647 &:= (9 - 8 - 7) \times 6 + 5! \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7648 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7649 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7650 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7651 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/6) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7652 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1) \\
 7653 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7654 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
 7655 &:= -9 + 8 - \sqrt{7 - 6 + 5!} \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7656 &:= (-9 + 8/(7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7657 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
 7658 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
 7659 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7660 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 7661 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7662 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7663 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7664 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7665 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) - 4! - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 7666 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 7667 &:= 9 - 8 + 7!/6! + 5! \times 4^3 - 21 \\
 7668 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! - 6!/(5 + 4))/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7669 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7670 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7671 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7672 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 7673 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 7674 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7675 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7676 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7677 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 7678 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 7679 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 7680 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 7681 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7682 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4 + (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7683 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7684 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7685 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7686 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7687 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7688 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7689 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7690 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7691 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7692 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7693 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7694 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7695 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7696 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
7697 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7698 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7699 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7700 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7701 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7702 &:= -1 + 2 + ((3!! \times 4 - 5!)/6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7703 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7704 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7705 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7706 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 - 5! - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
7707 &:= 1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5 - 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
7708 &:= 1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + (5! - 6 - 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
7709 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7710 &:= ((-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7711 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7712 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
7713 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7714 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7715 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7716 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7717 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7718 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7719 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7682 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7683 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 \times 6! + 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7684 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7685 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7686 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7687 &:= 9 - 87 + 6^5 - 4 - 3! - 2 + 1 \\
7688 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7689 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7690 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7691 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7692 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7693 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7694 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7695 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7696 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7697 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
7698 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7699 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! + 5 + 43 + 2) - 1 \\
7700 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7701 &:= 9 - 87 + 6^5 - 4 + 3! + 2 - 1 \\
7702 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7703 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7704 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7! - 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7705 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7706 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7707 &:= \sqrt{9} \times \sqrt{87 - 6} + 5! \times \sqrt{4^{3 \times 2 + 1}} \\
7708 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7709 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7710 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7711 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7712 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7713 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6!)/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7714 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7715 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7716 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + (6!/5!)^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7717 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - (6!/5!)^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7718 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7719 &:= (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7)^6 \times 5! + 4 + 3!^2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7720 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7721 &:= 1^2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times 6 + 7! + 89 \\
7722 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7723 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7724 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7725 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7726 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7727 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7728 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7729 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7730 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7731 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!)) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7732 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})^5 - 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
7733 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!^4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7734 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)!/4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7735 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3!)) \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7736 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})^5 - (6 \times 7 - 8 + 9) \\
7737 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7738 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7739 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7740 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7741 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7742 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7743 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7744 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7745 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7746 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7747 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7748 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7749 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7750 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7751 &:= (1^2 + 3 + \sqrt{4})^5 - (6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7752 &:= (1 \times 23 - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
7753 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7754 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7755 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7756 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7757 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7720 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7721 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7722 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7723 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
7724 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
7725 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5! - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7726 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7727 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7728 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7729 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7730 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7731 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7732 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7733 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6!/5!)^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7734 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7735 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 - 5!)) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7736 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7737 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7738 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7739 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7740 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7741 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7742 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3! + 2 \times 1 \\
7743 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - 6 + 5!) \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7744 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - \sqrt{4} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7745 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 32 + 1 \\
7746 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7747 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7748 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7749 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6!) \times 4!/5! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7750 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7751 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7752 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7753 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7754 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7755 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7756 &:= (98 + 7 \times 6 \times 5! \times 3/4) \times 2 \times 1 \\
7757 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 \times 6! + 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7758 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7759 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^{(4!+5+6)/7} - 8 - 9 \\
7760 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^{(4!+5+6)/7} - 8 - 9 \\
7761 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7762 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
7763 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!^4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7764 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7765 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7766 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7767 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7768 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7769 &:= 1 - 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7770 &:= 1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5) \times (6 - 789) \\
7771 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7772 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7773 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7774 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7775 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7776 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7777 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7778 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7779 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7780 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7781 &:= (1 \times 2)^3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6789 \\
7782 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7783 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7784 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7785 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7786 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7787 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!^4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7788 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7789 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7790 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) - 4! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7791 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7792 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^{(4!+5+6)/7} + 8 + 9 \\
7793 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7794 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7758 &:= 9 \times (8 + (7! - 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7759 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7760 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7761 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7762 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/6) + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7763 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7764 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7765 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7766 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)^5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7767 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7768 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
7769 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
7770 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
7771 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 - (7 - 6^5 + \sqrt{4} - 3 \times 2 \times 1) \\
7772 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6^5 - 4 \times (-2 \times 1 + 3) \\
7773 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7774 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)^5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7775 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7776 &:= (98/7 - 6) \times 54 \times 3! \times (2 + 1) \\
7777 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - (4 - 3)^2 \\
7778 &:= 9 \times 876 - (5! - 4 - 3^2 - 1) \\
7779 &:= 98/7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3! - 21 \\
7780 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7781 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - ((6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7782 &:= \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7783 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7784 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 21 \\
7785 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7786 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7787 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7788 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7789 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7790 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7791 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7792 &:= 9 \times 876 - 5! - 4 + 32 \times 1 \\
7793 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6^5 + 4 + 3! \times 2 + 1 \\
7794 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7795 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7796 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
7797 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7798 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7799 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7800 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7801 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!^{4-5+6} + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7802 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
7803 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7804 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
7805 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7806 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7807 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times ((4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7808 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7809 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7810 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7811 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7812 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7813 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7814 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4! \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7815 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7816 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7817 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!^4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7818 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7819 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7820 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7821 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7822 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7823 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7824 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7825 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7826 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7827 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7828 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7829 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7830 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7831 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7832 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7833 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7795 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
7796 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7797 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7798 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7799 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7800 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7801 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7802 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) - \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7803 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7804 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
7805 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7806 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 + 1 \\
7807 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7808 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
7809 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
7810 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7811 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7812 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7813 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6^5 + 4! + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
7814 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!)) - 2 - 1 \\
7815 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! + 3! - 2 + 1 \\
7816 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7817 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + (6!/5!)^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7818 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7819 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7820 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7821 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7822 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7823 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^{5!/(4 \times (3+2+1))} \\
7824 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7825 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7826 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7827 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7828 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7829 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7830 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7831 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7832 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7833 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 \times 3/4 + 21
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7834 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
7835 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
7836 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7837 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7838 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7839 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7840 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
7841 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7842 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7843 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4!) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7844 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7845 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7846 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
7847 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7848 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7849 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7850 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7851 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!) - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7852 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7853 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7854 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7855 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7856 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7857 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9) \\
7858 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7859 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7860 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7861 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times 5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7862 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7863 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7864 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7865 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7866 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7867 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7868 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)!) + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7869 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7870 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7871 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7872 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
7873 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7834 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7835 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7836 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7837 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7838 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4!/3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7839 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
7840 &:= -9 - 8 - ((7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7841 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7842 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7843 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7844 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7845 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7846 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5 - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
7847 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7848 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7849 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7850 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7851 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7852 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7853 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7854 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)!) - 6) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7855 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7856 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7857 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!/5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7858 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6! + 5) \times \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7859 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7860 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7861 &:= -9 - (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
7862 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7863 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7864 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7865 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!) \\
7866 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7867 &:= -9 - (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7868 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7869 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7870 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!) + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7871 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
7872 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7873 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7874 &:= -1 - 2^3! + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7875 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7876 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7877 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7878 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7879 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
7880 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7881 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7882 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7883 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7884 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7885 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7886 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 - (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
7887 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7888 &:= (-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)!)/(5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7889 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7890 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7891 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7892 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
7893 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7894 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7895 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7896 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7897 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7898 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4! + 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7899 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7900 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7901 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7902 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7903 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7904 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
7905 &:= -1 + 2^3! \times (4 + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7906 &:= (-1 - 2^3!) \times (4 - 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7907 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7908 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4^5)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
7909 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7910 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!)) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7911 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7912 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7913 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7874 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6! + 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7875 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!! \\
7876 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7877 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7878 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7879 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7880 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
7881 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
7882 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7883 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7884 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! + (6 + 5) \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7885 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7886 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - 4 \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!) \\
7887 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
7888 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (\sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7889 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7890 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7891 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7892 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7893 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7894 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
7895 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7896 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7897 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7898 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7899 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7900 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7901 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
7902 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
7903 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + (6 - 5) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7904 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7905 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7906 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7907 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7908 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7909 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7910 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7911 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7912 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7913 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7914 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7915 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7916 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7917 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7918 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7919 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7920 &:= -1 \times (2 \times 3)! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7921 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7922 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5!)) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7923 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7924 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7925 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
7926 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7927 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7928 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
7929 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7930 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7931 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7932 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7933 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7934 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7935 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7936 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7937 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7938 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7939 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7940 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7941 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7942 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7943 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7944 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)! \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7945 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7946 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7947 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7948 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7949 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7950 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7951 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7952 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
7953 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7914 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7915 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7916 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7917 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7918 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7919 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7920 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7921 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7922 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7923 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7924 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7925 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7926 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7927 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7928 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!/5! + 4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
7929 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7930 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7931 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7932 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7933 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
7934 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
7935 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7936 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
7937 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
7938 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7939 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
7940 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7941 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7942 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
7943 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7944 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
7945 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7946 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! + 5 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
7947 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - 5 - 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7948 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
7949 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7950 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7951 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
7952 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! - 4^{3+2+1}) \\
7953 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$7954 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7955 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7956 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7957 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)/(4 \times 5)$$

$$7958 := (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$7959 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7960 := -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4! \times (5! + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$7961 := -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$7962 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7963 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7964 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7965 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7966 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7967 := -1 + (2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7968 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7969 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$7970 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7971 := -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7972 := -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4! + 5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7973 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7974 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$7975 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7976 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7977 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7978 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$7979 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7980 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$7981 := -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$7982 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4^5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7983 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7984 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7985 := -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7986 := (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7987 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7988 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7989 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7990 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$7991 := -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4) - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$7992 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7954 := -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7955 := -9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7956 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7957 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7958 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7959 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7960 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1})$$

$$7961 := -9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$7962 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9 + 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$7963 := -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7964 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6! + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$7965 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7966 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3!! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7967 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5!/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7968 := ((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7969 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3^{(2+1)!})$$

$$7970 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7971 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7972 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - 3!) - 2 - 1$$

$$7973 := -9 - 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$7974 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7975 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7976 := (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)) \times (4 + 3)/5 + 2 + 1$$

$$7977 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$7978 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4^3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$7979 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7980 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7981 := -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3^{(2+1)!})$$

$$7982 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3!! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7983 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4!)) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7984 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}}$$

$$7985 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$7986 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$7987 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$7988 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7989 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$7990 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$7991 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$7992 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7993 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7994 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7995 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
7996 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
7997 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
7998 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
7999 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8000 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8001 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8002 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8003 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8004 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8005 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8006 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8007 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4) \times (5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8008 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8009 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8010 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8011 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8012 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8013 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8014 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8015 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8016 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8017 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4^5 - 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8018 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8019 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!!/(4 + 5) + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8020 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8021 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8022 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8023 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8024 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8025 &:= -1 + 2 - ((3! - 4! \times 5!)/6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8026 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8027 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5!) - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8028 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8029 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8030 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7993 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 - 4 - 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
7994 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4))^3 - (2 + 1)! \\
7995 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
7996 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
7997 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
7998 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
7999 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8000 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4^{3+2+1}} \\
8001 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8002 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
8003 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
8004 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8005 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8006 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4))^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8007 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 - 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8008 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
8009 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + \sqrt{(6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}} \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\
8010 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8011 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8012 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^{3!-2-1} \\
8013 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8014 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
8015 &:= 98 + 7! + 6 \times 5! \times 4 - 3! + 2 + 1 \\
8016 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8017 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8018 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8019 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8020 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
8021 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8022 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8023 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8024 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 - 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8025 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8026 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4^3 + 2 + 1) \\
8027 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8028 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8029 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8030 &:= (98 - 76) \times 5 \times (4! \times 3 + 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8031 &:= -1 - ((2+3)^4 - 5 \times 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8032 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8033 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8034 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8035 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3+4)!/5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
8036 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8037 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8038 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8039 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8040 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3! \times (4 + 5)) \times 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8041 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8042 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8043 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8044 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8045 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8046 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8047 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8048 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5!) \times 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8049 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4^5 - 6! \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8050 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8051 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5! + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8052 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - 5!) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8053 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8054 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8055 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8056 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8057 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8058 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8059 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8060 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8061 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8062 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8063 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8064 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8065 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8066 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8067 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8068 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8069 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8031 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8032 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8033 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8034 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8035 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8036 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8037 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8038 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6! \times 3!/(5 + 4)) - 2 - 1 \\
8039 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8040 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8041 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8042 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8043 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
8044 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8045 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8046 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8047 &:= 98 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8048 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
8049 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8050 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6!) \times (4 + 3)/5 + 2 + 1 \\
8051 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8052 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 \times 5) + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8053 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
8054 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8055 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8056 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8057 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8058 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5! \times 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8059 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) + 4 + 3!! \times 2 \times 1 \\
8060 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8061 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7!/(6 - 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8062 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8063 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8064 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8065 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8066 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times (4 + 3)/5 + 2 + 1 \\
8067 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8068 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8069 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8070 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8071 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5! + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8072 &:= -1 + 2^{3!-4+5+6} - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8073 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - (4! + 5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8074 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8075 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8076 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8077 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8078 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8079 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8080 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8081 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8082 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8083 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8084 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8085 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8086 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8087 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8088 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 - 5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8089 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8090 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8091 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5 - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8092 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8093 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8094 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8095 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8096 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8097 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8098 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8099 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8100 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8101 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4!) \times 5 \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8102 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8103 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8104 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8105 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8106 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8107 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times ((4! - 5 - 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
8108 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8109 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4! - (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8070 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)}) \\
8071 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8072 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
8073 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8074 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
8075 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8076 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8077 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8078 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4!) - 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
8079 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8080 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6!/(5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8081 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8082 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 - 5 + 4)!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8083 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!) - 4!) + (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
8084 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8085 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! \times 5/4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8086 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8087 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8088 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5)) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8089 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6^5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8090 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
8091 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8092 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8093 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8094 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8095 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8096 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
8097 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! \times 5/4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8098 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8099 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8100 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8101 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)! \\
8102 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4 + 32 + 1 \\
8103 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 - 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8104 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5 - (4 \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
8105 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8106 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8107 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8108 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
8109 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8110 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3+4)!/5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8111 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8112 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8113 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8114 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8115 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4^5 - 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8116 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8117 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8118 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8119 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8120 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8121 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8122 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8123 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8124 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 45) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8125 &:= 1 - (2 - 3!! + 4) + (5! - 6) \times (7 \times 8 + 9) \\
8126 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8127 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8128 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8129 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8130 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8131 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8132 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8133 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8134 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8135 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8136 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8137 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8138 &:= \sqrt{12/3} - 4! + 5! \times (67 - 8 + 9) \\
8139 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8140 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8141 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8142 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8143 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5 + \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}) \\
8144 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8145 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8146 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8147 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8148 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! - 4^5)) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8110 &:= 9 \times 876 + 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!^{2+1} \\
8111 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8112 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8113 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
8114 &:= (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4 + 321 \\
8115 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
8116 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
8117 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8118 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! \times (5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6!) \\
8119 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8120 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7!/6! - 5) \times 4^{3+2+1} \\
8121 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8122 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
8123 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8124 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^{4!/(3+2+1)} \\
8125 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - (4 - 3!!/2 + 1) \\
8126 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8127 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8128 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 + 3!) - 2 - 1 \\
8129 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6^5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8130 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8131 &:= 98 - 7 + 6! + 5! \times (4^3 - 2 - 1) \\
8132 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8133 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8134 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8135 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8136 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8137 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8138 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8139 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8140 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8141 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8142 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - (6 - 5 + 4)!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8143 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8144 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8145 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8146 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8147 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8148 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3^{(2+1)!})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8149 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8149 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8150 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 8150 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8151 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9) & 8151 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8152 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 & 8152 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8153 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 8153 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
8154 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 8154 &:= (-9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8155 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 & 8155 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8156 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 8156 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1) \\
8157 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8157 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7! / 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
8158 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8158 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8159 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8159 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8160 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8160 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8161 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8161 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 \times (4! - 3!!)) / (2 + 1) \\
8162 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9)) & 8162 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! \times 5/4) \times 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
8163 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 & 8163 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 + 5! / 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8164 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 8164 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3!! / (2 + 1) \\
8165 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 + (4! - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 8165 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8166 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8166 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8167 &:= -1 + 2^{3!-4+5+6} - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8167 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! / 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8168 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) & 8168 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + (4! + 3!!) / (2 + 1) \\
8169 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (-5 \times 6 + 4) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 8169 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8170 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4/5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 8170 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6^5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8171 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8171 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
8172 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 8172 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4) / 6 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8173 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8173 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8174 &:= -1 - 2^{3!+4} \times (5 - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 & 8174 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8175 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 8175 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8176 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 8176 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8177 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 8177 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8178 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 8178 &:= (-9 + (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8179 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) & 8179 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6) - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8180 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) & 8180 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! / 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8181 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8181 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8182 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 8182 &:= 98 + 7 + 6 - 5! + 4^{3!} \times 2 - 1 \\
8183 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! + 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8183 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! / 6! - 5)^{4+3+2+1} \\
8184 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 8184 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6! + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8185 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) & 8185 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8186 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 8186 &:= (9 + 8 - 7! + 6^5 - 4!) \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\
8187 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) & 8187 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$8188 := -1 + 2 + 3 + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$8189 := -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8190 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8191 := 1 + (2 \times 3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (5 \times 6! + (7 + 8) \times 9)$$

$$8192 := \sqrt{-1 + 2 + 3} \times 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}$$

$$8193 := -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8194 := -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8195 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8196 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8197 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8198 := -1 \times 2 - ((3 + 4)! - 5!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)/6$$

$$8199 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8200 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8201 := -1 + 2^{3! - 4 + 5 + 6} - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8202 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8203 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9})$$

$$8204 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times (5! - 6) - 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$8205 := -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8206 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8207 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8208 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8209 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8210 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - (4^5 + 6! - 7! - 89))$$

$$8211 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8212 := -1 + 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8213 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! - 6) + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8214 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8215 := -1 + 2^{3! - 4 + 5 + 6} + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8216 := \sqrt{(-1 + 2 + 3)^{(4 + 5 + 6)}} + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8217 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8218 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8219 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8220 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8221 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8222 := -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8223 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8224 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$8225 := (-1 + 2)^3 + 4^5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8188 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8189 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8190 := -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8191 := -9 + 8 + (7!/6! - 5) \times 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8192 := (9 - 8) \times \sqrt{-7 + 6 + 5} \times 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8193 := -9 \times (8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4 - 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8194 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8195 := -9 - 8 \times (4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!) / (7 - 6 - 5)$$

$$8196 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8197 := -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4! \times 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8198 := -9 - 8 + 7 + (6^5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8199 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8200 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6^5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8201 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8202 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}}) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8203 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8204 := -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8205 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4 - 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$8206 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8207 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8208 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!$$

$$8209 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8210 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8211 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8212 := -9 \times (8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8213 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8214 := -9 \times 8 \times (7! - 6^5) / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8215 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8216 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8217 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8218 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3!!) + 2 + 1$$

$$8219 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - ((6 - 5!) \times 4! - 3!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8220 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8221 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8222 := -9 + 8 + (7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4!) \times 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8223 := -9 + (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)! \times (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$8224 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8225 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8226 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8227 &:= -1 - (2 - (3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8228 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8229 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8230 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8231 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8232 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^{4+5-6} \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8233 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8234 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8235 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8236 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8237 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3^4 - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8238 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8239 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8240 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8241 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8242 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8243 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8244 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8245 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8246 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8247 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8248 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8249 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8250 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8251 &:= -1 + 2 + ((3 - 4!) \times 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8252 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8253 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times 4! - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8254 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8255 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8256 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8257 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! / 4) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8258 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 8259 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8260 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8261 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8262 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8263 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8264 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8226 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 8227 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8228 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8229 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8230 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8231 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8232 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8233 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 8234 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
 8235 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8236 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 5/6 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 8237 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8238 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8239 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
 8240 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8241 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8242 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
 8243 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8244 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8245 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8246 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8247 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8248 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
 8249 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8250 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! - 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8251 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
 8252 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4 - 3!! / (2 + 1) \\
 8253 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5!/4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8254 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 + 5! - 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 8255 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6^5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 8256 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8257 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8258 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8259 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1) \\
 8260 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8261 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8262 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
 8263 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4)/6 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8264 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8265 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8266 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8267 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8268 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8269 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8270 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8271 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8272 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 - 4 - 5! \times (6! - 789) \\
8273 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9) \\
8274 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))) \\
8275 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4 - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8276 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8277 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8278 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8279 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8280 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8281 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8282 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8283 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8284 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8285 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8286 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! + (4! \times 5! / 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8287 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4^5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8288 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 - 5!) \times 6! / (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8289 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8290 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8291 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8292 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8293 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8294 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8295 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8296 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
8297 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8298 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8299 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
8300 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8301 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8302 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) / \sqrt{4} \\
8303 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8265 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8266 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8267 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8268 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
8269 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 + 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
8270 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - (5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!)) \\
8271 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8272 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 + 3^{(2+1)!} \\
8273 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8274 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8275 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8276 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6! / 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8277 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 - 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8278 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! / 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8279 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8280 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! / 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8281 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8282 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8283 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 + 5) + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)! \\
8284 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6! / 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8285 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6! / 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8286 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8287 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6^5 / 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8288 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5 + 4) / 6 + 3^{(2+1)!} \\
8289 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / 6 - 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8290 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8291 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8292 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5!) - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8293 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
8294 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + (4! / 3)^{2+1} \\
8295 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8296 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8297 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8298 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! / ((6 - 5) \times 4)!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8299 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 \times \sqrt{3^{(2+1)!}} \\
8300 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8301 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
8302 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8303 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 / 3! - (2 + 1)!!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8304 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8305 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8306 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) - 5) \times 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8307 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6!/(7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8308 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8309 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 - 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8310 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8311 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4! + 5 - 6!)) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8312 &:= -1 + (2 - (3! - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8313 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9) \\
8314 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8315 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8316 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8317 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8318 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8319 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8320 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8321 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8322 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8323 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8324 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (34 - (5! + 6! - 7! + 8 \times 9)) \\
8325 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8326 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4)! + 5!)/6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8327 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8328 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8329 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8330 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8331 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8332 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8333 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8334 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8335 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8336 &:= (1 + 2)! - (3 + 4 - 5! - 6) \times 7!/(8 \times 9) \\
8337 &:= -1 - 2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8338 &:= -1 \times 2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8339 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8340 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8341 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8342 &:= -1 - 2 \times (((3 + 4)! + 5!)/6 - 7!) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8304 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8305 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))^{5!/4!-3} - (2 + 1)!! \\
8306 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)! \\
8307 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8308 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
8309 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
8310 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8311 &:= -9 - (8 - 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8312 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8313 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8314 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4/3! + 2 + 1 \\
8315 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
8316 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5 \times 4)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8317 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4/3! + (2 + 1)! \\
8318 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
8319 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
8320 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8321 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8322 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8323 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - 5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
8324 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8325 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! + 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}) \\
8326 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)! \\
8327 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6!/5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8328 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
8329 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8330 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8331 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8332 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8333 &:= -9 - 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8334 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8335 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8336 &:= (-9/(8 + 7 - 6) + 5!) \times 4^3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8337 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8338 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7!/6) \times 5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8339 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8340 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8341 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8342 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$8343 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$8344 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5 - 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$8345 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8346 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8347 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8348 := (-1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times 5! + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8349 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8350 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8351 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8352 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8353 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8354 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8355 := -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8356 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 - 5!) \times 6!/(7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8357 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + (4! + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8358 := -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8359 := -1 - (2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8360 := (-1 - (2 - 3 - 4) - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8361 := (-1 + 2)^3 + (4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8362 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8363 := -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$8364 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8365 := -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8366 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8367 := -1 + 2 + 3! + (4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8368 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8369 := -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8370 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8371 := (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8372 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8373 := -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8374 := -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8375 := -1 + (2 \times 3!!/4 - 5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8376 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8377 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8378 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8379 := -1 + 2 - 3 + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8380 := -1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4! - 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8381 := -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8382 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8343 := -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8344 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8345 := -9 - ((8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8346 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8347 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$8348 := -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

$$8349 := -9 + 8 + (7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8350 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5 - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)!$$

$$8351 := -9 + 8 - (7!/6! + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8352 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8353 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8354 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8355 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$8356 := (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6) \times 4/5 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8357 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8358 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8359 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8360 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5! + 4 - 3! \times (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8361 := -9 - (8 - 7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8362 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8363 := -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8364 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8365 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8366 := -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$8367 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8368 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8369 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8370 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8371 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8372 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - (4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!!))$$

$$8373 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8374 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$8375 := -9 + (8 - (7! - 6! - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8376 := -9 - 8 - 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8377 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^{5/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8378 := -9 \times 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8379 := -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - 5 + 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8380 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8381 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8382 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8383 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3^4) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8384 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8385 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8386 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8387 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8388 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8389 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8390 &:= -1 \times (2 - 3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8391 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8392 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8393 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8394 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8395 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8396 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8397 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 - 4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8398 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8399 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8400 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8401 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8402 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8403 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8404 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8405 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4!)) + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8406 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4)! - 5!)/6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8407 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8408 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8409 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8410 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8411 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8412 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8413 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8414 &:= (2 \times 3 - 1 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8415 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8416 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8417 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8418 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8419 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8420 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8421 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8422 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8383 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
8384 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
8385 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8386 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8387 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8388 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8389 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8390 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8391 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8392 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8393 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8394 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8395 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8396 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
8397 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8398 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8399 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/6! \\
8400 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8401 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8402 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8403 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! + 6! - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8404 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8405 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8406 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8407 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8408 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4)^3 - (2 + 1)! \\
8409 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8410 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7!/6) \times 5 \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8411 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8412 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8413 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8414 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8415 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8416 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8417 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8418 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8419 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8420 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8421 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8422 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! \times 4! \times 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$8423 := -1 - (2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8424 := (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8425 := -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8426 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$8427 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4! - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8428 := -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$8429 := -1 - ((2 - 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8430 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8431 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4^5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8432 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! + (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8433 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8434 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5! - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8435 := -1 - (2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8436 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8437 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times ((5 - 6 + 7)! - 8 - 9)$$

$$8438 := -1 + 2 - 3 - (4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8439 := -1 + (2 - (3 + 4) \times 5! - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8440 := (-1 - (2^{3+4} - 5 + 6!)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8441 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8442 := (-1 + 2 \times 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8443 := -1 - 2 - 3 + (4 \times (5! + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8444 := -1 + 2^{3!} + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8445 := -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6! - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8446 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) + 6! - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8447 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8448 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5! - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8449 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8450 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8451 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5 + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8452 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 + (4 \times (5! + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8453 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4 \times (5! + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8454 := (-1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8455 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8456 := -1 - 2 \times (((3 + 4)! - 5!)/6 - 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$8457 := -1 - 2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8458 := -1 \times 2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5! + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8459 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8460 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - 4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8461 := -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8423 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8424 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8425 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8426 := -9 + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$8427 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8428 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8429 := -9 + 8 - ((7 + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$8430 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8431 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8432 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + (4!/3)^{2+1}$$

$$8433 := -9 - 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8434 := (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6! - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8435 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8436 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + (6! - 5) \times \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8437 := (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8438 := -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8439 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/(6 + 5 + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8440 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8441 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8442 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8443 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8444 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$8445 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8446 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8447 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8448 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8449 := -9 + 8 + (7!/6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8450 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8451 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8452 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8453 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8454 := (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6! - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8455 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8456 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8457 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8458 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! - 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8459 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8460 := ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8461 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8462 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8463 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8464 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8465 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8466 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8467 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8468 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8469 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8470 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8471 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4!)^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8472 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8473 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8474 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (((3 + 4)! - 5!)/6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8475 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times (6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8476 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! - 6)/4 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8477 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8478 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8479 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8480 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8481 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8482 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8483 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8484 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8485 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
8486 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4)^5 + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8487 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8488 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4) \times (5! + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8489 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8490 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5 \\
8491 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + (4! + 5!) \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8492 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8493 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8494 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8495 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8496 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8497 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8498 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8499 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8462 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8463 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8464 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8465 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8466 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8467 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8468 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8469 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8470 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8471 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! \times 5!/6!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8472 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8473 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 4!/5 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8474 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4 - 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
8475 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
8476 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8477 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8478 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8479 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
8480 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8481 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8482 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8483 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8484 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8485 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8486 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8487 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8488 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8489 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8490 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^{5!/4!} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8491 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8492 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8493 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8494 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8495 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
8496 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8497 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8498 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8499 &:= -9 + (8 + (7! + 6! - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8500 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8501 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8502 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8503 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8504 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8505 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8506 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8507 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8508 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8509 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8510 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8511 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8512 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8513 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8514 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8515 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8516 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8517 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8518 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8519 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8520 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8521 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8522 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8523 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3)! - 4 + 5! \times 6! / (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8524 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8525 &:= ((-1 + 2)^3 + 4!) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8526 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8527 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8528 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8529 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8530 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8531 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8532 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8533 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8534 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6 - 7!) \times (8 + 9) \\
8535 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
8536 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8537 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8538 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8500 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8501 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 4! / 5 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8502 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8503 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8504 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8505 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8506 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8507 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8508 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times (5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
8509 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8510 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8511 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!!) \\
8512 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8513 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8514 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8515 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8516 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8517 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8518 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8519 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8520 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8521 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8522 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
8523 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}) \\
8524 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
8525 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8526 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8527 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5! / 4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8528 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4^3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8529 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8530 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8531 &:= -8 \times 7 - 9 - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8532 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8533 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
8534 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4! + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8535 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8536 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8537 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)! \\
8538 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8539 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8540 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 8541 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 8542 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8543 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!) \times (4! + 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8544 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8545 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4! - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8546 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - (5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8547 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8548 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8549 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8550 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8551 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8552 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
 8553 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8554 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8555 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8556 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8557 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8558 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times ((4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 8559 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8560 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8561 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8562 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8563 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8564 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8565 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8566 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8567 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8568 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8569 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8570 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8571 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8572 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8573 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8574 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8575 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8576 &:= -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8577 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8578 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8539 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8540 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - (5! + (4 + 3)!)) / (2 + 1)!! \\
 8541 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8542 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8543 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^{5!/4!} + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8544 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8545 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8546 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 8547 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8548 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8549 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 8550 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8551 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8552 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
 8553 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
 8554 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8555 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8556 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8557 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - 4 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8558 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8559 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! - 6! \times 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8560 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 8561 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8562 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8563 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8564 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8565 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
 8566 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8567 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8568 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8569 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8570 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 8571 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6! / 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8572 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8573 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8574 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 8575 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8576 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 8577 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 8578 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8579 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8580 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8581 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8582 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8583 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8584 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8585 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4) - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8586 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8587 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8588 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8589 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8590 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8591 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8592 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8593 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
8594 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
8595 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8596 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8597 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8598 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8599 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8600 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4^5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8601 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8602 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8603 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8604 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8605 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8606 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - (4 \times 5 - 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
8607 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8608 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8609 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8610 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8611 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8612 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8613 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8614 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8615 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8616 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8617 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8618 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8579 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8580 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8581 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8582 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8583 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8584 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
8585 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6! + 5!)/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8586 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8587 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8588 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8589 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! + 6!)/(5 - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
8590 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8591 &:= -9 + 8 - (7!/6! + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8592 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7!/6! - 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8593 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8594 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8595 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8596 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8597 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8598 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8599 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8600 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8601 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8602 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8603 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8604 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8605 &:= -9 + (8 - (7! - 6! - 5)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8606 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3)/(2 + 1)! \\
8607 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
8608 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
8609 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8610 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8611 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8612 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! + 6!) \times (5 - 4 - 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8613 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8614 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 - 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8615 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8616 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8617 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 - 5! \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8618 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8619 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8620 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8621 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8622 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! + (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8623 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8624 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8625 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8626 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8627 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8628 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8629 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8630 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5 - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8631 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8632 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8633 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8634 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8635 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8636 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8637 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8638 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8639 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8640 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8641 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8642 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8643 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8644 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8645 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8646 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8647 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8648 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8649 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8650 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8651 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8652 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8653 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8654 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4 - (5 - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
8655 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8656 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8657 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8658 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times (4 + 5 - 6)! + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8619 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8620 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6!) \times (5 - 4 - 3) - 2 - 1 \\
8621 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8622 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8623 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8624 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8625 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8626 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8627 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8628 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8629 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8630 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! - 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8631 &:= -9 + (8 - 7) \times 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8632 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8633 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8634 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8635 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
8636 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8637 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8638 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8639 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8640 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)/5 \\
8641 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8642 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8643 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8644 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8645 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8646 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8647 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6 \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8648 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
8649 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8650 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8651 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8652 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8653 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8654 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8655 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8656 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 + 4) \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
8657 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8658 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8659 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8660 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 - 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8661 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8662 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8663 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8664 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8665 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8666 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8667 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8668 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8669 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8670 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8671 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8672 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 - 5) \times (6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8673 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8674 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8675 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8676 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8677 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8678 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8679 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8680 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8681 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4) - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8682 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8683 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8684 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8685 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8686 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8687 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8688 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4 - 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8689 &:= (123 - 4! + 56) \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\
8690 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8691 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8692 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8693 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8694 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8695 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8696 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8697 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8698 &:= -1 \times 2 + ((3!/\sqrt{4})!! + 5) \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8659 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8660 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
8661 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8662 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! - (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8663 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8664 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times (6 + 5) + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8665 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8666 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8667 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
8668 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8669 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8670 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8671 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8672 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4!) \times 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
8673 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
8674 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8675 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6 - (5 + 4) \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8676 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8677 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
8678 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5^4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8679 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! + 6! \times (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8680 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8681 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8682 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8683 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5 + 4) \times (3! + (2 + 1)!) \\
8684 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8685 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! \times 5/4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8686 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3!! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
8687 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8688 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8689 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4!) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8690 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8691 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8692 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8693 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8694 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8695 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6!) - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8696 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8697 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6!)/(5 - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
8698 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!
\end{aligned}$$

$$8699 := -1 + (2 - 3 \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8700 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 - 5 - 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8701 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$8702 := (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$8703 := -1 + 2^{3!} - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8704 := -1 \times 2^{3 \times \sqrt{4}} \times (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8705 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8706 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8707 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8708 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8709 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8710 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8711 := -1 + (2 - 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8712 := (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4! - 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8713 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8714 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8715 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8716 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8717 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8718 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8719 := (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8720 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8721 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8722 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8723 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8724 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8725 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8726 := ((-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8727 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8728 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8729 := -1 - (2 + 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8730 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8731 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8732 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 - (4! \times (5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$8733 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6! + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$8734 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6! + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$8735 := -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8736 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8737 := 1 - (2 - 3) \times 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8 \times 9$$

$$8699 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! + (5 \times 4)^3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8700 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8701 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8702 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8703 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8704 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$8705 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$8706 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8707 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8708 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8709 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$8710 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$8711 := -9 + (8 + (7! - 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8712 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8713 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8714 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 + (5 \times 4)^{3!-2-1}$$

$$8715 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$8716 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8717 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8718 := (-9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8719 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8720 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$8721 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$8722 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times 5 + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8723 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8724 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8725 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8726 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$8727 := -9 + (8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times \sqrt{4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$8728 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4!/3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$8729 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$8730 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$8731 := -9 - (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8732 := -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8733 := -9 - (8 - 7!/6 - 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8734 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8735 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8736 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$8737 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$8738 := (-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - (5! - 6 - 7))) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8739 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$8740 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$8741 := -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8742 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8743 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8744 := (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4^5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8745 := -1 - 2 - (3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8746 := -1 \times 2 - (3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8747 := -1 - (2 \times 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8748 := (-1 - 2 - 3 - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8749 := -1 + 2 - (3! + 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8750 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8751 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$8752 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5)) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8753 := (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$8754 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8755 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8756 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8757 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8758 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8759 := -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 \times 5! \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8760 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8761 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8762 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) - 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$8763 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6!)) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8764 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8765 := (1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 - 5! \times (6 - 8 \times 9 - 7)$$

$$8766 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8767 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (((4! + 5 + 6)/7)! + 8 + 9)$$

$$8768 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 - 6!) + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8769 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8770 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8771 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8772 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8773 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8774 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8775 := (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8776 := -1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 - (5 + 6) \times 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$8738 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8739 := -9 \times (8 - (7!/6 - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8740 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8741 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$8742 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8743 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8744 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + (5! \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8745 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$8746 := -9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$8747 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 - 5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$8748 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8749 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8750 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$8751 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8752 := -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3!)^{2+1}$$

$$8753 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8754 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!))$$

$$8755 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6! - 5!)/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8756 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8757 := -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8758 := -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8759 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8760 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8761 := (-9 - 8) \times (7!/6! - 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8762 := -9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4!) \times 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8763 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8764 := -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$8765 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8766 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6! + 5! - 4))/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8767 := -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8768 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8769 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3!) - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8770 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$8771 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8772 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7! - 6!/5)/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8773 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$8774 := (-9 \times 8 - (7! - 6! - 5)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8775 := (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8776 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8777 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4! - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8778 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8779 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5) - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8780 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8781 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8782 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8783 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! \times 4 - 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8784 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8785 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8786 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5! + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8787 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8788 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8789 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8790 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8791 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8792 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8793 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times 5 - (6! - 7! - 8 - 9)) \\
8794 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
8795 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8796 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8797 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
8798 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! - (5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9)) \\
8799 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3!! / (4 + 5) + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8800 &:= 12 \times 3!! + 4! + 5! + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8801 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8802 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)!)) \times 4 - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8803 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! / (4 + 5) - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8804 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! / (4 + 5) - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8805 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8806 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4 - (5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8807 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8808 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 - 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8809 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8810 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!! / (4 + 5) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8811 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8812 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
8813 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! / (4 + 5)) \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8814 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8815 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times ((4 + 5 - 6)^7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8777 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7! + 6!)/5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8778 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8779 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8780 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 - 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
8781 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8782 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8783 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8784 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8785 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8786 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! + 5) \times 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
8787 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7! + 6!) \times (5 - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
8788 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 - (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
8789 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^{4!(3+2+1)} \\
8790 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5^4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8791 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
8792 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8793 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8794 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7! - 6! + 5)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8795 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8796 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
8797 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8798 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 + 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
8799 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8800 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7! / ((6 - 5 - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
8801 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8802 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8803 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8804 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6! - 5^4 \times 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
8805 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
8806 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4 / (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8807 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8808 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8809 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8810 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8811 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8812 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8813 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8814 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8815 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8816 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 - (5 + 6) \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8817 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8818 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8819 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8820 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8821 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 + 4) \times (5! + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8822 &:= 12 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 + 9 \\
8823 &:= (-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8824 &:= -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 \times 5! - 6 \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8825 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8826 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 \times ((5 - 6 + 7)! + 8 + 9)) \\
8827 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8828 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8829 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3^4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8830 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8831 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8832 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8833 &:= 12 + 3!! \times (56 - 7)/4 - 8 + 9 \\
8834 &:= \sqrt{1 \times 2^{3!}} + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 + 7!/8 \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
8835 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8836 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5! + 6)/4 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
8837 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8838 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8839 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8840 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8841 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5! - 6) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8842 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times ((5 - 6 + 7)! + 8 + 9) \\
8843 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8844 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8845 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8846 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8847 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! - 4) \times (5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
8848 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8849 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8850 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4!)) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8851 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
8852 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
8853 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6!/(7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8854 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! - 6!/(7 - 8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8816 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 - 3!!/(2 + 1)!) \\
8817 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
8818 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8819 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8820 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8821 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7 + 6)! - 5^4) \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
8822 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\
8823 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8824 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3!) + 2 + 1) \\
8825 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8826 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7! - 6! + 5!)/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8827 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6!/5! + 4)^{3!/(2+1)} \\
8828 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8829 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8830 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! + 4!)) \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
8831 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8832 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8833 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8834 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8835 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8836 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 - 5) + 4)^{3!/(2+1)} \\
8837 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 + 3^{(2+1)!} \\
8838 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8839 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
8840 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3!^{2+1}) \\
8841 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8842 &:= -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + (5 \times 4)^3 + 2 + 1 \\
8843 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5^4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)) \\
8844 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8845 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
8846 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5!) \times 4 \times 3/(2 + 1)! \\
8847 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8848 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
8849 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8850 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
8851 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8852 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
8853 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8854 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8855 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8856 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8857 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8858 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8859 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8860 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8861 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8862 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8863 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 8864 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8865 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8866 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8867 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8868 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8869 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8870 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times 3^4 - 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8871 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8872 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8873 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8874 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8875 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8876 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5! - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
 8877 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8878 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 - 4 - 5) \times 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8879 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8880 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8881 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 8882 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! - 6! + 7!)) + 8 + 9 \\
 8883 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8884 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4 + (5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8885 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 8886 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! - 5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8887 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8888 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8889 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\
 8890 &:= -1 - (2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8891 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8892 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)} \\
 8893 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4! + (5 - 6 + 7)!)) - 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8855 &:= -9 + (8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8856 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 8857 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3! + (2 + 1)!)) \\
 8858 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4) + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
 8859 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8860 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8861 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8862 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 8863 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8864 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 8865 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6! + 5!)/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8866 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times 4) + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8867 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8868 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8869 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
 8870 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8871 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8872 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
 8873 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! \times 4) \times 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
 8874 &:= -9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8875 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
 8876 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3!) - (2 + 1)! \\
 8877 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6! + 5!)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 8878 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
 8879 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8880 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8881 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
 8882 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8883 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (4 + 3)!/(5 \times (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8884 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5^{4+(3-2-1)!} \\
 8885 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 - 5!) \times (4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
 8886 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
 8887 &:= -9 - (8 + 7! - 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8888 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8889 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (4 + 3)/5 + (2 + 1)! \\
 8890 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5^4)^{3!/(2+1)} \\
 8891 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8892 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6 + 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 8893 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 + 3!!/(2 + 1)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8894 &:= (-1 + 2^{31} + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 8895 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8896 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
 8897 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8898 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times 5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8899 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8900 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + \sqrt{4^5}) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 8901 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8902 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8903 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8904 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8905 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8906 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! + 6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 8907 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8908 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8909 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8910 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8911 &:= (1 - 2^3) \times (4! - 5) \times 67 \times (8 - 9) \\
 8912 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 8913 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
 8914 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8915 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8916 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8917 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 8918 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times ((4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8919 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 8920 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! - (4 + 5!) \times 6!/(7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8921 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 8922 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 8923 &:= -1 - (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 8924 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 8925 &:= (-1 + 2^{31} \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8926 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8927 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8928 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8929 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8930 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4!) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 8931 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 8932 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - (4 + 5!) \times 6!/(7 - 8 - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8894 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8895 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 8896 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8897 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8898 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8899 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 8900 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - (6! - 5 - 4!) \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 8901 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8902 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4^{3!}) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8903 &:= -9 - 8 \times 4^{3!}/(7 - 6 - 5) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8904 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8905 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8906 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8907 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
 8908 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
 8909 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8910 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8911 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8912 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8913 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8914 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8915 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!/(2 + 1)!) \\
 8916 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
 8917 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
 8918 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + \sqrt{6!/5} \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8919 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 8920 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 8921 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
 8922 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!/4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8923 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6^5 - 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 8924 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8925 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 8926 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - 4!)) \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
 8927 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6^5/(4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 8928 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 8929 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4) - 3!/(2 + 1) \\
 8930 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
 8931 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 8932 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!!/(2 + 1)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8933 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8934 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! - (4 + 5!) \times 6! / (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8935 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4^5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8936 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3!! / (4 + 5) - 6!)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8937 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times (4 - 5! + 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8938 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 \times (4 \times (5 - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
8939 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! / 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8940 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8941 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8942 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8943 &:= -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
8944 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8945 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8946 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
8947 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
8948 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3!! + 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8949 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3!) - 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8950 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3 + 4! + 5!) \times 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8951 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8952 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8953 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3!) - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8954 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3!)) \times (4 \times 5 + 6!) / (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8955 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 - 5 - 6! - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
8956 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5! / 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8957 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!^4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8958 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8959 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8960 &:= (1 \times 2)^3 \times 4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\
8961 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
8962 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8963 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
8964 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3! - 4 \times 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
8965 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3!) - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8966 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8967 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
8968 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 \times 4! + 5 - 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8969 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!! / 4 - 5 + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
8970 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3!) / 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8971 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 \times 6 \times 7 + 89)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8933 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
8934 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! \times (4 + 3) / 5) - 2 - 1 \\
8935 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times (3! \times 2 + 1) \\
8936 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
8937 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - (6! / 5 + 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8938 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8939 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6^5 - 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8940 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8941 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + (5! + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8942 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6! / (5 + 4)) \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\
8943 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8944 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
8945 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
8946 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8947 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
8948 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4!) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
8949 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
8950 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7! / 6! - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8951 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8952 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8953 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8954 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
8955 &:= -9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
8956 &:= -9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - 3!!) - 2 - 1) \\
8957 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5! + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
8958 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times ((6! / 5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8959 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times 3 \times (2 + 1) / \sqrt{4}) \\
8960 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! \times 4 / 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
8961 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
8962 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + ((6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
8963 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
8964 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8965 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
8966 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8967 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
8968 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4! + (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
8969 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8970 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
8971 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times (6 - 5! - 4!) + (3 - 2 - 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$$8972 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!!/4) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$8973 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8974 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8975 := -1 + (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$8976 := (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8977 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8978 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8979 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8980 := -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$8981 := -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$8982 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8983 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$8984 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$8985 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8986 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8987 := -1 - (2 \times 3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8988 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8989 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8990 := -1 - 2 - (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8991 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8992 := (-1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$8993 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8994 := -1 + 2 - (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$8995 := (-2 \times 3 - 1) \times (4! - (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$8996 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - (5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$8997 := -1 - 2 + (3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8998 := -1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8999 := -1 - 2 \times 3!! \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))/4$$

$$9000 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9001 := -1 + 2 + (3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9002 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9003 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - 5! \times (6 \times 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$9004 := -1 - (2 + 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9005 := (-1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9006 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4! + 5)) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9007 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9008 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6! - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9009 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8972 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8973 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8974 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$8975 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8976 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6 - 5) \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8977 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!)$$

$$8978 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$8979 := ((7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8980 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$8981 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8982 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8983 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8984 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!$$

$$8985 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 \times 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8986 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + (5! + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$8987 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8988 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$8989 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8990 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8991 := -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8992 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$8993 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8994 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 - 5 + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8995 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8996 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8997 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 \times 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8998 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$8999 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9000 := -9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9001 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9002 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9003 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!/5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$9004 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9005 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9006 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 - 5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9007 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9008 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9009 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9010 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9011 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9012 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9013 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9014 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9015 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9016 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times (5 + 6)/4 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9017 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times 5! + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9018 &:= ((-1 + 2^3!) \times 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9019 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9020 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9021 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9022 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9023 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9024 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9025 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!!/4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9026 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9027 &:= (-1 - (2 - 3) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9028 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9029 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3^4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9030 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9031 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9032 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9033 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9034 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times (5! + 6) - 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9035 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9036 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9037 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9038 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9039 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6)) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9040 &:= -1 \times (2 \times 3!) \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))/(4 + 5) \\
9041 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))/(4 + 5) \\
9042 &:= (-1 + 2^3!) \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9043 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9044 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9045 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9046 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9047 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9048 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9010 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9011 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) - 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9012 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9013 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9014 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! - (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
9015 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9016 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9017 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
9018 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9019 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
9020 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!^{2+1}) \\
9021 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9022 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9023 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + (5! + 4) \times 3 \times (2 + 1)) \\
9024 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9025 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)!} \\
9026 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6!/5!)^4 - 3!) - 2 - 1 \\
9027 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
9028 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9029 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9030 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5!) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9031 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9032 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
9033 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9034 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9035 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6!) \times (5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9036 &:= (-9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9037 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) \times 3! + (2 + 1)! \\
9038 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5! + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
9039 &:= -9 - (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9040 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5! \times (4 - 3!)/(2 + 1) \\
9041 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9042 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9043 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6^5 - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
9044 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9045 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9046 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
9047 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9048 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9049 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9050 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9051 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9052 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9053 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6)) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9054 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9055 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9056 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9057 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9058 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9059 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!/4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9060 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9061 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9062 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9063 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9064 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9065 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9066 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9067 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 - (6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9068 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9069 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9070 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9071 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4 - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9072 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9073 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9074 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9075 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9076 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9077 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9078 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9079 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9080 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9081 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9082 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9083 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9084 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9085 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9086 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! \times 6/(4 + 5) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9087 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9049 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9050 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3!} - 2 - 1 \\
9051 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9052 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) + (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
9053 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9054 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 - 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9055 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + (6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9056 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3!} + 2 + 1 \\
9057 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9058 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9059 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9060 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9061 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 \times 5 \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9062 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5!)^4 - 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
9063 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9064 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + ((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2+1} \\
9065 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5!)^4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9066 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9067 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9068 &:= (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + (7! - 6!/5) \times \sqrt{4} - 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\
9069 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9070 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9071 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9072 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)!/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9073 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9074 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5!) \times \sqrt{4} - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9075 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9076 &:= (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9077 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6!/5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9078 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9079 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9080 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) - (2 + 1)!! \\
9081 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9082 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5! + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9083 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9084 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9085 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9086 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 - 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
9087 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$9088 := -1 + (2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9089 := -1 - ((2 + 3)^4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9090 := (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9091 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9092 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9093 := -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9094 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9095 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9096 := (-1 - (2 + 3 - 4!) \times 5!/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9097 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9098 := -1 - 2 + 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9099 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9100 := -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9101 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9102 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9103 := -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4! + 5)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9104 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9105 := -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5 + 6!)) + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9106 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times (5! + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9107 := -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9108 := (-1 - (2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9109 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9110 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! - 4^5 - 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9111 := -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9112 := (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9113 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9114 := (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9115 := -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9116 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9117 := -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9118 := -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9119 := -1 - ((2 \times 3)! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9120 := (-1 \times (2 \times 3)! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9121 := -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9122 := (-1 - 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5! - 6! - 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9123 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9124 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9125 := -1 - (2^{3^{\sqrt{4}}} - 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9126 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9088 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$9089 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9090 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9091 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9092 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5! + \sqrt{4} - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9093 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - (5! - 4 - 3)) - 2 - 1$$

$$9094 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9095 := (-9 - 8) \times ((7! - 6! + 5!)/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9096 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9097 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6!/5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9098 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 - 5! + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9099 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9100 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9101 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - (4! - 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9102 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - (5! - 4 - 3)) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9103 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9104 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4! - 3 \times (2 + 1))$$

$$9105 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9106 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9107 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9108 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9109 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! + 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$9110 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9111 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5! + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9112 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9113 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times ((6!/5!)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9114 := (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9115 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9116 := ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 + 5) \times (4 - 3!)^{2+1}$$

$$9117 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! \times (4 + 3)/5 - (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9118 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9119 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5! \times 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9120 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9121 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!$$

$$9122 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9123 := -9 \times (8 - 7!/6 + 5) + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9124 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9125 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9126 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9127 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9128 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9129 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9130 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9131 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9132 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9133 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!^4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9134 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9135 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! - (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9136 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\
9137 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9138 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 - 4!) \times (5! - 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9139 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9140 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9141 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9142 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9143 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9144 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9145 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9146 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!)) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9147 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9148 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9149 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times ((4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9150 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9151 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9152 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9153 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^{(4+5-6)!} + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9154 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9155 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! - (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
9156 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9157 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! - (4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9158 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9159 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 678 + 9 \\
9160 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9161 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9162 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9163 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times (5 + 6 + 7)/4) \times (8 + 9) \\
9164 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9165 &:= (1 + 234) \times (5! - 6 - 78 + \sqrt{9})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9127 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9128 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/6) - (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
9129 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9130 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9131 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9132 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9133 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9134 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9135 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9136 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9137 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
9138 &:= (-9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9139 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9140 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9141 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9142 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3!)^{2+1} \\
9143 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9144 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - (6!/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9145 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 - 4 - 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
9146 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9147 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
9148 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9149 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9150 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! + 5!)/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9151 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
9152 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9153 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)!! \\
9154 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9155 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9156 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9157 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
9158 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
9159 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9160 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9161 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
9162 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9163 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9164 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9165 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9166 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!^4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9167 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!/4 + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9168 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)^4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9169 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9170 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9171 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)) \\
9172 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} + 5!/6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9173 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9174 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9175 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9176 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9177 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9178 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9179 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9180 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9181 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9182 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9183 &:= -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4! - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9184 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9185 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9186 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9187 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9188 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9189 &:= -1 + (2 - 3^4 - 5! - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9190 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4! + 5!) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9191 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9192 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9193 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 - 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9194 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9195 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9196 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9197 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9198 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
9199 &:= -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9200 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9201 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9202 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9203 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4! + 5 - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9204 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9166 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!! \\
9167 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9168 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9169 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9170 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9171 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9172 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9173 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - (5! - 4 - 3)) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9174 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5!/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9175 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9176 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9177 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9178 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9179 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9180 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9181 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9182 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3!)^{2+1} \\
9183 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9184 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9185 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9186 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!) \\
9187 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
9188 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9189 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9190 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9191 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9192 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9193 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9194 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
9195 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9196 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!) \\
9197 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9198 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9199 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9200 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! + (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)) \\
9201 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!) \times 4!/5! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9202 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
9203 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
9204 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9205 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9206 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4 - 5!) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9207 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9208 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9209 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9210 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/5 \\
9211 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9212 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9213 &:= -1 + (2 + (3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9214 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + (5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9215 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9216 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9217 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9218 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9219 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9220 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9221 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4! + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9222 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9223 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9224 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9225 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9226 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9227 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9228 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9229 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4 - 5) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9230 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9231 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times (6 + 7)/5! \times (8 + 9) \\
9232 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9233 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9234 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9235 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9236 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9237 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! - 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9238 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9239 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9240 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9241 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9242 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9243 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5 - 6! - 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9205 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9206 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
9207 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7! + 6!)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9208 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9209 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9210 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9211 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5! - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9212 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9213 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!) \times 4!/5! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9214 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6!)/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9215 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9216 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9217 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9218 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
9219 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9220 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9221 &:= -9 - (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9222 &:= (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9223 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9224 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6^5 + 4!/3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
9225 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9226 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9227 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9228 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
9229 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times (5!/4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9230 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9231 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9232 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)! \\
9233 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9234 &:= -9 \times ((-7 \times 6 + 8) \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9235 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9236 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9237 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9238 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
9239 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9240 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9241 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9242 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9243 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$9244 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times (5! - 6) - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9245 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9246 := (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$9247 := (-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9248 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (6 + 7)/5!) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9249 := -1 - 2 \times (3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7))) - 8 - 9$$

$$9250 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7))) - 8 - 9$$

$$9251 := -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9252 := (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9253 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9254 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9255 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9256 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9257 := -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9258 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9259 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9260 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9261 := -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9262 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$9263 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9264 := (-1 + 2 + 3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9265 := -1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9266 := (-1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9267 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9268 := -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times 6 + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$9269 := -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4! + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9270 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! + 4!) \times (5! \times (6 - 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9271 := ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9272 := (-1 + 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9273 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9274 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$9275 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9276 := -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4 - 5)) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$9277 := -1 + ((2 - 3 + 4)!! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9278 := (((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9279 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9280 := -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9281 := -1 + (2 - 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9282 := (-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9244 := -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6 - 5 - 4)! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9245 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9246 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6!/5 + 4)) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9247 := -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9248 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9249 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9250 := -9 + 8/(7 - 6 - 5) + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9251 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!))$$

$$9252 := 9 \times (87 \times \sqrt{6!/5} - 4 - 3! - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9253 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9254 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3!)^{2+1}$$

$$9255 := -9 - 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9256 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9257 := -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9258 := (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9259 := -9 - 8 - (7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9260 := -9 - (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9261 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9262 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9263 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6!/5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9264 := -9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9265 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 - 5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9266 := -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$9267 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!))$$

$$9268 := -9 + 8 + (7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$9269 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9270 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9271 := -9 + ((7 \times 6 + 8)/5)^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9272 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!))$$

$$9273 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9274 := -9 + (8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$9275 := -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9276 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5^{4!/(3+2+1)})$$

$$9277 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9278 := -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9279 := -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9280 := -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

$$9281 := -9 \times 8 - 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9282 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9283 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)/5! & 9283 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9284 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! \times 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9284 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9285 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 9285 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9286 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 & 9286 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9287 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4) + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9287 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9288 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 9288 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9289 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 9289 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9290 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 + 5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 9290 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9291 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 9291 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9292 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 9292 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9293 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 9293 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!) \\
9294 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9294 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9295 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9295 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9296 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 9296 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6! - 5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9297 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9297 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
9298 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 9298 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - ((6 + 5 - 4!) \times 3!! - 2 - 1) \\
9299 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9299 &:= -9 - (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9300 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9300 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
9301 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9301 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9302 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7))) + 8 + 9 & 9302 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9303 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9303 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9304 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9304 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4 - 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9305 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9305 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9306 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9306 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9307 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9307 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9308 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9308 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9309 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9309 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
9310 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9310 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9311 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 9311 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9312 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 9312 &:= -9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9313 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 9313 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9314 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) & 9314 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9315 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)! \times (6 + 7)/5!) \times (8 + 9) & 9315 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9316 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 9316 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 \times 5) + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9317 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4! + 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 9317 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9318 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9318 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9319 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 9319 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9320 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 & 9320 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
9321 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 9321 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6^5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
9322 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5 - 6!)) - 7! - 8 - 9 & 9322 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6!/5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$9323 := (-1 + (2 \times 3!)) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9324 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9325 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9326 := -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9327 := (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9328 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9329 := -1 + ((2 \times 3!) + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9330 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9331 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9332 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9333 := -1 - (2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9334 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9335 := -1 + (2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9336 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9337 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9338 := (-1 - 2 - 3!! \times (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9339 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$9340 := -1 - 2 - 3!! \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9341 := -1 \times 2 - 3!! \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9342 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9343 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9344 := -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9345 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9346 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$9347 := (-1 - 2 - 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9348 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9349 := (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9350 := -1 + (2 - 3!!) \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9351 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 + 5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9352 := -1 - 2 \times 3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9353 := (-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9354 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9355 := -1 + ((2 \times 3!) - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9356 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9357 := -1 - ((2 - 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9358 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9359 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9360 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + (4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9361 := -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9362 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9323 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9324 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6!/5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9325 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9326 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5!/4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$9327 := -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9328 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9329 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5!/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9330 := (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9331 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9332 := -9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9333 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9334 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9335 := -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9336 := -9 - 8 - 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9337 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9338 := -9 + (8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$9339 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9340 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9341 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - (5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$9342 := -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9343 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!$$

$$9344 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9345 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9346 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9347 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9348 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9349 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9350 := -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9351 := -9 - (8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9352 := -9 + 8 - 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9353 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9354 := (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9355 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9356 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9357 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9358 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - (5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$9359 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)!!$$

$$9360 := (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6! \times 5! / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9361 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9362 := (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9363 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9364 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3! - 4 - 5)!!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9365 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9366 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9367 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9368 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
9369 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9370 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9) \\
9371 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9372 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9373 &:= (1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!!) \times (-5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9374 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9375 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4! \times 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9376 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! - 4 - 5)!! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9377 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 5)!! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9378 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9379 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (-6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9380 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9381 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9382 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9383 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9384 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9385 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9386 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9387 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9388 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9389 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9390 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9391 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9392 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4^{5+6-7} \times (8 + 9) \\
9393 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9394 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9395 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9396 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9397 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9398 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9399 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9400 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9401 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9363 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9364 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9365 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9366 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9367 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9368 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
9369 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9370 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
9371 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! \\
9372 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9373 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9374 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9375 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9376 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)!/6 - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9377 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
9378 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9379 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9380 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3!) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9381 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7)^{\sqrt{6+5-4-3}}) \times (2 + 1) \\
9382 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4 - 3)! + 2 + 1) \\
9383 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9384 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5! + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9385 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9386 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9387 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6^5/4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9388 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 + 4! + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9389 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9390 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9391 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)) \\
9392 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5^4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9393 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6!/5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9394 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9395 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9396 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9397 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9398 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
9399 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9400 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! \times 5/(4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9401 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5! \times 4)/(3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9402 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9403 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9404 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9405 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 \times (5! + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9406 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!) + 4! + 5 - (6! - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9407 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4 \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9408 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} - 4 \times (5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9409 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9410 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9411 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3!) + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9412 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3!) + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9413 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9414 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9415 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! - 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9416 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9417 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9418 &:= ((-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9419 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9420 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9421 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9422 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9423 &:= -1 + 2^{3!+4} - (5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9424 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3!) + 4! - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9425 &:= (-1 - (2 \times 3!) - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9426 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9427 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times ((4 - 5 + 6)! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9428 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9429 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9430 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) - 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9431 &:= -1 + (2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9432 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9433 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9434 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9435 &:= -1 - 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9436 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9437 &:= -1 - (2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9438 &:= (-1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9439 &:= -1 + 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9440 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9402 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9403 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9404 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9405 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9406 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9407 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9408 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9409 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7 - 6)! + 5! - 4!)^{3!(2+1)} \\
9410 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9411 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!/5!) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9412 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\
9413 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9414 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times (5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)/6! \\
9415 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9416 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9417 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9418 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9419 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + (5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9420 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5^4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9421 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9422 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9423 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9424 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9425 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9426 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9427 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9428 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times (3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9429 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9430 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9431 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9432 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7!/(6 + 5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9433 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9434 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9435 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)! \\
9436 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5!) \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9437 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9438 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9439 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6!/(5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9440 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9441 &:= -1 + ((2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9442 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9443 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4^5 - 6! - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9444 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9445 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9446 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9447 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9448 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9449 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9450 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9451 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9452 &:= -1 \times (2^{3!} + 4) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9453 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9454 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9455 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9456 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9457 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9458 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9459 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9460 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9461 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9462 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9463 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9464 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
9465 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9466 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9467 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9468 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9469 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7))) - 8 - 9 \\
9470 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9471 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9472 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9473 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9474 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9475 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3^4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9476 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9477 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9478 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9479 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9441 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 - (5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\
9442 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9443 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9444 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9445 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9446 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
9447 &:= -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9448 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
9449 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 + (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
9450 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7!/6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9451 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9452 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 \times 5) - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9453 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!/6 + 5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9454 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9455 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - (6 - 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9456 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5^{4/(3+2+1)}) \\
9457 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9458 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5^4) + 3!/(2 + 1) \\
9459 &:= -9 \times (8 + (7 + 6!/(5 - 4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
9460 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9461 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9462 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! + \sqrt{4}) \times (\sqrt{3^2 \times 1})! \\
9463 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9464 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9465 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! \times 3!!/((5 + 4) \times (2 + 1)!) \\
9466 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9467 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
9468 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6) \times (5 - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9469 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
9470 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9471 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6!) + 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9472 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9473 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9474 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9475 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! - 4 + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9476 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9477 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9478 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 \times (4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9479 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9480 &:= (-1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9481 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3!) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9482 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
9483 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9484 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9485 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9486 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9487 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
9488 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
9489 &:= -1 - (2 - 3! - 4 - 5) \times (6! - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9490 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4 - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9491 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9492 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9493 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3!) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9494 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9495 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9496 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9497 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9498 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9499 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9500 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9501 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9502 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9503 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9504 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9505 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9506 &:= -1 + (2 + 3! \times 4!) \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9507 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9508 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5!) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9509 &:= -1 - ((2 - 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9510 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9511 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)! - 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9512 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9513 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5 \times 6!) / (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9514 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times 5! \times 7 \times (8 + 9) / 6 \\
9515 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4 \times 5! \times 7 \times (8 + 9) / 6 \\
9516 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9517 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9518 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9480 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9481 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! - 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9482 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9483 &:= 98 + 7! + 6! \times (4 + 3!!) / 5! + 2 - 1 \\
9484 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
9485 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5! + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!! \\
9486 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9487 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9488 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9489 &:= (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9490 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9491 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times (5 - 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9492 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
9493 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9494 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3!^{2+1} \\
9495 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)! - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
9496 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9497 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3!^{2+1} \\
9498 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9499 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9500 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
9501 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6! / (5 + 4) + 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9502 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! / 4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9503 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9504 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9505 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9506 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9507 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
9508 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3!^{2+1} \\
9509 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5^4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9510 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9511 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9512 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4! - 3!!) / (2 + 1) \\
9513 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! + 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
9514 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7! / ((6 - 5 - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)! \\
9515 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9516 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! + \sqrt{6! / 5}) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9517 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9518 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times 3! / (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$9519 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)! \times (8 + 9)/(5 + 6 + 7)$$

$$9520 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9521 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9522 := (-1 - 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$9523 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$9524 := (-1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9525 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$9526 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$9527 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! + 4! + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9528 := (-1 + 2 + 3!^{\sqrt{4}} \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9529 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9530 := -1 + ((2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9531 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9532 := -1 + (2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!)) \times 6 + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$9533 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9534 := -1 - 2 \times (3! \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9535 := -1 - 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 \times 6!)/(7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9536 := -1 \times 2^{3!} \times (4! - 5 \times 6!)/(7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9537 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9538 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6! - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9539 := -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9540 := -1 + 2 \times (3 - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9541 := (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) - 8 - 9$$

$$9542 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)! \times 6/5! - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9543 := -1 - 2 - (3! - 4! + 5) \times (6! + 7 + 8) - 9$$

$$9544 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9545 := (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5! - 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9546 := -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! \times (5 + 6) + 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9547 := -1 - (2 - 3! - 4!) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9548 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9549 := -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5 + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$9550 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) - 8 - 9$$

$$9551 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9552 := -1 - (2 + 3)! - (4! + 5! - 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9553 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/5 - 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9554 := (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9555 := (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9556 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9557 := -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9558 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9519 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9520 := (-9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9521 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9522 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!)/4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9523 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9524 := -9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 - 4!) \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$9525 := (7 \times 6 - 9 - 8) \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9526 := (-9 - 8) \times 7!/((6 - 5 - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9527 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9528 := -9 \times 8 + (7!/6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9529 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9530 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9531 := -9 + (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9532 := -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$9533 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9534 := (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9535 := -9 - 8 \times (7!/6! - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9536 := (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9537 := (-9 - 8) \times (7!/(6 - 5 - 4) - 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$9538 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9539 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9540 := (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6) \times 5! \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$9541 := -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9542 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)!$$

$$9543 := -9 + (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9544 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5! \times 4) + 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9545 := -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9546 := -9 - (8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$9547 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!!/(2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9548 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9549 := (-9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5!)) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9550 := (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1))$$

$$9551 := -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 - 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9552 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9553 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9554 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9555 := (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9556 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9557 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9558 := -9 \times (8 + (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9559 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9560 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9561 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 - (5! - 6) \times 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9562 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9563 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9564 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9565 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9566 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! - 5 - 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9567 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9568 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9569 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9570 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9571 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5!) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9572 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9573 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9574 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9575 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9576 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5 / 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9577 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9578 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times 4 \times (5! - 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9579 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9580 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9581 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9582 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! / (4 + 5 - 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9583 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9584 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9585 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9586 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9587 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9588 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9589 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9590 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9591 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9592 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)! \times 6 / 5! - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9593 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9594 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9595 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9596 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 - 5 - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9597 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9598 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9559 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 - 6 - 5!) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9560 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4^{3!}) / (2 + 1) \\
9561 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4^3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
9562 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\
9563 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 \times 5 + 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9564 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9565 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
9566 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4^{3!}) / (2 + 1) \\
9567 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) / 4 \\
9568 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - (4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!!)) \\
9569 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9570 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9571 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5! + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9572 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9573 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
9574 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5! + 4! - 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
9575 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \\
9576 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - 4! - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9577 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
9578 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9579 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
9580 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9581 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
9582 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7! \times (5 - 4!) / 6! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9583 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9584 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
9585 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! \times (5 + 4)) / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9586 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 - 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9587 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9588 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9589 &:= (-7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times (5! - (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\
9590 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! / 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9591 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9592 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 3!! / ((5 + 4) \times (2 + 1)!) \\
9593 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
9594 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9595 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9596 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9597 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 + 5! \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9598 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times 4) \times 3! / (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9599 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9600 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5! \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
9601 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9602 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9603 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9604 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 \times 5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9605 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9606 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9607 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3 - 4) \times (5 - 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9608 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9609 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\
9610 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9611 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9612 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9613 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!^{4+5-6} - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9614 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^{4+5-6} - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9615 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9616 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9617 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9618 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9619 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9620 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9621 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9622 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!)) - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9623 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4 \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9624 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5) \times (7 + 8 + 9)/6 \\
9625 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9626 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9627 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9628 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9629 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9630 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9631 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9}) \\
9632 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9633 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9634 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9635 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4^5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9636 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9637 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9638 &:= -1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9599 &:= -9 + 8 + (7!/6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9600 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9601 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9602 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9603 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9604 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9605 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9606 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9607 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9608 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/5 + 4 - 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
9609 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9610 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
9611 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6! + 5) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9612 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 - 6 + 5)!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4 \\
9613 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9614 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5^4) + 3!^{2+1} \\
9615 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9616 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5! - 4!)/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
9617 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times ((6 - 5!) \times 4 \times 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
9618 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7! - 6 - 5 - 4)/3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9619 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9620 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 + 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9621 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)!) \\
9622 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7!)/((6 - 5 - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
9623 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9624 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6 + 5) \times (4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9625 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3!!) + (2 + 1)! \\
9626 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9627 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3!)) \times (2 + 1) \\
9628 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - 4! - 3)) + (2 + 1)! \\
9629 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 + 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\
9630 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9631 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + 5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9632 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9633 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
9634 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6! + 5!)) \times (4 - 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9635 &:= -9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) - 3!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9636 &:= -9 - (8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9637 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9638 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9639 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9640 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! + 4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9641 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4 \times (5! - 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9642 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9643 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9644 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5! - 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9645 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9646 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9647 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5! - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9648 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 \times 4! - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9649 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4! - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9650 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9651 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9652 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9653 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9654 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9655 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9656 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9657 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9658 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9659 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9660 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
9661 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\
9662 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9663 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5 \times 6!)/(7 + 8 + 9) \\
9664 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9665 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^{4+5-6} - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9666 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9667 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9668 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
9669 &:= -1 - 2 - (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9670 &:= -1 \times 2 - (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9671 &:= -1 - ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9672 &:= -1 \times ((2 \times 3)! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9673 &:= -1 + 2 - (3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9674 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5 - (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
9675 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 - 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9676 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
9677 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9678 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9639 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9640 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
9641 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9642 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9643 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9644 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6!/5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\
9645 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4)) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
9646 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 - 4! - 3 - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9647 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6! + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9648 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9649 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times 3! - (2 + 1)! \\
9650 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)) \\
9651 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9652 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
9653 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5! \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9654 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9655 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9656 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
9657 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! \times (4 + 3)/5) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9658 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9659 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9660 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5!/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9661 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) \times 3! + (2 + 1)! \\
9662 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3!!) - 2 - 1 \\
9663 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9664 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9665 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9666 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9667 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - 4!)) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9668 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) - (2 + 1)! \\
9669 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4)) \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
9670 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5! - 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)! \\
9671 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9672 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7 - 6!) \times (5 - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
9673 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9674 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9675 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
9676 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4 - 3!!/(2 + 1)) \\
9677 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) + 2 + 1 \\
9678 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$9679 := -1 - (2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9680 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4^5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9681 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9682 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!^{4+5-6} - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9683 := -1 + (2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9684 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9685 := (-1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9686 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9687 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9688 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9689 := (-1 + (2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9690 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9691 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9692 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9693 := -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9694 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9695 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9696 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9697 := -1 - (2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9698 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9699 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9700 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9701 := -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9702 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9703 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9704 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9705 := -1 + 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9706 := -1 - (2 + 3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)!) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9707 := (-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)!/5!)) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9708 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 - 5 - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9709 := -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/(5 \times 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9710 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/(5 \times 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9711 := (-1 - 2 - 3!! - 4!) \times (5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9712 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - (4 + 5) \times 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9713 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9714 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9715 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9716 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9717 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$9679 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - 4!)) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9680 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9681 := -9 - (8 + 7) \times (6!/(5 + 4) - 3! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9682 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - 4!)) + 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9683 := -9 + 8 + 7! + (6 \times (5 + 4) + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9684 := (-9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6) \times (5 - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9685 := -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9686 := -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9687 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9688 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9689 := -9 + 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9690 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1))$$

$$9691 := -9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9692 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3!)) - 2 - 1$$

$$9693 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9694 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9695 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9696 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9697 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9698 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3!)) + 2 + 1$$

$$9699 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9700 := -9 \times 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9701 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$9702 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - (4! - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9703 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9704 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9705 := -9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$9706 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + 5! \times (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9707 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9708 := -9 \times (8 - 7! + 6 \times 5!)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9709 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4!/3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9710 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9711 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! \times (5 + 4)/(3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9712 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9713 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!$$

$$9714 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5 \times 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9715 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9716 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9717 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5! \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1)$$

$$9718 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$9719 := -1 + (2 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$9720 := (-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9721 := -1 + 2 + 3!! \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)/4$$

$$9722 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9723 := -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9724 := 1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8)/9$$

$$9725 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9726 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9727 := -1 - (2 - 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9728 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9729 := -1 + (2 - 3 \times 4!) \times (5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9730 := (-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4!) \times 5! - 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9731 := -1 - 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9732 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 + 5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9733 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9734 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9735 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9736 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9737 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9738 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9739 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9740 := (-1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9741 := -1 - 2 - (3! - 4 \times 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9742 := -1 \times 2 - (3! - 4 \times 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9743 := -1 + (2 + 3 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9744 := (2 \times 3 - 1 + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9745 := -1 + 2 - (3! - 4 \times 5) \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9746 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! + 5! + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9747 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9748 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9749 := -1 - (2 - 3!!/(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9750 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9751 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9752 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9753 := -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9754 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9755 := -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9756 := (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5!) \times \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$9718 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9719 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9720 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9721 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$9722 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9723 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)) \times 4! \times 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9724 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9725 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 + (3 - 2 - 1)!$$

$$9726 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5 \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9727 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - (6 + 5!)) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9728 := -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6! + 5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$$

$$9729 := -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9730 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9731 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4!/3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9732 := -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9733 := -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9734 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9735 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 + 5) \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9736 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9737 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4!) \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$9738 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9739 := -9 - 8 + (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9740 := -9 + 8 + (7!/6! + 5! \times (4! + 3)) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9741 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!/5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9742 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9743 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9744 := (-9 - 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9745 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))^{5!/4!-3} + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9746 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + 3!!) - 2 - 1$$

$$9747 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$9748 := -9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9749 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$$

$$9750 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9751 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9752 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + 3!!) + 2 + 1$$

$$9753 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4! + 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9754 := -9 - 8 - (7 - (6 + 5!)) \times 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9755 := -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5) \times 4!) \times 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9756 := -9 \times (8 \times 7 + (6 - 5!)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9757 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9758 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4!) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9759 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!/4 - 5 - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9760 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/(5 \times 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9761 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9762 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5!)) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9763 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!) + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9764 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9765 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9766 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5!/6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9767 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9768 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3! \times (5 \times 6 + 4)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9769 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9770 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4! + 5! - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9771 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9772 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9773 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3 \times ((4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\
9774 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9775 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9776 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!/4 - 5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9777 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/(5 \times 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9778 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4)!/(5 \times 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9779 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9780 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
9781 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9782 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9783 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
9784 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
9785 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
9786 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
9787 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3) + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9) \\
9788 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9789 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9790 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9791 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9792 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9793 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times (5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9794 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9795 &:= -1 - (2 - 3^4) \times (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9757 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times (5 + 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9758 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9759 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7!/6 + (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
9760 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3!!/(2 + 1)) \\
9761 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
9762 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9763 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9764 &:= (-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9765 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5!) \times (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
9766 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6! - 5) + 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!! \\
9767 &:= -9 + (8 - 7! + 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9768 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9769 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9770 &:= -9 + 8 - (7 - (6 + 5!) \times 4!) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
9771 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9772 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9773 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!! \\
9774 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9775 &:= -9 - 8 - (7! - 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9776 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/(5 + 4)) \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
9777 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6!/5)/4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9778 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9779 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9780 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9781 &:= -9 - (8 \times (7 - 6! + 5!) - (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!) \\
9782 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4! + 3^{(2+1)!}) \\
9783 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9784 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9785 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9786 &:= -9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
9787 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
9788 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5!/4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9789 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9790 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! + 4^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
9791 &:= -9 + 8 - (7! - 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9792 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9793 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6^5 - 4! + 3 \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9794 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7! + 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9795 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!
\end{aligned}$$

$9796 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! - 6 - 7) - 8 - 9$	$9796 := (-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
$9797 := (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$	$9797 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) - 2 - 1$
$9798 := (-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9)$	$9798 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
$9799 := -1 + 2 + 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9)$	$9799 := -9 - (8 + 7! - 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9800 := ((-1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4 \times 5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$	$9800 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
$9801 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))$	$9801 := -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
$9802 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9$	$9802 := (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! - 4!) \times 3!/(2 + 1)$
$9803 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$	$9803 := -9 + (8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9804 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$	$9804 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times 5!/4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
$9805 := -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6)! - 7! + 8 + 9)$	$9805 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
$9806 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6)! - 7! + 8 + 9)$	$9806 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!$
$9807 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + (5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))$	$9807 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!$
$9808 := -1 - (2 - 3 - 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)!) \times (8 + 9)$	$9808 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4!/3 + (2 + 1)!)$
$9809 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$	$9809 := 98 \times (6! - 5 \times 4)/7 + 3 \times (2 + 1)$
$9810 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$	$9810 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
$9811 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$	$9811 := -9 - 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9812 := -1 + 2 - (3! - 4) \times (5! + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9$	$9812 := -9 + 8 + (7 + (6 + 5!) \times 4!) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$
$9813 := -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$	$9813 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4) - 3!!) + 2 + 1$
$9814 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9$	$9814 := -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!)$
$9815 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$	$9815 := -9 + (8 - 7 \times 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9816 := -1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! - 5! - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$	$9816 := (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 9) \times 5!/4 + 3 + 2 + 1$
$9817 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$	$9817 := -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times 4 \times 3!!/(2 + 1)$
$9818 := (-1 - 2 - 3 + 4) \times (5! - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$	$9818 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!)$
$9819 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))$	$9819 := -9 \times (8 - 7 \times (6!/5 + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!))$
$9820 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! + (4 \times 5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$	$9820 := (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$
$9821 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$	$9821 := (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!) \times (4^3 - 2 - 1)$
$9822 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$	$9822 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$
$9823 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6)! - 7!) - 8 - 9$	$9823 := -9 - 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9824 := -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4!) \times (5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$	$9824 := (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3!) - (2 + 1)!$
$9825 := -1 + (2 - 3 \times 4! \times (5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$	$9825 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
$9826 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)$	$9826 := (-9 - 8 - 7! + 6!/5) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9827 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9$	$9827 := -9 + 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9828 := (-1 - (2 + 3)! + 4) \times (5! + 6!)/(7 - 8 - 9)$	$9828 := (-9 + 8) \times (7! - 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9829 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 \times 7 - 8 - 9))$	$9829 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4) + (3 - 2 - 1)!$
$9830 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! - 6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	$9830 := (-9 + 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9831 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9))$	$9831 := -9 - ((8 - 7 + 6)! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
$9832 := 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9)$	$9832 := -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$
$9833 := (-1 + 2 + 3!)! - (4! \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9)$	$9833 := (-9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)$
$9834 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5!/6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$	$9834 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$
$9835 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$	$9835 := -9 - 8 - (7! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$

$$9836 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9837 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9838 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + \sqrt{4})! \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$9839 := -1 + 2 \times 3! \times (4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9840 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5! - 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9841 := -1 + 2 - (3!! + 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9842 := -1 \times 2 \times (3!! \times (4 - 5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9843 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9844 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9845 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9846 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9847 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9848 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! - 6 - 7)) - 8 - 9$$

$$9849 := -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9850 := (-1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4! \times (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9851 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9852 := (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9853 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9854 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! - 6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9855 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9856 := (-1 \times 2 \times 3!! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9857 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9858 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9859 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + (5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$9860 := ((-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9861 := -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9862 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9863 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$9864 := ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9865 := -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9866 := -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9867 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! - 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9868 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + (4 - 5 + 6)! - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9869 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9870 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9871 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9872 := 1 \times 2 + (3!!/4 + 5 \times 6) \times (7 \times 8 - 9)$$

$$9873 := -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5 - 6)! - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9874 := (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5! + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9836 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! - 4 + 3!!/(2 + 1)!$$

$$9837 := -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6! - 5!)/4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9838 := (-9 + 8 + 7! - (6 - 5 + 4)!) \times 3!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9839 := -9 + 8 - (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9840 := (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5! - 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$9841 := -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9842 := (-9 + 8 - 7 \times 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9843 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5! - (4 + 3)!) + 2 + 1$$

$$9844 := -9 - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9845 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 \times 4 \times 3!!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9846 := (-9 - (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5! + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9847 := -9 - (8 + 7 \times 6! - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9848 := -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6!/(5 + 4)) \times 3!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9849 := -9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9850 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9851 := -9 + 8 - (7! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9852 := (-9 + 8) \times (7! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9853 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9854 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9855 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9856 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5)! + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9857 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!$$

$$9858 := (-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9859 := -9 - (8 + 7! + 6 - 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9860 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9861 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9862 := (-9 - 8 - (7! - 6 - 5!)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9863 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9864 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9865 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$9866 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$9867 := -9 + (8 - 7 \times (6 - 5! \times \sqrt{4})) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9868 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9869 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9870 := (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9871 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9872 := (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - 5 \times (4! + 3!))/(2 + 1))$$

$$9873 := (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$9874 := -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9875 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
9876 &:= -1 - (2 - (3!! - 4 - 5! - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9877 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9878 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
9879 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9880 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9881 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! + 5!/6 - 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
9882 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
9883 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9884 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + (5 - 6) \times (7! - 8 - 9)) \\
9885 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) - 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9886 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9887 &:= -1 - (2 - 3 \times (4! + 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9888 &:= 12 \times 4! \times (5! + (6 - 7) \times 8 - 9)/3 \\
9889 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
9890 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9891 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9892 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3!^4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\
9893 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! - (4^5 - 6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
9894 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! - 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9895 &:= -1 + 2 + (3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)!) \times (8 + 9) \\
9896 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9897 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9898 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!!/(4 + 5) - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9899 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - (5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9900 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9901 &:= -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9902 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
9903 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9904 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9905 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9) \\
9906 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9907 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4! - 5 - 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
9908 &:= -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9909 &:= 1^2 \times 3!! \times (56 + 7 - 8)/4 + 9 \\
9910 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9911 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
9912 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4^5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9913 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5 + 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9875 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9876 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!/6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9877 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 + 3 + (2 + 1)! \\
9878 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
9879 &:= -9 - (8 - 7!/\sqrt{6!/5}) \times 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9880 &:= (-8 \times 7 - 9) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4! - 3!)/(2 + 1) \\
9881 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)! \\
9882 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9883 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6^5 - 4! + 3!)/(2 + 1)! \\
9884 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9885 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
9886 &:= (-9 - 8 - 7! - 6 + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9887 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1) \\
9888 &:= -9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6!/5) + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
9889 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9890 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5!) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\
9891 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times (5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9892 &:= -9 \times (8 - 7 - 6! - 5) + 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!! \\
9893 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9894 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 + 5! - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9895 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5! - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9896 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9897 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9898 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9899 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\
9900 &:= -9 \times (-7 \times 6 + 8) \times 5!/4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9901 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4) + (3 - 2 - 1)! \\
9902 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 - (4! - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!!)) \\
9903 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9904 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9905 &:= (98 - 7 + 65 \times 4!) \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
9906 &:= -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9907 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9908 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9909 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 \times (5 + 4))) \times \sqrt{3^{(2+1)!}} \\
9910 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9911 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5! - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9912 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (\sqrt{5! + 4!} - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9913 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6!/5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9914 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 & 9914 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5) \times 4 \times 3 / (2 + 1)! \\
9915 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) & 9915 &:= -9 - (8 - (7! - 6 \times (5 + 4))) / 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
9916 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 & 9916 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9917 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 & 9917 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6! - 5! - 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9918 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3! - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 9918 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5! / 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9919 &:= -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 & 9919 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9920 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times ((4 + 5 - 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) & 9920 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!) / 5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
9921 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 - 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 & 9921 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9922 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 - 5 - 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 & 9922 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - (6! / 5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9923 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5 - 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 & 9923 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9924 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! - 5 - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9924 &:= -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6! + 5!) / 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9925 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9925 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) - 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9926 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9926 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 - 5) \times (4! / 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
9927 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9))) & 9927 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9928 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7! - 89) & 9928 &:= (-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6! - 5 - 4 - 3!!) / (2 + 1)!) \\
9929 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 9929 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! / 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!) \\
9930 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9930 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9931 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 & 9931 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6!) / 5 + 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9932 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 & 9932 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! / 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9933 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 9933 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (5 + 4 + 3) / 6 - 2 - 1 \\
9934 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 9934 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9935 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4! - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 9935 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! + 6^5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
9936 &:= (12 + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 567 - 8 - 9) & 9936 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 5! / (6 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9937 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! \times (5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 9937 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9938 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 9938 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! / 5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1) \\
9939 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 9939 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9940 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 \times 4! - 5 - 6 - 7!) - 8 - 9 & 9940 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9941 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 9941 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6! / 5 - (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!) \\
9942 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 & 9942 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times (6! / 5! - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
9943 &:= -1 \times ((2 + 3)! \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9) & 9943 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5) + 4^{3+2+1} \\
9944 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 - 5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 & 9944 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5^4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
9945 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4 + 5 + (6 + 78) \times 9) & 9945 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9946 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9946 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
9947 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! + 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9) & 9947 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!) \\
9948 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times 4! + 5 + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) & 9948 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3) / (2 + 1)! \\
9949 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3!! / (4 + 5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9949 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\
9950 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!! / (4 + 5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9950 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9951 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 9951 &:= -9 - (8 \times 7 - 6!) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9952 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9) & 9952 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6!) - 5! + 4^{3+2+1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$9953 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$9954 := (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4! + 5!) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9955 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9956 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9957 := -1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9958 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9959 := -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9960 := (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4! + 5! - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9961 := -1 - 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9962 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9963 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9964 := -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9965 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$9966 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9967 := (-1 \times 2 - 3!) \times (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$9968 := -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9969 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9970 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4! + 5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$9971 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) - 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9972 := -1 - 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9973 := -1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9974 := -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5 - 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9975 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$9976 := -1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - (5! - 6 - 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$9977 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! - (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9978 := (-1 \times 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9979 := (-1 \times (2 - 3 - 4) \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9980 := -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! \times 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$9981 := -1 - 2 + (3!! - 4^5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9982 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4^5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9983 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) - 5!) + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9984 := (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9985 := -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4^5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$9986 := -1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4 - 5)^6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9987 := -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4! - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$9988 := (-1 - (2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$9989 := -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$9990 := (-1 - 2) \times (3!!/4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9991 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$9953 := -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 - 5! + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9954 := -9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6!/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9955 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9956 := -9 + 8 + 7! - (6 + 5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$9957 := (7 \times 6 - 9 + 8) \times 5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

$$9958 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) - 2 - 1$$

$$9959 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5!) + 4^{3+2+1}$$

$$9960 := (-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5!) \times \sqrt{4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)}$$

$$9961 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1)!!$$

$$9962 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! - (5! - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)$$

$$9963 := (-9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 - 5!)) + (4 + 3)! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$9964 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$9965 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9966 := -9 \times (8 - (7! - 6! + 5!))/4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9967 := (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!$$

$$9968 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9969 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!) - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$9970 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

$$9971 := -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - (5! - (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9972 := -9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6) \times 5!)/4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9973 := -9 - (8 + 7 - 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9974 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 - 3!! - (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9975 := -9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5!/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9976 := -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$9977 := -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times (5! - 4!) + 3!/(2 + 1)$$

$$9978 := (-9 - 8 - 7!/(6 - 5 - 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9979 := (-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5 \times 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9980 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6!) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)!$$

$$9981 := -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6! - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9982 := ((-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9983 := -9 + 8 \times ((7! + 6!)/5 + 4 + 3) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$9984 := (-9 \times 8 - 7 \times 6! + 5!) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9985 := -9 + (8 - 7 \times (6! - 5)) \times (4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$9986 := (-9 + 8 + 7!/6!)! + 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

$$9987 := -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6! - 5!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)/4$$

$$9988 := -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 - (4! - 3!! - (2 + 1)!)!)!$$

$$9989 := -9 + 8 + (7! - (6 + 5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$9990 := -9 \times (8 + 7 - 6 - 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$9991 := -9 - (8 - 7 \times 6!/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9992 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 - 5 - 6)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9993 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! + (4 + 5) \times 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\
9994 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 - (4 + 5) \times 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
9995 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 + 6 - 7)!) \times (8 + 9) \\
9996 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
9997 &:= -1 - 2 + (3! + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
9998 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
9999 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3 + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)} \\
10000 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3! + 4)^{5!/(6+7+8+9)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9992 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 + 5 + (4! - 3)^{2+1} \\
9993 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - \sqrt{6!/5} + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9994 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
9995 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
9996 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
9997 &:= 9876 + 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 \times 1)! \\
9998 &:= -9 - 8 - (7 + 6) \times (5!/4! - 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
9999 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - 6!/5! + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\
10000 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7! - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

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References

- [1] J.S. Madachy, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.
- [2] H.E. Dudeney, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [3] H. Heinz, Magic Squares, Magic Stars & Other Patterns, <http://recmath.org/MagicSquares/miscnum.htm>.
- [4] E. Friedman, Math Magic Archive, <https://erich-friedman.github.io/> or <https://erich-friedman.github.io/mathmagic/index.html>.
- [5] R. Knott, The Mathematical Magic of the Fibonacci Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibmaths.html>
- [6] R. Knott, Fibonacci and Lucas Number Calculator, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibCalcX.html>
- [7] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 0 to 11111 in terms of Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9, Jan. 2014, pp.1-161, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479>.
Site link: Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers – The 10958 Problem,
a. <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2018/11/16/crazy-representations-of-natural-numbers-the-10958-problem>.
b. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=893>.
- [8] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000, **Zenodo**, January 18, 2019, pp. 1-224, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543626>
- [9] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 30000, **Zenodo**, February 3, 2019, pp. 1-276, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2556036>– Revised in Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 40000, **Zenodo**, November 03, 2021, pp. 1-541, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642776>

- [10] Inder J. Taneja, Natural Numbers From 1 to 20000 in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 3, 2019, pp. 1-491, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2575093>.
- [11] Inder J. Taneja, Pyramid-Type Representations of Natural Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 5, 2020, pp. 1-213, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3637662>
- [12] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 40000, **Zenodo**, November 03, 2021, pp. 1-541, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642776>
- [13] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 40001 to 60000, **Zenodo**, November 03, 2021, pp. 1-541, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642826>
- [14] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 60001 to 80000, **Zenodo**, November 03, 2021, pp. 1-537, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642896>
- [15] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 80001 to 100000, **Zenodo**, November 03, 2021, pp. 1-533, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642929>
- [16] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 100001 to 120000, **Zenodo**, December 11, 2021, pp. 1-527, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773381>.
- [17] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 120001 to 140000, **Zenodo**, December 11, 2021, pp. 1-524, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773384>.
- [18] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 140001 to 160000, **Zenodo**, December 11, 2021, pp. 1-526, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773386>.
- [19] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 160000 to 180000, **Zenodo**, December 11, 2021, pp. 1-521, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773388>.
- [20] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 180000 to 200000, **Zenodo**, December 11, 2021, pp. 1-526, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773390>.
- [21] Inder J. Taneja, Representation of Numbers from 1 to 10000 in Terms of Palindromic Digits 2022-2202, **Zenodo**, January 02, 2022, pp. 1-238, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5813778>.
- [22] Inder J. Taneja, Representation of Numbers from 1 to 20000 in Terms of Palindromic Digits 1357-9-7531, **Zenodo**, January 06, 2022, pp. 1-266, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5826240>.
- [23] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 200001 to 220000, **Zenodo**, January 08, 2022, pp. 1-529, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831196>.
- [24] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 220001 to 240000, **Zenodo**, January 08, 2022, pp. 1-534, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831198>.
- [25] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 240001 to 260000, **Zenodo**, January 08, 2022, pp. 1-532, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831200>.
- [26] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 260001 to 280000, **Zenodo**, January 08, 2022, pp. 1-537, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831206>.
- [27] Inder J. Taneja, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 280001 to 300000, **Zenodo**, January 08, 2022, pp. 1-535, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831208>.
- [28] Inder J. Taneja, Pyramid-Type Representations of Natural Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 5, 2020, pp. 1-213, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3637662>.

- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Representation of Numbers from 1 to 10000 in Terms of Palindromic Digits 2022-2202, **Zenodo**, January 02, 2022, pp. 1-238, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5813778>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Representation of Numbers from 1 to 20000 in Terms of Palindromic Digits 1357-9-7531, **Zenodo**, January 06, 2022, pp. 1-266, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5826240>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and S-gonal Values - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 6, pp. 1-115, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a06.pdf>.
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and S-gonal Values - II, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 7, pp. 1-115, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a07.pdf>.
- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Natural Numbers in Terms of S-gonal (Pentagonal and Hexagonal) Values, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 18, pp. 1-101, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a18.pdf>.
- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Natural Numbers From 1 to 20000 in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers. **Zenodo**, February 3, 2019, pp. 1-491, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2575093>.
- [36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.
- [37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>.
- [38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574136>.
- [39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Fibonacci Sequence Values, **Zenodo**, January, 14, 2024, pp. 1-261, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10501468>.
- [40] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, January, 16, 2024, pp. 1-259, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516039>.
- [41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Square Function, **Zenodo**, March 28, 2024, pp. 1-259, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10892480>.
- [42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Cubic Function, **Zenodo**, March 30, 2024, pp. 1-259, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10899695>.
- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Factorial and Square Root, **Zenodo**, April 07, 2024, pp. 1-260, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10938234>.
-